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REVIEW OF THE JOB SEARCH WORKSHOPS PROGRAM

TECHNICAL REPORT

CITIZENSHIP AND IMMIGRATION CANADA, ONTARIO REGION

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Review of the Job Search Workshops Program - Technical Report

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1. About This Document

This document, submitted as a companion document to the Job Search Workshops (JSW) Program Review, describes the program review methodology and includes detailed findings from several of the data collection channels.

For a summary of the findings from the review and recommendations please refer to the Job Search Workshops (JSW) Program Review.

2. Detailed Methodology

The methodology used for the JSW Program Review that was undertaken by RealWorld Systems from December 2006 through May 2007 was consistent with the Treasury Board Secretariat's policy on Results Based Management and Accountability Frameworks, Citizenship and Immigration Canada's [CIC's] Contribution Accountability Framework (CAF), and the Canada Ontario Immigration Agreement (COIA) Strategic Framework.

In keeping with evaluation guidelines and best practice, RealWorld Systems used a range of data sources to enhance the validity of the findings. Multiple data sources allowed the evaluation team to address the evaluation questions from different angles.

The JSW Program Review was carried out in four phases:

- **PHASE 1:** In the first phase, RealWorld Systems refined the research questions and desired outcomes of JSW through a review of background materials and consultations with CIC and the JSW Advisory Group.
- **PHASE 2:** In Phase 2, the research literature on effective service models and success factors in achieving the desired outcomes of JSW was reviewed and subject matter experts were identified and interviewed.
- **PHASE 3:** In this phase, RealWorld Systems collected data about JSW through multiple channels including a survey of JSW Service Providing Organizations, site visits, statistical analysis and other methods.
- **PHASE 4:** In the last phase of the project the collected data were analyzed to develop the final report in consultation with CIC staff and the JSW Advisory Group and other stakeholders.

A detailed description of the methodological components of each phase follows. Detailed findings from several of the components are included in the appendices.

2.1. PHASE I

The first step in the JSW Program Review was to orient the evaluation team, create a detailed evaluation plan with input from CIC staff and other stakeholders as selected by CIC and to define specific research questions to guide the review. These objectives were accomplished as follows:

2.1.1. Reviewed background documents

RealWorld Systems conducted a review of background documents to ensure that the evaluation team had a good understanding of the JSW program and its various forms of delivery. Background document review also provided information that addressed some of the evaluation questions, reducing the need for more time-consuming and expensive data collection efforts. Among the background documents reviewed were the final report from the 2001 JSW review, JSW guidelines, the JSW manual, the JSW program terms of reference, and other policy and research papers published on government sites and on settlement.org.

2.1.2. Met with CIC and JSW Advisory Group

RealWorld Systems met with CIC and the Advisory Group early in the project in order to learn their concerns, assumptions, questions, data needs, priorities and intentions for the evaluation and to gather their input and insights on the JSW program as it is delivered throughout the Ontario region.

In addition, RealWorld Systems met with CIC and the JSW Advisory Group several times over the course of the project in order to solicit their assistance in guiding the project. Specifically, the members of the Advisory Group were asked to contribute their knowledge and expertise to the methodological design and into the development of recommendations. Their guidance lends additional credibility to the evaluation results.

The JSW Advisory Group had representation from major stakeholders including JSW Service Providers, Human Resources and Skills Development Canada (HRSDC), Ministry of Training, Colleges and Universities (MTCU), City of Toronto, Economic Development Division, Ontario Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration, OCASI and CIC. Advisory Group members are listed in Appendix A.

2.1.3. Defined Research Questions

Good evaluation practice and current international guidelines on evidence-based policy require that program reviews include a review of the research literature on the effectiveness of the service model being studied. Preferably, program activities should be supported by research evidence such as best practice analysis or

qualitative information. To deal with this strategic objective the Canada Ontario Immigration Agreement Strategic Framework and Logic Model were used to orient the review.

A core strategic objective of the Canada Ontario Immigration Agreement (COIA) Strategic Framework is to design, fund and administer settlement and language training services based on how well the programs support key outcomes as they are defined in the COIA Settlement and Language Services Logic Model. The key outcomes for all Citizenship and Immigration Canada - Ontario Region (CIC) and the Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration (MCI) funded activities for settlement services and language programs in Ontario, including JSW, are defined in the COIA logic model.

RealWorld Systems reviewed the extent to which JSW activities were likely to produce the desired outcomes of this logic model.

As a first step RealWorld Systems developed a list of research questions linked to the most pertinent primary, secondary and tertiary short term and intermediate outcomes as defined in the COIA logic model.

Primary outcomes were defined as those directly related to JSW's core objective (i.e., helping newcomers to obtain employment by providing job preparation and job searching skills training, labour market information and other services). Secondary outcomes included those related to essential features of the JSW service - for example, information and referral linkages. Tertiary outcomes included those related to program management - for example, program administration & support, program monitoring, and so on.

As the search for evidence progressed, research questions were added and refined and used to guide subsequent phases of evidence collection specific to the JSW Program (as described in Phases II and III below).

2.2. PHASE II

The objective of Phase II was to look for evidence that would:

- Provide guidance for refining and prioritizing specific research questions,
- Identify key success factors associated with finding and applying for employment
- Identify specific measures that would be good indicators of desired outcomes,
- Support the JSW Program design (its theory of change),
- Identify promising practice, and
- Ultimately support program improvement recommendations.

To accomplish the objective for this phase, RealWorld Systems:

2.2.1. Reviewed the literature

RealWorld Systems reviewed the relevant international research literature including articles from academic journals, key government reports, results from the Longitudinal Survey of Immigrants to Canada and the results of four related literature reviews that RealWorld Systems had carried out in recent years. The results of the literature review were used to develop an internal discussion document that was used by the evaluation team (including the JSW Advisory Group) to develop hypotheses about how JSW might be more effective and to focus additional data collection methods to find evidence that either supported or challenged the findings from the literature. The internal discussion document is included in Appendix B.

2.2.2. Solicited input from employment services experts

RealWorld Systems consulted with 7 employment services experts to solicit their input on key success factors, best practices and indicators. The interviews tested hypotheses as they emerged from the other data sources and ensured that our assumptions were questioned, challenged and examined at each stage of the analysis. Findings from this data collection channel are incorporated in the Final Report and in the literature review document (described above). A list of the experts interviewed is included in Appendix G.

2.3. PHASE III

In this phase, RealWorld Systems reviewed JSW program activities, outputs and outcomes in relation to the set of key success factors, indicators and research questions identified in Phases I and II.

Specifically this phase had the following objectives:

- Investigate how the program currently operates and describe the context in which it operates
- Seek evidence from CIC and JSW Program Service Providers about the extent to which particular activities led to desired outcomes
- Identify important successes, promising practices or issues that warrant replication or further study

RealWorld Systems met these objectives by using the following methods:

2.3.1. Conducted agency staff surveys

RealWorld Systems surveyed JSW Service Providing Organizations (SPOs) at two points during the review. The first, in March was via a 2-page questionnaire filled out by agency staff at the annual conference of JSW facilitators. Results from this questionnaire are included in Appendix C.

The second survey was conducted in April via a 16-page survey and was sent to all JSW service providing agencies. The survey included a mix of open and closed ended questions on a broad range of program related topics including several that sought to identify particularly effective service elements, models and agencies. These agencies or models were flagged for deeper assessment (as described in Section 2.3.3. below). To ensure a high response rate, RealWorld Systems contacted non-respondents to encourage their participation. An 81% response rate was achieved. Detailed findings from the survey as well as the survey protocol and list of respondents are included in Appendices D, E and F respectively.

2.3.2. Reviewed service statistics for JSW SPO's across Ontario

RealWorld Systems summarized and reviewed applicable service statistics from sources such as the statistical reports developed for the program in 2005/2006 as identified in the RFP, and other sources as identified during the course of the evaluation. The information gleaned helped to place the service in context in terms of its scope or reach (e.g., the number of clients served by the various agencies). Relevant findings are described in the Final Report.

2.3.3. Conducted in-depth reviews of 4 agencies

RealWorld Systems conducted 4 site visits with agencies identified in the earlier phases of the project as having the most effective services. During these site visits we:

- Attended selected workshops to observe classroom facilitation and activities and to gather information related to environmental conditions.
- Interviewed staff at the agencies in order to identify or confirm the types of models that were being delivered, and delve in some depth into the processes that went into their services. We gathered sufficient information about the models so that we could describe the key components and fit the models into meaningful categories for analysis. In addition, we looked into the effectiveness and applicability of the monitoring data being collected in the system. As part of this review RealWorld Systems requested and where possible, reviewed any data on client surveys of satisfaction and effectiveness that agencies had collected.

- Met with a sample of clients at each of the agencies and interviewed them on their satisfaction levels and their ideas and recommendations for improvement.

2.4. PHASE IV

2.4.1. Analyzed data and developed recommendations

During the analysis phase, RealWorld Systems tested emerging recommendations with CIC, the JSW Advisory Group and other stakeholders before finalizing them. This interactive analysis and testing process identified risks, allowed the Program Review to incorporate feedback, added credibility to the findings, and makes the final recommendations easier to implement. Summary findings as well as recommendations are included in the Final Report.

Appendix A - JSW Advisory Group Members

Name - Title <i>(In Alphabetical Order)</i>	Organization
Bettencourt, Elisete - Program Advisor	Citizenship and Immigration Canada - Settlement Directorate, Ontario Region
Brown, Susan - Senior Policy Advisor	Labour Force Development, Economic Research and Business Information, City of Toronto
Di Zio, Josie - Senior Director	Planning and Program Development, COSTI Immigrant Services
Dossal, Yasmine - Director, Social Services	COSTI Immigrant Services
Vane, Jenny	Ontario Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration - Settlement and Diversity Unit
Le, Khanh - Manager	Finance and Resource Development, Ontario Council of Agencies Serving Immigrants (OCASI)
Owen, Timothy - Director	World Education Services (WES)
Tong, Haorong	Ministry of Training, Colleges and Universities
Tsegaye, Mengis - Director	LASI World Skills, Ottawa (SPO)
Webb, Hazel - Director	Community Programs, Community Micro-Skills Development Centre

Appendix B - Results from Literature Review - Internal Discussion Paper

Internal Discussion Paper

Job Search Workshops Program Review

Preliminary Research Findings

February 28, 2007

Prepared By:

Lori Criss Powers

Foreword

RealWorld Systems has been engaged by Citizenship and Immigration Canada, Settlement / Intergovernmental Affairs Directorate (CIC) to undertake a review of the Job Search Workshops Program (JSW).

The major objective of the review is to describe and review JSW as it is currently delivered across Ontario and to make recommendations around improving the delivery of the program.

As part of the review, RealWorld Systems is in the process of conducting a literature scan using the Scholars Portal to locate peer reviewed journal articles and Google searches to locate key reports from credible online sources. The literature scan is focused on reviewing job search related material specific to immigrant populations but because the literature is limited in this area, information referring to other populations is included.

To supplement the literature scan RealWorld Systems has so far consulted with four employment services experts to solicit their input on key success factors and best practices.

The purpose of this report is to present the findings from the research conducted thus far. The findings are preliminary. Further information regarding JSW, the job search process and best practices will be included in the interim and final reports for this project.

This is an internal discussion document meaning that the audience for the report is limited to the JSW Program Review team, including staff at Citizenship and Immigration Canada (the sponsor of the review), the JSW Advisory Group and the review team at RealWorld Systems. The report acknowledges the extensive knowledge and experience of the audience and does not offer in-depth background information or lengthy explanations except where considered necessary to frame the findings.

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Introduction

The key outcomes for all Citizenship and Immigration Canada and Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration funded activities for settlement services and language programs in Ontario are defined in the Canada Ontario Immigration Agreement (COIA) Settlement and Language Services Programs Strategic Plan¹ and Logic Model.

The logic model (shown in Figure 1) includes two closely related short term outcomes for newcomer employment bridging programs².

The first short term outcome states that newcomers should have the skills necessary to find and apply for employment.

The second states that newcomers should be linked to local labour markets. Newcomers are considered 'linked' either directly or indirectly to local labour markets when they:

- Have a job in the local labour market relevant to their skills and interests (direct link),
- Are part of a community of practice, an association or employment related network of some kind (indirect link),
- Are participating in employment related educational activities (indirect link), and/or
- Are being certified, accredited or otherwise recognized as a legitimate practitioner of their profession in Canada (indirect link).

Note

The Job Search Workshop Program (JSW) is a Citizenship and Immigration Canada (CIC) funded employment bridging program.

The core objective of the JSW program is consistent with the COIA logic model. The objective of the program (as stated on the program website at <http://www.jswontario.org>) is to facilitate the employment of new immigrants to Ontario (the key objective of the second short term outcome described above) and familiarizing them with effective job-search practices and techniques in Canada in a culturally appropriate manner (the first short term outcome described above).

¹ See <http://www.cic.gc.ca/english/pub/coia-plan.html> for an electronic version of the COIA Strategic Plan.

² A bridging program is defined broadly as one that assists immigrants to enter the job market more quickly (FuturEd, 2004).

COIA Settlement and Language Services Programs Logic Model

Figure 1: COIA logic model

Labour Market Integration

The process for achieving successful integration³ into the Canadian labour market is complex. Newcomers looking to enter the labour market will have different career paths and different support needs based on their particular circumstances (Gardner Pinfold Consulting Economists, 2004). Skilled immigrants⁴ for example may need to have their education accredited in Canada or they may need to obtain bridge training⁵ before they can obtain employment in their chosen profession, while others may follow a more direct path.

The following diagram illustrates a typical labour market integration path for newcomers to Canada.

³ Successful integration is defined as obtaining paid employment consistent with a newcomer's skill, education and experience (sometimes referred to as 'full' employment). Refer to intermediate outcomes shown in Figure 1.

⁴ Here skilled newcomers are defined as "individuals who have immigrated to Canada with post-secondary education and/or professional training and experience" (Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council, 2006).

⁵ Bridge training is defined as any training or education that fills the gaps between a newcomers' current skills/education and Canadian occupation requirements.

Towards Canadian Labour Market Integration

Figure 2: Towards labour market integration

Looking at the diagram in Figure 2 and reading from the top down, a direct link to the Canadian labour market is established when a newcomer is employed in a paid job consistent with their skills, education and experience (often referred to as full employment). Alternatively the newcomer is employed in a job *not* consistent with their skills, education and experience (they are underemployed) or they are unemployed (not shown). Continuing down, we see that in order for a newcomer to be fully employed in Canada they usually must either have some Canadian education, some relevant paid Canadian work experience (a paradox) and/or recognition of their foreign education and experience.

Recognition of foreign education and experience can come from an “official” body (e.g., a certification, accreditation or licensure body) and/or the employer. In other words, newcomers, especially skilled newcomers, who are unable to have their foreign experience and education ‘officially’ recognized will either need to obtain some Canadian education and/or Canadian work experience or will end up under- or un-employed (there are exceptions that are not shown in the diagram⁶).

Looking at the diagram in Figure 2 from the bottom up you will see a newcomer seeking full employment in Canada should be ‘employment ready’ and possess the skills and knowledge necessary to conduct an independent job search. Furthermore they should possess the skill to market themselves to employers through resumes, interviews, applications and/or employer administered tests. If newcomers are able to do this successfully they may avoid under- and unemployment⁷.

Because this paper is concerned with employment bridging programs that offer job searching services the diagram includes detail around the ‘employer determined’ path (the arrows along the

⁶ The diagram does not include all possible routes to successful labour market integration; for example, integration through self-employment is not shown.

⁷ Figure 2 attempts to illustrate a path for successful labour market integration but it does not include reference to all of the many factors that must be addressed in order for a newcomer to obtain full employment. For example there are other important factors to consider, including the following:

- A job must be open that is consistent with the jobseeker’s expectations for employment
- The employer must be willing to accept diversity in their work force

These types of circumstantial (or environmental) factors are important but are not elaborated on in this paper.

path are bolded and shown in blue). The remainder of this paper focuses discussions in terms of this path (for example the paper discusses employment readiness but does not discuss issues related to accreditation).

Note

The Job Search Workshops Program is just one of the many services provided by CIC and others to help newly arrived permanent residents integrate into the Canadian labour market. Refer to Appendix A for a small sample of labour market integration services available to newcomers in Ontario.

See Lim, Lo, Siemiatycki & Doucet (2005) for a more comprehensive list of newcomer services in the Greater Toronto Area. See also Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council (2006) and Ontario Administration of Settlement and Immigration Services (2002).

Job Searching Defined

'Job searching' is defined by Saks (2005) as a process that "involves gathering information in the pursuit of potential job opportunities, generating and evaluating job alternatives, and choosing a job from the alternatives". Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales (1989) use the term 'job hunting' and describe it as a process for finding work after a career decision has been made.

For the purposes of this paper we will define job searching in terms of the key set of behaviours (preparatory and active) that job seekers need to exhibit in order to find and apply for employment (Moynihan, Roehling, LePine & Boswell, 2003; Saks, 2005)⁸. Each of these behaviours are associated with multiple activities as follows:

[1] Preparatory job search activities include:

- Gathering job search information (including information related to the job search process and employer requirements for desired types of occupations)
- Identifying appropriate employers and job opportunities (using various independent job search methods including networking, reviewing newspaper or online advertisements)
- Preparing resumes and cover letters

[2] Active job search activities include:

- Sending out resumes and cover letters (solicited or unsolicited), making cold calls or visiting employers
- Completing applications (or employer administered tests)
- Interviewing with prospective employers
- Evaluating job offers

This definition implies that the act of 'job searching' does not include those behaviours, activities or supports associated with attaining a state of employment readiness (to be discussed fully later) nor does it include supported job search methods (e.g. job matching services) or actually obtaining employment.

The following diagram illustrates the boundaries implied by the definition:

⁸ According to Saks (2005) there are other job search behaviours that job seekers engage in during a job search including job source usage, job search effort and job search intensity. But these 'behaviours' are considered to be measures of the strength or quality of the preparatory and active job search behaviours.

Figure 3: Boundary implied by the ‘job searching’ definition

Note

The Job Search Workshops Program is a short term intervention (typically supplying between 16 and 24 hours of service to each newcomer student) that provides 'job searching' related services. We deduce from the current curricula, guidelines and prior evaluation, that the underlying definition for 'job searching' is currently rather broadly defined. For example in some cases, job development or matching services are provided to students.

Reaching agreement on a precise definition for 'job searching' will be critical for making recommendations for JSW Program improvement as there are several service designs that can be envisioned for JSW depending on how the program wishes to define itself. In order to reach agreement on a definition, program stakeholders should take into account other labour market integration services currently available to newcomers (see Appendix A for a small sample), evidence found in the literature, JSW resources and current capacity to deliver specific types of services, and newcomers' needs.

The JSW Program Review conducted by Sparks & Wolfson in 2001 asked JSW students exiting workshops "to identify the most useful topics covered in the workshops - many clients indicated resumes and interviews. They also felt that these were areas where more time was needed. In particular, clients were interested in more opportunities to practice interviews and work on their resumes. A number of clients identified labour market information as being the least useful topic. Both professionals and non-professionals wanted additional support with resume writing. Professionals wanted stronger links to employers through co-op, placements and job postings. Non-professionals identified interest in more access to counselors and facilitators." Sparks & Wolfson go on to say that when "program coordinators were asked if the JSW program was sufficient to enable newcomers to go on and benefit from other employment programs and services that are available to the general public 54% responded 'no'. The following explanations were provided by the coordinators:

- The evening, weekend models provide more time for clients to internalize materials; the day program is too short.
- Many clients need more one-on-one counselling.
- Need an intermediate step between JSW and the labour market.
- Clients need more job counselling. Job placement, job finding clubs would help.
- Most other employment services are not designed to meet the needs of newcomers.
- Newcomers are ineligible for a lot of other programs.
- Many graduates not ready to go with mainstream programs.
- The 3-day program is jammed with content; that's why individual follow-up is required.
- Need more time to deal with resumes and interviews.
- Workshop needs to be longer.
- Many participants need one-on-one counselling and career planning.
- Maybe 30% can move on; rest need further supports.
- Mainstream services are not yet adequate to deal with needs of newcomers.

Job Search Success Defined

In order to determine the effectiveness of job search behaviours or interventions that seek to affect them, we need to have a clear understanding of what we mean by success. Research indicates that the effectiveness of job search depends heavily on the criteria used to measure success (Brasher & Chen, 1999; Saks, 2005).

In 1999 Brasher & Chen conducted a study that attempted to understand job search success from the job seekers' perspective. The study included a review of the literature to identify the most commonly used success indicators and the drawbacks for each. The job search success indicators discussed included the following:

Job Search Success Indicators	Drawbacks
Obtaining a job within a specified period of time	Timeframe is arbitrary Does not take job quality into account (job seekers facing employment pressure may take a less than desirable job)
Search duration (how long job searchers take to find a job)	Does not take job quality into account
Job quality - salary	Does not take labour market variations into account Differences in salary should be attributed to the choice of profession rather than to success in the search process
Job quality - fit (between job and education, skills, interests) ⁹	Poor match between person (e.g., skills) and environment (e.g., job demand) might have a functional impact on job involvement or strain reactions May not be a primary objective of all job seekers

⁹ As in the COIA Settlement Logic Model shown in Figure 1 paid employment consistent with education, skills and experience is often used as a proxy measure for successful economic integration. See also Canadian Council for Refugees, 1998.

Job quality - satisfaction ¹⁰	<p>Causes of job satisfaction are complex and intertwined</p> <p>Empirical evidence suggests that job satisfaction tends to be associated with age and tenure</p> <p>Self-report of job satisfaction may vary depending on the time at which employees respond</p>
Number of interviews / job offers	Some job seekers may focus on a narrow range of jobs in a particular locale and seek relatively few interviews

Table 1: Job search success indicators

Basher and Chen’s study examined two theoretical models that depicted structural relations among nine success indicators often employed in the job search literature. They found weak relationships among them and concluded that the meaning of job search success needed to be carefully considered and studied further.

Since 1999, when Basher and Chen conducted their study, numerous other studies have been conducted to test various indicators of success. For example, Saks, conducting his study six years after Basher and Chen, found that the relationship between job search behaviour and employment status is not as direct as had been previously suggested in the job search literature. The findings of his study suggest an unfolding process in which job search behaviour leads to job interviews, job interviews lead to job offers, and job offers result in employment. The following diagram illustrates:

Figure 4: From job search to employment

¹⁰ According to Munoz de Bustillo & Macias (2005) job satisfaction is not a good indicator of the quality of work. They find ‘unequivocally’ that job satisfaction has no apparent or relevant relation to other “objective indicators of job quality”.

The results of Saks' study suggest that job search behaviour has an indirect effect on employment status through job interviews and offers, and thus the best predictor of employment status is the number of job offers that a job seeker receives.

In terms of practice, the results of Saks study suggest "that career counselors and job search training programs should emphasize job interviews as a critical job search outcome as well as the ability to convert job interviews into offers."¹¹ Saks recommends that "job seekers should be instructed on how to set goals for their job search and in particular, setting goals for interviews as a distinct and more immediate goal than the more distal goal of obtaining employment". He goes on to state that "job seekers should receive extensive training on interviewing and this should probably involve boosting their interview self-efficacy and lowering their interview anxiety. Further, previous research has shown that career exploration activities predict interview readiness, and both career exploration and interview readiness predict interview performance and interview outcomes."

Note

Currently JSW relies on indicators related to obtaining a job within a specified period of time (n = 3 months) and job quality / fit (employment in chosen field) to judge effectiveness.

Factors Related to Successful Job Searching

The literature identifies several factors related to job search success. These include factors related to the job seeker's job search intensity, effort, usage and self-efficacy.

Job Search Intensity and Effort

¹¹ There is evidence to suggest that low-intensity job search assistance programs have small effects when considering employment as the primary outcome (Van Den Berg & Van Der Klaauw, 2006).

Studies have shown that job search intensity (the frequency with which job seekers, during a set period of time, engage in preparatory and active job search activities) predicts job search success (Kanfer et al., 2001; Mace, Atkins, Fletcher & Carr, 2005). Job search intensity has been found to be the best predictor of the number of job interviews and offers obtained (Saks, 2005). As well, job search effort (the amount of energy, time, and persistence that a job seeker devotes to their job search) has also been positively related to job search success (Saks, 2005).

Job search intensity is important but experts agree that it is not the only factor to consider (Laroche, 2007; Singer, 2007)

Job Source Usage

Studies linking job search success and job source usage (the means by which job seekers learn about job opportunities e.g., methods such as networking, reviewing advertisements, cold calling, etc.) have mixed results (Rankin, 2003; Theodore & Mehta, 2001). Some of the literature, expert opinion and popular wisdom suggest that informal sources result in faster or better employment (e.g., Kunz, 2005) others find no such advantage (e.g., Lamba, 2003; Saks, 2005; Wanber, Kanfer & Banas, 2000)¹². According to Saks (2005) the use of informal sources may be more likely to result in obtaining a job or a better job but there is evidence to suggest that formal sources “result in higher-level occupations and jobs that are more closely related to previous training”. It is worth noting that in Saks’s (2005) study job seekers who used informal sources received fewer job offers and as a result, they were less likely to find employment¹³.

A study in the UK tested different job search strategies (including job centres, social networking, advertisements and etc.) and found that the choice of search methods explained virtually none of

¹² A interesting study conducted by Addison & Portugal (2001) suggests that there are different time and money costs associated with different methods thus some may be used more frequently than others.

¹³ The effect size was small. Saks speculates that “it is possible that informal sources are not as effective today for several reasons. In particular, both the job search and selection process have become more rigorous and extensive over the years. As a result, job seekers need to devote much more time and energy in their job search than they might have in past decades. Similarly, the selection process has advanced over the years and many organizations now use a battery of valid selection techniques. Thus, an over reliance on informal sources such as personal contacts may no longer be sufficient for obtaining employment. In other words, job seekers need to do much more than simply rely on informal sources when searching for employment and they also need to perform well on selection tests and in structured interviews.”

the difference in job finding probabilities between UK born Caucasians and different immigrant populations. They found that immigrants in the UK do worse from all forms of job search. The authors suggest that this may be due to “their human capital being less suited to the UK labour market, their search for more restricted types of employment or employer preferences restricting their likelihood of success” (Frijters, 2005).

A study by Wanberg, Kanfer & Banas (2000) found that “although networking is useful, claims should not be made that this method is superior to traditional job-search techniques”. Wanberg, et al., do recommend however that “job-search professionals continue to encourage networking as a job-search method, as networking does indeed lead individuals into new jobs” (in their study approximately 36% of the time). However, they state “job-search professionals should communicate to individuals that networking is best used as a complement to other job-search methods”.

In any case, the research seems clear that the more job methods that are employed by the job seeker the more likely it is that they will obtain employment (Mace, Atkins, Fletcher & Carr, 2005; Saks, 2005).

Job Search Self-efficacy

In his study, Saks found that job search self-efficacy (a job seeker’s confidence in his or her ability to successfully perform a variety of job search activities) was a significant predictor of job search success. This finding is confirmed by several other studies. Interestingly, Saks’s study also found that job seekers who have low job search self-efficacy are more likely to accept a job offer rather than to continue their search and that this potential under-utilization of skills¹⁴ is less likely with high self-efficacy job seekers. Job seekers with high self-efficacy are less likely to accept the first job offer but instead continue their search in order to maximize their success (Saks, 2005).

An issue related to job search intensity is that of maturation. Maturation means that people tend to get better at the job search process as they go along which in turn increases their self-efficacy (Singer, 2007). As well the literature indicates that training in job search skills (e.g., training in preparing for and participating in interviews) increases self-efficacy, which in turn leads to more extensive job search behaviour (Gawronski, 2001; Ward & Riddle, 2003).

¹⁴ “Under-utilization of immigrant skills may be defined as any employment of immigrants in work below a level of skill at which they could function as effectively as native-born Canadians.” (Reitz, 2001)

Prerequisites for Successful Job Searching

Job searching interventions are considered more effective when job seekers are ‘ready’ for employment (Ward & Riddle, 2006). In order to be considered ‘ready’ for employment an individual must have the ability to communicate orally in the official language of the workplace, literacy skills (document use, reading, numeracy), problem-solving, social judgment and team-work skills, sufficient understanding of career interests and the ability to overcome or cope with employment barriers. The following discussion briefly explores the concept of employment readiness.

The term ‘employability’ or ‘employment readiness’, applicable to those already employed as well as those unemployed, has been used in a variety of contexts and has been given different meanings in the literature (McQuaid, 2002). Ward & Riddle (2006) use the term ‘employment readiness’ and define it as “being able, with little or no outside help, to find, acquire, and keep an appropriate job as well as being able to manage transitions to new jobs as needed”. McQuaid (2002) uses the term ‘employability’ and defines it as “an individual’s ability to gain initial employment, maintain employment, move between roles within the same organization, obtain new employment if required, and (ideally) secure suitable and sufficiently fulfilling work”.

Many in the literature define employability in terms of the skills necessary to achieve it. For example, the Australian Department of Education, Science and Training undertook a project to develop an approach to support the universal recognition and recording of employability skills. The final report from that project defines employability skills as those “skills required not only to gain employment, but also to progress within an enterprise so as to achieve one’s potential and contribute successfully to enterprise strategic directions” (Allen Consulting Group, 2004). Overtoom (2001) defines employability skills as “transferable core skill groups that represent essential functional and enabling knowledge, skills, and attitudes required by the 21st century workplace”. The Conference Board of Canada defines employability skills as the critical skills needed in the workplace. Human Resources and Skills Development Canada (HRSDC) uses the term ‘essential skills’ and defines it as “the skills needed for work, learning and life”¹⁵.

Employability Skills

¹⁵ HRSDC notes that while similar, essential skills are not exactly the same as employability skills which often are defined to include such factors as an individual’s attitudes and behaviours (HRSDC, 2006). See http://srv600.hrdc-drhc.gc.ca/esrp/english/general/Understanding_ES_e.shtml for descriptions of each skill.

Employability skills are grouped into various categories by organizations and in the literature. For example the Conference Board of Canada (2000) groups employability skills into 3 categories and 11 subcategories:

- Fundamental skills:
 - communicate,
 - manage information,
 - use numbers,
 - think and solve problems
- Personal Management Skills:
 - demonstrate positive attitudes and behaviours,
 - be responsible,
 - be adaptable,
 - learn continuously,
 - work safely
- Team Work Skills:
 - work with others,
 - participate in projects and tasks

The Australian project mentioned earlier grouped employability skills into eight categories:

- Communication skills that contribute to productive and harmonious relations between employees and customers;
- Team work skills that contribute to productive working relationships and outcomes;
- Problem-solving skills that contribute to productive outcomes;
- Initiative and enterprise skills that contribute to innovative outcomes;
- Planning and organizing skills that contribute to long-term and short term strategic planning;
- Self-management skills that contribute to employee satisfaction and growth;
- Learning skills that contribute to ongoing improvement and expansion in employee and company operations and outcomes; and
- Technology skills that contribute to effective execution of tasks.

Others group employability skills into categories such as the following:

- Basic academic skills (e.g., reading, writing, basic science, math, oral communication, listening) (Lankard, 1989; Robinson, 2000);
- Higher-order thinking skills (e.g., learning, reasoning, thinking creatively, problem solving, decision making) (Lankard, 1989; Robinson, 2000);
- Developmental Skills (or personal qualities) (e.g., is responsible, has self confidence, exercises self control, has social skills, is honest, has integrity, is adaptable and flexible, has team spirit, is punctual and efficient, is self directed, has a good work attitude, is well groomed, is cooperative, is self motivated, is able to self manage) (Cotton, 1993).

Another skill mentioned as prerequisite for job searching is computer skills (e.g., word processing for developing resumes and cover letters, for conducting employment related research online, e-mail for submitting resumes) (Adamowicz, 2004). We note however, that a study in Scotland found

that those already disadvantaged in terms of skills, educational attainment and income are clearly less likely to have the access and skills required to benefit from using Internet as a job search tool (McQuaid, Lindsay & Greig, 2003).

The State of Employment Readiness

Research suggests that a state of employment readiness is important for successful job search (Boyd, 2001; Ward & Riddle, 2006).

While some employment readiness skills can be taught (Robinson, 2000) the literature suggests that the presence of supports (such as social support) to manage challenges or barriers to employment¹⁶ are key to achieving a state of ‘employment readiness’ (Boyd, 2001; Ward and Riddle, 2003). The literature also suggests that other factors are important such as the job seekers ability to cope in a multicultural environment (Gawronski, 2001), a desire to learn (Robinson, 2000), motivation, flexibility, and a clear understanding of career interests¹⁷ (sometimes termed ‘job search clarity’) (Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales, 1989; Wanberg, Hough, Song, 2002; Ward & Riddle, 2003)¹⁸.

Individuals without supports (or a sufficient number of them) are considered ‘not employment ready’ since they require assistance beyond training to obtain employment (Ward & Riddle, 2006). Research indicates that if such job seekers do not get the assistance they need; they have only a 40 percent chance of getting and keeping a job (Ward & Riddle, 2006).

¹⁶ Commonly cited barriers include: financial disincentives (will consumer lose social assistance or medical benefits if she gets a job?); caregiver responsibilities at home (small children or ill family member); transportation problems; poor physical health or substance abuse; disability; limited job history and difficulty using official languages.

¹⁷ For some newcomers a clear understanding of career interests comes easily (for example when a foreign career has a direct equivalent in Canada) (Adamowicz, 2004) but for others this understanding is not so easily obtained (for example when a foreign career has no direct equivalent in Canada). In these cases newcomers need information related to occupations in Canada before being able to make career choices and thus before being technically ‘employment ready’.

¹⁸ In Ward and Riddle’s study (2003) 40% of all clients and 70% of “not ready” clients reported needing help with Career Decision-Making. They conclude that making an appropriate occupational choice would seem to be an important prerequisite to success in finding and keeping a job.

Ward & Riddle (2006) also suggest that job search interventions do not, by themselves, move individuals ‘not ready’ for employment to a state of employment readiness and that addressing the full range of factors needed to ensure that not ready clients become ‘ready’ can increase their chances of work success by more than 50%.

Some bridging programs in Canada restrict entry to those considered employment ready. For example, a popular, highly effective¹⁹ and comprehensive employment bridging program for Engineers in Alberta²⁰ restricts entry to program to participants who demonstrate that they are employment ready. At intake clients perform guided self-assessments of their credentials, describe their employment goals / aspirations, and determine their readiness to enter the labour force²¹. Applicants to the program must be at a Canadian Language Benchmark (CLB) level 5 or higher in order to gain entry²².

¹⁹ In 2004 there were approximately 200 applicants competing for 45 seats - most were recruited by word of mouth. 80% or more of graduates found employment in the chosen field within 3 to 6 months after course completion. See Adamowicz, 2004 for more information.

²⁰ The Engineers and Technologists Integration Program. See Adamowicz, 2004 for more information.

²¹ To enter the Canadian labour market immigrants often require assessment in a number of areas among them are assessments of academic credentials, employability, language and occupational competency (Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council, 2006). See The Ministry of Community, Aboriginal and Women’s Services. (2004). An inventory of assessment tools for skilled immigrants. Final Report.

http://www.ecdev.gov.bc.ca/ProgramsAndServices/IQU/resources/expo19_mosaic.pdf for more information.

²² The report admits that the intake and assessment process is highly controversial but rationalize the rigorous screening by stating, among other things, that the program is not intended to instruct applicants in English. However it is important to note that the report further states “even when language proficiency levels are lower, there may be other factors that compensate and help create success in the workplace. These include the [jobseeker’s] skill in his / her profession, ability to learn the language, and the opportunity to use his / her first language on the job. Some or all of these factors may make the difference between success and failure”. See Adamowicz, 2004 for more information.

Note

The discussion regarding employment readiness has possible implications for the JSW Program intake and assessment components and in other areas as well.

Currently, to be eligible for the JSW Program a person must meet the following criteria (as posted on the JSW website):

“To be eligible for the JSW program you must:

- be a permanent resident of Canada, landed immigrant, live-in caregiver on convention refugee
- be able to communicate in the English language
- be able to attend a 3 or 4 day, full time, training program

Canadian citizens, visitors or refugee claimants are NOT eligible for the JSW Program.”

Eligibility criteria in the JSW Ontario Region Agency Statistics Guideline (2005) add that as a “guideline” newcomers should have LINC level 4 language proficiency.

Regarding employment barriers - in the 2001 JSW Program Review Sparks & Wolfson found that “about 70% of the sample clients reported that they had experienced more than 1 employment barrier and 25% said they had experienced more than 3 barriers”. Barriers to employment included (but were not limited to) a lack of Canadian experience, language/communication issues, non-recognition of foreign education, childcare, transportation and personal/family responsibilities.

Knowledge and Skills Necessary for Successful Job Searching

A study conducted by Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales in 1989 using questionnaire responses from employment counselors (many in a high school setting) and other human services personnel (n =1,121) found that the top ten critical knowledge and skills necessary for job searching included the following:

1. Ability to identify one's aptitudes
2. Ability to identify one's skills
3. Ability to identify one's interests
4. Knowledge of the importance of personal appearance and hygiene in getting a job
5. Ability to sell one's skills to get a job
6. Awareness of the importance of a properly completed application
7. Ability to relate one's skills, interests, aptitudes and values to jobs
8. Knowledge of how to participate in a job interview
9. Ability to prepare for an interview
10. Knowledge of the personal characteristics that are considered important by employers

However recent literature more accurately places Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales' items 1 - 4 into the employability skills set discussed earlier.

The following discussion assumes an employment ready newcomer job seeker²³.

Newcomers need to provide proof that their education, skills and experience are comparable to that of a Canadian (Adamowicz, 2004). In the absence of (or in addition to) official recognition of their education and experience (by an official accreditation, certification or licensure body), a newcomer must be able to clearly and succinctly present and market their skills to potential employers as well as to those in their social networks (Barnard, 2006; McQuaid, 2002). Without this ability, newcomers may find themselves under or unemployed.

In order to clearly and succinctly present and market their skills and foreign education and experience successfully newcomers must have the ability to:

1. Determine occupational requirements and fit
2. Identify appropriate job opportunities
3. Develop quality resumes and cover letters
4. Prepare for and participate in interviews successfully

Note

Information in this section of this report is incomplete. Research into necessary skills and knowledge for effective job searching, effective program models and best practice is still ongoing.

~~where newcomers may have special job searching needs.~~

Ability to determine occupational requirements and fit²⁴

Newcomers must determine where they fit within the Canadian version of their occupation. “For example, a Railway Engineer from the Peoples’ Republic of China must determine if their background makes them more a Civil than a Mechanical or Industrial Engineer because there is no direct equivalent of this designation [in Canada]” (Adamowicz, 2004). Another example is given in Atlin, (2000) wherein “a diesel mechanic who had worked in the shipping industry would not find an identical trade title in the list of Ontario Trades. However, this individual would have skills that could apply to a range of Ontario trades such as truck and coach mechanic, train mechanic, small engine mechanic, or marine engine mechanic”. These examples point to the need for some newcomers to obtain detailed occupation specific information including requirements for that occupation (Adamowicz, 2004; Laroche, 2007). Once occupational requirements are understood a newcomer can proceed to identify appropriate job opportunities (assuming they have the appropriate occupation specific skills), develop resumes and cover letters and prepare for and participate in interviews.

Ability to identify appropriate job opportunities

Newcomers need to have an overall understanding of the job searching process in Canada since it may differ from the job searching process in their country of origin (for example according Gawronski (2001) resumes are not typically used in Russia). As well, newcomers need to be proficient in utilizing as many job search strategies (methods) as possible.

These methods include the ability to network²⁵ (Mclean, 2003; Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council, 2006), to locate and review job advertisements (including online advertisements), to make cold calls (via telephone or in person to places of business) to attend job

²⁴ For immigrants the determining occupational requirements overlaps somewhat with the career aspects of employment readiness.

²⁵ See Mclean (2003) pg. 20 for information on how to network ‘Canadian Style’.

fairs or clubs (if appropriate, possible) and to make use of job centres or employment agencies (if appropriate, possible).

Ability to develop quality resumes and cover letters

Most job seekers need to be able to develop quality resumes and cover letters customized to particular job opportunities (Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales, 1989; Laroche, 2007). Unlike job seekers with Canadian work experience and education however, many newcomers need additional knowledge and skills to accomplish this. For example, a job seeker with Canadian experience and education can develop a quality resume simply by listing their Canadian work history and education in a suitable format. The information contained in the resume will be readily understood by Canadian employers. A newcomer on the other hand will often need to prove that their foreign education and experience is transferable to the Canadian labour market. To do this, newcomers may need to 'translate' their foreign experience into terms that Canadian employers can relate to and understand.

“Employers demand educational pre-requisites and other qualifications for many types of jobs, not only for the licensed trades and professions but also for semi-professions which are not formally regulated, and for other jobs at various skill levels as well” (Reitz, 2001). At the same time there is evidence to indicate that Canadian employers find it difficult to evaluate foreign educational credentials and work experience (Forum, 2004; Reitz, 2001). It may be suggested that in the absence of any external intervention, it is up to the newcomer to properly translate and communicate their skills, experience and education in ways that can be easily understood by the employer. Occupation specific information (as discussed above) may be an important prerequisite for preparing resumes and cover letters that accomplish this translation.

Employers surveyed in the Public Policy Forum study (2004) complained that immigrants often do not “not do all that they could to make their credentials easy to verify (for example, by providing English translations of these credentials)” Furthermore the report states that employers’ experience with evaluating foreign credentials is limited and that very few employers can name an organization that provides credential recognition services²⁶.

Findings from a study conducted by Fritzsche & Brannick (2002) found that recruiters often use unstable strategies for reviewing resumes and that favorable ratings for resumes may be a result of

²⁶ It is important to note that “about one-quarter of Canadian employers would consider foreign work experience, but do not view it as equal to Canadian work experience. Another quarter of employers would not hire immigrants without Canadian work experience. Focus group research found several employers admitting that, all things being equal, it is often easier and less risky to hire someone with Canadian work experience.” (Public Policy Forum, 2004)

not finding anything negative in the resume (as opposed to finding anything particularly positive). The study recommends that applicants should blanket employers with resumes as “interviews appear to be granted as much by luck and whim as by merit”. This may seem a controversial finding and certainly many recruiters would disagree with the conclusion drawn, however it does serve to draw attention to the importance of a high quality resume.

In 2004 the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union decided²⁷ to establish a single framework for “achieving the transparency of qualifications and competences by means of the creation of a personal, coordinated portfolio of documents, to be known as ‘Europass’, which citizens can use on a voluntary basis to better communicate and present their qualifications and competences throughout the European Union (EU) and other countries.

The Europass consists of five documents: two documents, Europass curriculum vitae (CV), and Europass Language Passport the individual completes themselves and three other documents, the Europass Certificate Supplement, Europass Diploma Supplement and Europass Mobility filled in and issued by competent organizations.

The Europass CV helps the individual to translate their skills and ‘foreign’ education and experience in such a way as to make their skills and qualifications clearly and easily understood throughout Europe. Instructions for completing the CV are available to individuals in over twenty languages. A copy in English is attached in Appendix C.

Ability to prepare for and participate in an interview

The ability to successfully participate in an interview requires newcomers to have:

- Skill in preparing for and participating in an interview (Gawronski, 2001)
- Skill in managing illegal questions during an interview (Immigrant Services Society, 2003; Toscani, 2007)
- Ability to market skills (e.g., successfully describing how skills, education and experience are transferable to the Canadian workplace) (Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales, 1989; Reitz, 2001)

Skill in preparing for and participating in an interview

²⁷ See

<http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu/europass/home/hornav/Downloads/MiscDocs/EuropassDecision/navigate.action> for the entire decision.

Skill in preparing for and participating in an interview is critical for job seekers (Helwig, Hiatt & Vidales, 1989) and may be especially so for newcomers.

A study in a small non-immigrant population found that interview coaching is related to higher performance in structured situational interviews (study participants were attempting to obtain a promotion). Specifically, attendance at a coaching session was significantly related to interview performance when controlling for job knowledge and motivation to do well. Race and sex were generally not empirically related to the study variables. Interview coaching seems to have an effect on performance by leading to specific types of preparation behaviour that leads to certain types of behaviour during interviews: Coaching → Preparation Strategies → Response Strategies → Performance. (Maurer, 2006)

According to Mauer & Solamon (2006) the following preparation strategies are related to success in the interview:

- Participating in role plays
- Participating in study groups
- Talking with past interviewees
- Talking with others knowledgeable about interviewing
- Thinking of and rehearsing interview questions
- Observing others perform in mock interviews
- Obtaining tips on how to succeed in an interview

The following response strategies are related to success in the interview:

- Using a notepad and pencil to make notes before answering
- Organizing answers in a chronological, logical and easy-to-follow manner

Since many desired employability skills are evident to employers in the job interview Lankard (1990) recommends several strategies for incorporating employability skill related concepts into the [job search] classroom (a similar list is found in Robinson (2000)). For example:

- Demand good deportment in the classroom and express work values through classroom instruction. Promote and require timeliness, effort, responsibility, and other values.
- Encourage self-esteem in students.
- Use instructional materials that illustrate the importance of employability skill development.
- Identify the problem so that the person can recognize habits that are annoying
- Give frequent feedback

Dealing with Workers' Rights Issues

Newcomers need information regarding Canadian employment practices in order to deal successfully with illegal interview questions and to avoid exploitation by unscrupulous employers (Immigrant Services Society, 2003).

Marketing Skills

Newcomers need skill in marketing their foreign education and experience to potential employers (Reitz, 2001).

Employers surveyed in the Public Policy Forum study (2004) complained that even when immigrants present excellent résumés and qualifications they cannot hire them because immigrants are often unable to describe their skills and experience in an interview (problems with official languages are cited by employers for these difficulties).

Other Knowledge and Skill Requirements

Other knowledge and skills that may be important for job searching include:

- Woman may require additional training due to expectations of significant others, discrimination and/or multiple role demands (Montero & Dey, 2003; Tastsoglou & Miedema, 2000). Additional training/services for woman might include assertiveness and negotiations skills training (Montero & Dey, 2003).
- Youth may require additional training in order to achieve a state of employment readiness (Weatherill, 2001)
- Information about particular communities, job growth trends and opportunities, information on credential and skills assessments or licensure, and/or information regarding education and training opportunities (Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council, 2006). Much of this information may be necessary either for achieving employment readiness (including job clarity), evaluating job offers or for ongoing career management but not necessarily for job searching itself.

A significant amount of information related to the Canadian labour market is available for newcomers - much of it online. A table showing some of the more popular sources and specifics around the type of information provided is included in Appendix B.

- Newcomers need information related to Canadian workplace norms. Behaviours that may be acceptable and expected in the Canadian workplace may be quite different from those in other countries (Immigrant Services Society, 2003). The importance of this topic is mentioned consistently in discussions regarding newcomers and their labour market integration needs (e.g., Adamowicz, 2004; Immigrant Services Society, 2003; Pollack, 2004; Singer, 2007; TRIEC, 2006).

In 2004, the Public Policy Forum undertook conducted a survey of 2,091 employers across Canada and 10 focus groups to confirm and validate findings. That study found that employers 'were happy to accommodate immigrants' but many felt that some 'cultural' issues were difficult to deal with. For example, some employers said that immigrant

employees were more likely to need time off to visit family abroad and to deal with family issues, some employers said that some male immigrants were uncomfortable working for women, some noted that immigrant employees did not socialize or mingle with other employees and some employers worried about inter-ethnic conflict between immigrant groups.

A study conducted with an immigrant population in New Zealand found that positive interview behaviours and cognitive flexibility did not assist immigrants in their job search process. The implication being that some systematic biases on the part of potential employers existed. In that study full employment was predicted by employer perceptions of cultural fit to New Zealand norms suggesting that employers over-emphasize similarity at the expense of diversity in the workplace (Mace, Atkins, Fletcher & Carr, 2005)²⁸. Similar notions of bias have been discussed in Canada as well (Gawronski, 2001; Pollack, 2004; Prefontaine & Benson, 1999; Reitz, 2001)

Without information on workplace culture some newcomers will have difficulty maintaining a job. However, how much of this information is necessary for the job search process itself is unclear. It may be that newcomers need to be taught how to address issues of culture during interviews so that employers can feel confident of a newcomers' ability to 'fit in'. Ideally, job search students would have training in this area prior to obtaining employment.

²⁸ See also Coates & Carr (2005)

Note

We stress again that the findings presented in this report are preliminary. Research is ongoing and the team remains open to new information. However, based on evidence collected thus far RealWorld Systems is developing several hypotheses about how JSW might be more effective. RealWorld Systems intends to test these approaches over the course of the program review. Our methodology will try to find evidence to support and to challenge the following:

1. The JSW program should focus the curriculum in the three areas that will have most impact on successful job searches:
 - Development of resumes and cover letters
 - Job interview skills (including interview coaching and practice)
 - Independent job search methods (including responding to advertisements, networking, unsolicited resumes, cold calls, etc.)

2. The learning objectives for the Job Search Workshops should be behaviour-based and should include the following:
 - By the end of the workshop the student will have demonstrated punctuality and appropriate dress and grooming for work
 - By the end of the workshop the student will develop a complete resume that shows his/her skills and experience in terms that are relevant to the Canadian labour market and his/her employment goals
 - By the end of the workshop the student will demonstrate the skills necessary to be able to perform well in an interview
 - By the end of the workshop the student will be able to demonstrate that he/she can utilize various independent job search strategies

3. The outputs of JSW should include measures of the behaviours above; for example:
 - Numbers of cold calls made
 - Completeness of resume
 - A rating of the student's job interview skills, etc.

4. The Job Search Workshops need to occur over a long enough time-frame to allow students sufficient time to demonstrate the appropriate behaviours as described above.

5. The indicators for JSW's desired short term outcomes should include the number of

Note (continued)

Potential benefits of focusing on behavioural outputs:

- When JSW focuses on desired behaviours, employment barriers become immediately apparent and can then be dealt with in the context of the JSW program. For example, a student who arrives late for class may reveal that s/he is having transportation problems while another may not have access to reliable child care. In response, a JSW staff member might provide information and referral services, or use program funds to provide transportation, or help students to problem-solve on transportation issues.
- Defining behavioural outputs (e.g., a complete resume; completed cold calls) allows JSW to be flexible regarding the curriculum while highly focused on the learning objective. For example, if students arrive at the workshop with high quality resumes, their homework assignments can focus on the areas where they need help and practice. The program can be customized to meet individual needs by helping students define their own homework assignments.
- The results of behavioural outputs provides immediate feedback to service delivery. If students are unable to achieve the minimum outputs, the program may need to be revised to meet their particular needs, or the needs of the community (e.g., setting up child care or providing mentoring for employment web searches or improving the curriculum).
- The communication of behaviour-based objectives helps students and teachers understand the expectations of the workshop, and collaborate to achieve them.
- Finally, the outputs all require practicing the desired behaviours in a real-life setting. Their achievement is immediately helpful to newcomers.

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Appendix A - Sample of Labour Market Integration Services in Ontario

According to the Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement (2005)²⁹, the range of initiatives Canada and Ontario currently undertake specifically for immigrants include: employment counselling and assessment; specialized job search assistance; labour market information and research; community partnerships; assessment and recognition of education, skills and foreign credentials; bridge training; assistance with access to regulated occupations; academic and essential skills upgrading; job preparation and work placements; apprenticeships; mentoring initiatives; and employment supports. The following diagram shows some of these services in relation to the Labour Market Integration path shown in Figure 1:

²⁹ The electronic version of the Canada-Ontario Immigration Agreement (2005) is located on Citizenship and Immigration Canada's website: <http://www.cic.gc.ca/english/policy/fed-prov/ont-2005-agree.html>

Figure 5: Sample services in relation to the labour market integration path

Appendix B - Popular Labour Market Information Sources

Source of Information	Source Type	Type of Information	Sponsor of Information	Link
Going to Canada (national portal)	Online	On-line qualifications and language assessment tools, orientation to Canada, educational programs, mentoring opportunities, job search preparation, labour market information	Joint initiative of five departments; CIC, HRSDC, Industry Canada, Health Canada, DFAIT	http://www.canadainternational.gc.ca/gtc/Going_To_Canada-en.aspx
Ontarioimmigration.ca	Online	Links to over 300 websites, guides on living, working, studying and doing business in Ontario	Ontario Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration	http://www.ontarioimmigration.ca/index.asp
2ontario.com	Online	Information of employment for immigrants - emphasis on self-employment, how to start a business in Ontario	Ontario Ministry of Economic Development and Trade	http://www.2ontario.com/
Settlement.org	Online	Wide range of information including job search links and resources, language training, housing, health, family sponsorship, etc. See Finding a Job - http://www.settlement.org/site/EM/finding_a_job.asp	Citizenship and Immigration Canada & Ontario government	http://www.settlement.org/
toronto.ca	Online	General orientation, links to sites on how to find employment, broader information about the City of Toronto, services and programs	City of Toronto	http://www.toronto.ca/
211toronto.ca	Online / Phone	Lists over 20,000 community resources	TBD	http://www.211toronto.ca/splash.jsp
Service Canada	Online	Information related to education & training,	Service Canada - Labour Market	http://www.labourmarketinformation.ca/stand

		employment (e.g. work permits), health, housing, etc. Also has information on the development of the labour market in Canada, the provinces and economic regions, publications, statistics	Integration Unit	ard.asp?pcode=lmiv_makin&lcode=e³⁰ http://www.servicecanada.gc.ca/ http://www.hrsdc.gc.ca/en/gateways/where_you_live/regions/on.shtml)
Career Maps	Online	Occupation & sector specific information - career maps in professions and trades	Ontario Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration - Labour Market Integration Unit And several developed by professional associations including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmacists • Nurses • Engineering technicians/technologists • Medical laboratory technologists • Teachers • Chartered accountants 	http://www.citizenship.gov.on.ca/english/citdiv/apt/occfact.html
Professional Associations	Online / Publications	Profession specific information, processes - some with Career Maps (see above)	Varies	See professional association websites
Regulatory Bodies	Online / Publications	Registration and licensing processes, labour market issues pertaining to specific occupations	Varies	See regulatory body websites
Canadian Orientation Abroad	Face-to-face information	Orientation sessions presented abroad	Citizenship and Immigration Canada - Settlement Division	http://www.cic.gc.ca/english/pub/orientation.html

³⁰ The information found here may be especially useful to newcomers

	n sessions		Integration Branch	
Newcomer Information Centres (NIC)	Counselling (in SPOs)	Basic information and referral	Citizenship and Immigration Canada (under ISAP) & Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration (under Newcomer Settlement Program)	See SPO websites
Newcomer informal networks (family and friends in Canada and overseas)	Informal counselling	Suppose basic information and referral (sometimes inaccurate)	NA	NA
Specific bridging & employment related programs / services	TBD	Labour market information, job search information, jobs, etc.	Varies	Many sites: some examples: www.hrsdc.gc.ca www.hrsdc.gc.ca/career/ Job Bank: jb-ge.hrdc-drhc.gc.ca www.worksearch.gc.ca imi-imt.hrdc-drhc.gc.ca www.theworkplace.ca www.jobsetc.ca

Table 2: Popular labour market information sources

Appendix C - Instructions for Completing the Europass CV³¹

³¹ See

http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu/img/dynamic/c1345/type.FileContent.file/CVInstructions_en_GB.pdf for an electronic version of the instructions.

Instructions for using the Europass curriculum vitae

(<http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu>)

Introduction

Drawing up a curriculum vitae is an important step in looking for any job or training. The CV is often the first contact with a future employer. It needs to seize the reader's attention immediately and to demonstrate why you should be given an interview.

Important! Employers generally spend no more than a minute on each CV when making an initial selection from applications received. If you fail to make the right impact, you will waste your opportunity.

Read the following information carefully before entering your details into the template.

General recommendations

Before starting to write your curriculum vitae, remind yourself of a few important principles:

Take care over the presentation of your CV

Set out your qualifications, skills and competences clearly and logically, so that your specific attributes are easily seen.

Give proper attention to all relevant detail, both of substance and presentation; there is no excuse for mistakes in spelling and punctuation!

Concentrate on the essentials

- a CV must be brief: in most cases, two pages are enough to show who and what you are. A three page CV may be considered too long in some countries, even if your work experience is outstanding.
- if your work experience is still limited (because you have just left school or university), describe your education and training first; highlight work placements during training (see online examples);
- concentrate on essential information that brings added value to your application: work experience or training which is old or not relevant for the application can be omitted.

Adapt your CV to suit the post applied for

Systematically check your CV every time you want to send it to an employer to see if it corresponds to the profile required; highlight your advantages according to the specific requirements of the prospective employer. A good knowledge of the company will help you tailoring your CV to the appropriate profile.

Take care: do not artificially inflate your CV; if you do, you are likely to be found out at the interview.

Keep to the structure of the template

The Europass curriculum vitae allows you to present your qualifications, skills and competences in a logical order:

- personal information;
- description of your work experience;
- description of your education and training (which may appear before the heading 'Work experience' for users with limited work experience; to invert the order of the two headings, use the 'copy/paste' command in your word processing software);
- detailed inventory of your skills and competences, acquired in the course of your training, work and daily life.

Notes:

- print your curriculum vitae on white paper;
- retain the suggested font and layout;
- avoid underlining or writing whole sentences in capitals or bold: it affects the readability of the document;
- do not split an entry under one heading over two pages (e.g. your list of training courses) – to avoid this use the 'page break' command in your word processing software;
- the boxes containing the various headings should not appear when the document is printed.

Be clear and concise

Your profile must be appreciated by the potential employer after a few seconds' reading. In consequence:

- use short sentences;
- concentrate on the relevant aspects of your training and work experience;
- explain any breaks in your studies or career;
- remove any optional heading (e.g. if you have no 'Artistic skills and competences' (see page 2 of the template) or if you consider that such skills and competences do not bring added value to your application, remove the whole entry using the 'cut' command in your word processing software.

Have someone else read your CV on completion

Check your CV carefully once you have filled it in to remove any spelling mistakes and to ensure it is laid out clearly and logically.

Have someone else read your CV so that you are sure the content is clear and easy to understand.

Detailed instructions for using the Europass curriculum vitae

(<http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu>)

How to draft your Europass curriculum vitae?

I. Use the online interface or download the CV template:

You can either

(a) use the online interface available on the Europass website. (<http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu>) Your CV can be then saved to the directory of your choice;

or

(b) download the CV template in the language of your choice from the same website and save it on your computer hard disk; you then complete the various headings in the right-hand column, and insert your personal data.

If you need guidance, consult the sample CVs provided on <http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu>

II. Fill in the different sections as follows

Important:

- do not change the wording of the left-hand column;
- keep to the layout and font used in the template.

Europass curriculum vitae

Insert photograph if requested (optional)

Notes:

- a picture is not essential in a CV, unless requested by the employer
- format: preferably jpg.

Personal information

Surname(s) / First name(s)
(remove if not relevant)

State your surname(s) (preferably using small capitals) and first name(s), (preferably using lower case), e.g.:

Smith, John Andrew

in conformity with the rules that apply in your country.

Note: if you have more than one other name, start with the one you usually use.

Address(es)
(remove if not relevant)

State your complete postal address(es) where you wish to be contacted, e.g.:

12, High Street, Newtown AB12 3CD

Notes:

- show clearly the address at which you can be contacted quickly. If your permanent address is different from where you are living at present, you may write both addresses, stating the dates between which you can be contacted at each;
- the order in which the items in an address appear may vary from country to country; follow the rules that apply so that post will reach you quickly; do not forget the country code if you are applying abroad (see [sample CV](#));
- in the case of Ireland, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands, the name of the country is written out in full:

Dublin 2
Ireland

...
London SW1P 3AT
United Kingdom

...
2500 EA Den Haag
Nederland

For further details, consult the Interinstitutional style guide, available on line:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-000400.htm>

Telephone(s) (remove if not relevant)	State the telephone number(s) where you wish to be contacted; if necessary, give specific days and times when it is possible to reach you (so that you can be contacted quickly), e.g.:
	Fixed: 0845 120 30 45 Mobile: 6945 12 36 54
	Notes: - if you wish to send your CV to other countries, give the country prefix and any regional prefix in brackets. These two prefixes should be joined by a hyphen, e.g.: (44-20) 80 12 34 56 for a number in London. - divide the principal number into groups of two from the right-hand side, the last group consisting of three digits if the number is odd (groups are separated by a space, not by a full stop), e.g. (353-1) 220 20 20 for a number in Dublin.
	For further details, consult the Interinstitutional style guide, available on line http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-000400.htm
Fax(es) (remove if not relevant)	Write your fax number(s), using the same rules as for your telephone number(s) e.g.:
	0845 120 30 46.
E-mail(s) (remove if not relevant)	Write your e-mail address(es) in full, specifying if it is your personal or professional address, e.g.:
	bragov@whao.com
Nationality(-ies) (optional)	Write your nationality(-ies), e.g.:
	Irish
Date of birth (optional)	Give your date of birth (dd/mm/yyyy), e.g.:
	02.04.1963
Gender (optional)	Specify your gender, (Male / Female) e.g.:
	Male
Desired employment / Occupational field (remove if not relevant)	Specify your job target or occupational field, e.g.:
	Database manager and administrator
	Note: this entry gives an immediate overview of your profile by focusing on your core competences.

Work Experience

Under this heading, make a separate entry for each relevant job held, starting with the most recent.

Notes:

- if you are applying for your first job, do not forget to mention work placements during training which provide evidence of initial contact with the world of work;
- if your work experience is still limited (because you have just left school or university), describe your education and training first (to invert the order of the two headings, use the 'copy/paste' command in your word processing software); highlight work placements during training (see online examples);
- for the sake of brevity, focus on the work experience that gives added weight to your application. Do not overlook experience which may be an asset even though it is not directly related to the profile of the job for which you are applying (e.g., time spent abroad, work bringing you into contact with the public, etc.);
- reproduce the table (using the 'copy/paste' command in your word processing software) as many times as required. To delete a heading, use the 'Table' commands menu in your word processing software.

Dates	Write the dates to show how long you held the job in question, e.g.: From March 1994 to December 1999
Occupation or position held	State your job title or the nature of your occupation, e.g.: HGV mechanic, Maintenance technician, Receptionist
Main activities and responsibilities	State your main activities and responsibilities, e.g.: Maintenance of computers or Relations with suppliers or Maintaining parks and gardens If necessary, quantify your responsibilities (percentage of working time, length of time spent on each occupation, etc.).
Name and address of employer	State the name and address of the employer, e.g.: Anderson and Dobbs Ltd., 12 Highland Road, Edinburgh EH3 4AB, United Kingdom Note: if relevant, add more information (telephone, fax, e-mail or Internet address), e.g.: Tel: (44-31) 123 45 67 - Fax (44-31) 123 45 68 - E-mail: J.Robinson@andes.co.uk; Website: http://www.anderdobbs.co.uk
Type of business or sector	State the nature of the employer's business or sector, e.g.: Transport and logistics or Auditing or Manufacturer of motor vehicle parts

Education and training

Under this heading, make a separate entry for each course completed, i.e., each course leading to a qualification, starting with the most recent.

Notes:

- if your work experience is still limited (because you have just left school or university), describe your education and training first (to invert the order of the two headings, use the 'copy/paste' command in your word processing software);
- there is no need to show all your qualifications: do not go back as far as primary school if you hold a university degree; focus on the qualifications which are an asset to your application;
- reproduce the table (using the 'copy/paste' command in your word processing software) as many times as required. To delete a heading, use the 'Table' commands menu in your word processing software.

Dates	Write the dates to show how long the course in question lasted, e.g.: From September 1994 to June 1998
Title of qualification awarded	Write the exact title of the qualification awarded, e.g.: National Vocational Qualification (NVQ) Level 2: Bakery Service Note: avoid using abbreviations on their own (e.g. NVQ).
Principal subjects/occupational skills covered	Summarise the main subjects or occupational skills taught during the course in question, grouping them together if necessary for the sake of brevity, e.g.: General - English language, Welsh language, mathematics, foreign language (Spanish) - physical education and sports Occupational - occupational techniques (making of standard breads, fancy breads, cakes and pastries) - science applied to food and equipment (microbiology, biochemistry, hygiene) - occupational technology (basic principles, hygiene and safety) - knowledge of business and its economic, legal and social context. Note: combine items, and focus on the occupational skills which would be an asset if you were appointed.
Name and type of organisation providing education and training	State the name (and if appropriate, the address) and type of the institution attended, e.g.: South Wales Technical College Glamorgan Place Cardiff CF1 2AB
Level in national or international classification (remove if not relevant)	If the level of the qualification corresponds to an existing national or international classification system, state the level within the classification concerned (national classification, ISCED, etc.). If necessary, ask the body which awarded the qualification. For more information on ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) devised by UNESCO, consult: http://www.uis.unesco.org/TEMPLATE/pdf/isced/ISCED_A.pdf

Personal skills and competences

This page is dedicated to skills and competences acquired in the course of life and career but not necessarily covered by formal certificates and diplomas. In other words, it aims to give a complete picture of your skills and competences. The headings below (languages, social, organisational, technical, computer-related, artistic and other skills and competences) allow you describe skills and competences acquired both in the course of your education and training (during your studies) during seminars or continuing training sessions, and in a non-formal manner (in the course of your occupational or leisure activities).

General note: Delete any heading under which you have nothing relevant to say, using the 'cut' command menu in your word processing software.

Mother tongue(s) State your mother tongue(s) here, e.g.: English

Other language(s) (remove if not relevant) Note: state in the section below your skills and competences in foreign languages. Use the self-assessment scale developed by the Council of Europe to help people self-assessing their foreign language level of proficiency in understanding, speaking and writing (see instructions below heading).

Table with columns: Self-assessment European level (1), Understanding (Listening, Reading), Speaking (Spoken interaction, Spoken production), Writing. Rows for Spanish and French.

(1) Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) level

Instructions for using the self-assessment grid

The self-assessment grid is based on the six level scale of the common European framework of reference for languages developed by the Council of Europe.

The grid consists of three broad levels as follows:

- Basic user (levels A1 and A2);
- Independent user (levels B1 and B2);
- Proficient user (levels C1 and C2).

To self-assess your foreign language level, read the descriptions below and write the relevant level (e.g. Proficient user - C2) in the adequate box of your CV (Listening, Reading, Spoken interaction, Spoken production and Writing).

Understanding

Listening

- A 1:** I can understand familiar words and very basic phrases concerning myself, my family and immediate surroundings when people speak slowly and clearly.
- A 2:** I can understand phrases and the highest frequency vocabulary related to areas of most immediate personal relevance (e.g. very basic personal and family information, shopping, local area, employment). I can catch the main points in short, clear, simple messages and announcements.
- B 1:** I can understand the main points of clear standard speech on familiar matters regularly encountered in work, school, leisure, etc. I can understand the main points of many radio or TV programmes on current affairs or topics of personal or professional interest when the delivery is relatively slow and clear.
- B 2:** I can understand extended speech and lectures and follow even complex lines of argument provided the topic is reasonably familiar. I can understand most TV news and current affairs programmes. I can understand the majority of films in standard dialect.
- C 1:** I can understand extended speech even when it is not clearly structured and when relationships are only implied and not signalled explicitly. I can understand television programmes and films without too much effort.
- C 2:** I have no difficulty in understanding any kind of spoken language, whether live or broadcast, even when delivered at fast native speed, provided I have some time to get familiar with the accent.

Reading

- A 1:** I can understand familiar names, words and very simple sentences, for example on notices and posters or in catalogues.
- A 2:** I can read very short, simple texts. I can find specific, predictable information in simple everyday material such as advertisements, prospectuses, menus and timetables and I can understand short simple personal letters.
- B 1:** I can understand texts that consist mainly of high frequency everyday or job-related language. I can understand the description of events, feelings and wishes in personal letters.
- B 2:** I can read articles and reports concerned with contemporary problems in which the writers adopt particular attitudes or viewpoints. I can understand contemporary literary prose.
- C 1:** I can understand long and complex factual and literary texts, appreciating distinctions of style. I can understand specialised articles and longer technical instructions, even when they do not relate to my field.
- C 2:** I can read with ease virtually all forms of the written language, including abstract, structurally or linguistically complex texts such as manuals, specialised articles and literary works.

Speaking

Spoken interaction

- A 1:** I can interact in a simple way provided the other person is prepared to repeat or rephrase things at a slower rate of speech and help me formulate what I'm trying to say. I can ask and answer simple questions in areas of immediate need or on very familiar topics.
- A 2:** I can communicate in simple and routine tasks requiring a simple and direct exchange of information on familiar topics and activities. I can handle very short social exchanges, even though I can't usually understand enough to keep the conversation going myself.
- B 1:** I can deal with most situations likely to arise whilst travelling in an area where the language is spoken. I can enter unprepared into conversation on topics that are familiar, of personal interest or pertinent to everyday life (e.g. family, hobbies, work, travel and current events).

- B 2:** I can interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible. I can take an active part in discussion in familiar contexts, accounting for and sustaining my views.
- C 1:** I can express myself fluently and spontaneously without much obvious searching for expressions. I can use language flexibly and effectively for social and professional purposes. I can formulate ideas and opinions with precision and relate my contribution skilfully to those of other speakers.
- C 2:** I can take part effortlessly in any conversation or discussion and have a good familiarity with idiomatic expressions and colloquialisms. I can express myself fluently and convey finer shades of meaning precisely. If I do have a problem I can backtrack and restructure around the difficulty so smoothly that other people are hardly aware of it.

Spoken production

- A 1:** I can use simple phrases and sentences to describe where I live and people I know.
- A 2:** I can use a series of phrases and sentences to describe, in simple terms, my family and other people, living conditions, my educational background and my present or most recent job.
- B 1:** I can connect phrases in a simple way in order to describe experiences and events, my dreams, hopes and ambitions. I can briefly give reasons and explanations for opinions and plans. I can narrate a story or relate the plot of a book or film and describe my reactions.
- B 2:** I can present clear, detailed descriptions on a wide range of subjects related to my field of interest. I can explain a viewpoint on a topical issue giving the advantages and disadvantages of various options.
- C 1:** I can present clear, detailed descriptions of complex subjects integrating sub-themes, developing particular points and rounding off with an appropriate conclusion.
- C 2:** I can present a clear, smoothly-flowing description or argument in a style appropriate to the context and with an effective logical structure which helps the recipient to notice and remember significant points.

Writing

- A 1:** I can write a short, simple postcard, for example sending holiday greetings. I can fill in forms with personal details, for example entering my name, nationality and address on a hotel registration form.
- A 2:** I can write short, simple notes and messages. I can write a very simple personal letter, for example thanking someone for something.
- B 1:** I can write simple connected text on topics which are familiar or of personal interest. I can write personal letters describing experiences and impressions.
- B 2:** I can write clear, detailed text on a wide range of subjects related to my interests. I can write an essay or report, passing on information or giving reasons in support of or against a particular point of view. I can write letters highlighting the personal significance of events and experiences.
- C 1:** I can express myself in clear, well-structured text, expressing points of view at some length. I can write about complex subjects in a letter, an essay or a report, underlining what I consider to be the salient issues. I can select a style appropriate to the reader in mind.
- C 2:** I can write clear, smoothly-flowing text in an appropriate style. I can write complex letters, reports or articles which present a case with an effective logical structure which helps the recipient to notice and remember significant points. I can write summaries and reviews of professional or literary works.

The complete self-assessment grid can be accessed from the website of the Council of Europe under [http://culture2.coe.int/portfolio/inc.asp?L=E&M=\\$t/208-1-0-1/main_pages/_/&L=E&M=\\$t/208-1-0-1/main_pages/levels.html](http://culture2.coe.int/portfolio/inc.asp?L=E&M=$t/208-1-0-1/main_pages/_/&L=E&M=$t/208-1-0-1/main_pages/levels.html)

Notes:

- if you have a certificate testifying to your competence (such as TOEIC -Test of English for International Communication), state the level and the date when you obtained;
- do not overestimate your level, which may well be checked if you are interviewed!

<p>Social skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>What are we talking about? Social skills and competences refer to living and working with other people, in positions where communication is important and situations where teamwork is essential (for example culture and sports), in multicultural environments, etc. Describe your social skills and competences, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - team spirit; - good ability to adapt to multicultural environments, gained through my work experience abroad; - good communication skills gained through my experience as sales manager. <p>Specify in what context they were acquired (through training, work, seminars, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>
<p>Organisational skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>What are we talking about? Organisational skills and competences refer to coordination and administration of people, projects and budgets; at work, in voluntary work (for example culture and sports) and at home, etc. Describe your organisational skills and competences, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - leadership (currently responsible for a team of 10 people); - sense of organisation (experience in logistics); - good experience in project or team management. <p>and say in what context they were acquired (through training, work, seminars, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>
<p>Technical skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>What are we talking about? Technical skills and competences refer to mastery of specific kinds of equipment, machinery, etc. other than computers, or to technical skills and competences in a specialised field (manufacturing industry, health, banking, etc.). Describe your technical skills and competences, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - good command of quality control processes (I was responsible for the implementation of quality audit in my dept); <p>Specify in what context they were acquired (through training, work, seminar, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>
<p>Computer skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>What are we talking about? Computer skills and competences refer to word processing and other applications, database searching, acquaintance with Internet, advanced skills (programming etc.). Describe your computer skills and competences, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - good command of Microsoft Office™ tools (Word™, Excel™ and PowerPoint™); - basic knowledge of graphic design applications (Adobe Illustrator™, PhotoShop™). <p>Specify in what context they were acquired (through training, work, seminar, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>

<p>Artistic skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>State here your artistic skills and competences which are an asset (music; writing; design, etc.) e.g.: carpentry</p> <p>Specify in what context they were acquired (through training, work, seminars, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>
<p>Other skills and competences (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>State here any other skill(s) and competence(s) which are an asset and are not mentioned under earlier headings (hobbies; sports, positions of responsibility in voluntary organisations), e.g.:</p> <p>- trekking</p> <p>Specify in what context they were acquired (through training, work, voluntary or leisure activities, etc.).</p>
<p>Driving licence(s) (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>State here whether you hold a driving licence and, if so, for which category of vehicle, e.g.:</p> <p>Category B</p>
<p>Additional information (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>State here any other information which you think relevant (publications or research; membership of professional organisations, military information [if you judge it important to specify that you have completed military service], marital status [if you judge it important to specify], contact persons or referees [name, job title, contact address, see note below]), e.g.:</p> <p>Publication</p> <p>Article: Molecular characterisation of a H3o-loaded brain cell, Immunology Quarterly, New York, 02/2002</p> <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- do not give the address of a contact person without obtaining his/her formal agreement; it is preferable to state 'References supplied on request' in order not to overload the curriculum vitae;- where appropriate, provide a brief description of your publications or research; specify the type of document (thesis, article, report, etc.).
<p>Annexes (remove if not relevant)</p>	<p>List any items attached to the CV, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- copies of degrees and other qualifications, including any certificates issued at the end of training courses which did not lead to a formal qualification;- testimonial of employment or work placement;- publications or research; etc. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- list the items in a logical order (e.g., place degrees or testimonials of employment together, numbering them if required) to help the reader;- never send originals of degree or qualification certificates as these might be lost; photocopies are adequate.

Appendix C - Agency Questionnaire Results

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree	TOTAL*		Average	Priority	Additional Comments
1. A complete and corrected resume should be a primary outcome of JSW.	1	4	3	15	13	36	143	4.0	1	We already do this
2. A significant amount of time in JSW should be spent on job interview skills – including interview coaching and practice.		3	1	18	15	37	156	4.2	2	We already do this
3. JSW graduates must know how to apply different job search methods: responding to ads, networking, making cold calls, etc.			1	13	23	37	170	4.6	3	We already do this Needs more time
4. JSW should be re-positioned as an overall orientation to job searching only so that participants have more realistic expectations that can be met.	1	6	16	8	6	37	123	3.3	1	
5. JSW should be expanded to allow clients time to develop resumes, practice interviews & demonstrate that they know how to apply different job search methods (e.g., make cold calls).		2	8	6	17	33	137	4.2	5	Can eligibility be looser also?
6. JSW should be expanded to include job development.	3	3	6	6	20	38	151	4.0	10	If funding for additional staff given. If additional staff appointed.

										Childcare, transportation. Expanded to include not job development as understood but employer education and outreach (partnership building with employers but not the job development model that exists)
7. JSW should track the number of interviews and job offers that graduates obtain as a way to demonstrate workshop effectiveness.	4	7	9	9	3	32	96	3.0		
8. JSW should be expanded to include one-on-one career counselling			4	17	15	36	155	4.3	4	
9. When numbers warrant, there should be specialized JSW sessions (e.g., for engineers, for health care professionals).	1	2	8	14	13	38	150	3.9	2	There are specific programs for this funded by MCI.
10. JSW should be better integrated with other employment services in the community (as part of a continuum).			5	14	19	38	166	4.4	1	With guidelines given by funding body. Currently we compete with programs funded by bodies (e.g., MCI, Emp. Ontario) we are fighting for numbers.

										Some, not all.
11. JSW provides insufficient assistance to internationally-trained professionals	5	5	7	16	4	37	120	3.2	3	

*TOTAL number of completed worksheets received = 38 / TOTAL number of respondents = 34

**Only 31 respondents identified a #1 priority

Other priorities:

- Childcare x 4
- Transportation x 3
- Job placement x 2
- Credential evaluations x 1
- More time x 1
- Snacks x 1

Appendix D - Agency Survey - Detailed Findings

Introduction

The Job Search Workshops (JSW) survey was piloted with 4 JSW service providing agencies. After minor modifications based on their feedback, the survey was sent, via email, to 39 additional JSW service providing agencies in Ontario (the total sample size was 43). Agencies were given over two weeks to respond to the survey. 35 responses were received for a response rate of 81.40%.

Total number of surveys sent	43
Total number of completed surveys received	35
Response percentage	81.40%

A copy of the survey sent to agencies is included in Appendix C. The list of responding agencies is included in Appendix D. For a summary of key findings refer to the JSW Program Review - Final Report.

Notes:

- The survey was piloted by 4 agencies. Questions that were added to the survey after the pilot are noted
- All percentages are rounded to two positions
- Two respondents had nearly identical comments. The comments from both respondents have been included.
- Open-ended responses are excerpted directly from the surveys; we did not make changes other than correcting typographical errors and spelling mistakes, and disguising agency identities. While respondents were not promised confidentiality, every attempt has been made to eliminate information from responses that could identify the responding agency (e.g., agency names have been deleted from responses). However, because the surveyed population was relatively small it is possible that responding agencies can be identified based on the content of their responses.

Part 1: Description of your JSW Program

1. What is your agency's name and address?

Responses by city

	Number	Percentage
Toronto	10	28.57%
Scarborough	5	14.29%
Ottawa	4	11.43%
Brampton	2	5.71%
Etobicoke	2	5.71%
Mississauga	2	5.71%
Hamilton	1	2.86%
Kitchener	1	2.86%
London	1	2.86%
North York	1	2.86%
Oakville	1	2.86%
Oshawa	1	2.86%
Richmond Hill	1	2.86%
Sarnia	1	2.86%
St. Catharines	1	2.86%
Windsor	1	2.86%
Total	35	100.00%

2. How long has your agency been delivering Job Search Workshops (JSW)?
Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Over 5 years	28	82.35%
Over 2 years and less than 5 years	3	8.82%
Under 2 years	3	8.82%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

3. Which Job Search Workshop Model does your agency deliver?
(Choose all that apply)

Responses	Number	Percentage
Model A – Daytime sessions	31	88.57%
Model B – Evening sessions	14	40.00%
Model C – Weekend sessions	8	22.86%
Total	53	NA*

Total number of survey respondents: 35
 Total number of respondents this question: 35
 * Many agencies deliver more than one model

4. Please describe your typical or usual workshop:

Usual number of total hours per workshop

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	8* to 25	21	20.32
Model B	15 to 21	16	16.64
Model C	7* to 24	21	18.71

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

*It is possible that some agencies misinterpreted this question and gave the number of hours for one session

Usual number of sessions per workshop

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	1 to 10	3	3.43
Model B	3 to 8	5	4.57
Model C	3 to 10	5	4.57

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34*

*One outlier record = Model A, 28 sessions removed prior to calculation, some survey respondents likely did not understand the question

Number of days that elapse from the first session to the last session

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	3 to 7	3	3.48
Model B	3 to 21	8	8.14
Model C	4* to 21	17	17.29

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

*Some survey respondents likely did not understand the question

Usual number of students per workshop

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	4 to 15	10	10.31
Model B	5 to 15	10	10.14
Model C	4 to 15	8	8.43

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Usual number of workshops that your agency delivers each month

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	.5* to 7	2	2.18**

Model B	1 to 5	2	1.54
Model C	1 to 5	2	2.14

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

* One workshop every other month

** One respondent entered "occasionally" for Model A, response not included in analysis

Usual number of facilitators and assistants who attend each session

	Range	Median	Average
Model A	1 to 2	1	1.39
Model B	1 to 2	1	1.14
Model C	1 to 2	1	1.43

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Comments survey question 4

To be more effective the workshop could be at least a week long and include a resume writing session
We deliver model B to LINC centers
Number of hours per workshop, workshop sessions and elapse time are dependent on the number of participants present in workshop. As well, these variables are correlated with season and weather patterns.
Part-time clerical assistant does not attend sessions
Clerical assistant (part time) does not attend the JSW sessions.
Assistant attends only when support is needed such as drafting resume
Since we work with a flexible model, information given above could change, but our regularly scheduled workshops are reflected above, except that model C Saturday workshops are scheduled every 3 months, to be delivered over 3 weeks.
With two facilitators, our target is to offer 30 workshops per year about half of which is Model A and the other half, Model B. In 2006-2007, we served 343 clients.
[Agency] has sites with different Facilitators offering [type of program] at one site two (English/French)
It is better to have two. Better for the clients so they cannot get [someone else's] approach or style. Allows you to not get very, very tired by end of day. When working with newcomers, sometimes have to repeat yourself. More time involved. Complicated, might take two of you to give more assistance than regular job searchers.
There is always one facilitator and one volunteer on every session
For the interviews, there is a second person.

5. In general, do you feel that the length of the Job Search Workshops is:

	Number	Percentage
Just right	17	56.67%
Should be longer	11	36.67%
Should be shorter	1	3.33%
Don't know	1	3.33%

Total	30	100.00%
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Total number of survey respondents: 31. This question was *not* in the pilot survey

Total number of respondents this question: 30

Comments for survey question 5

Length of workshops should be:	Comment
Shorter	The expectation of 4 day commitment can be difficult for clients who have special needs like child care, survival jobs, and transportation difficulties. Although the four days allow the facilitator to relay the necessary information, it puts stress on clients who have other responsibilities. Perhaps JSW workshops can be more specific to meet client needs (i.e. resume writing clinics) if individuals are unable to attend the full session.
Longer	Length of delivery time is dependent on group size, for instance when the group size is 10+ then definitely the time is extended, for at times, up to 5 days but when group size is less than 8 then 4 days is sufficient.
Just right	More time is needed to apply what is learnt in the workshop
Longer	4-hour evening sessions overly long for participants' concentration and energy levels. Suggest 3-hours per session preferable (but increase number of sessions).
Just right	Clients wish to have one-on-one counselling. Often, after the workshop clients will come back to the Facilitator with requests that she tailor the workshop to their specific needs. Thus, workshops for specific careers were created
Just right	Additional time could always be made use of for interview practice but students have limited amount of time to commit
Longer	The hours of each session should be reduced from 4 to 3 hours. This would allow the number of sessions to be increased and result in better client retention of information.
Longer	There is not enough time to cover all the needs to be covered in 3 days time.
Longer	There ought to be more sessions or increased number of hours per session due to client attention and energy span.
Just right	Its length is suitable for a number of newcomers who are not available for longer program, or can be an introduction that leads them into a longer or more intensive service
Don't know	The clients come to the JSW workshop at various levels and we aim to provide extra assistance to clients who may have some difficulty but we also want to move ahead so that we do not bore the clients who are quick. We should have the flexibility to adjust the length of time the workshop will take.
Longer	A longer workshop (at least by half a day) will enable the students to communicate more with one another and share experiences via discussions. There will also be time to look through some job ads in order to develop a focused resume, as well as more time to discuss interview techniques which participants find very helpful. More time can be devoted to reviewing the mock interview video tapes as well.
Just right	Based on participant evaluations after JSW. It is introductory to the labor market to allow newcomers understand the realities of the job contexts of their new home and know how to overcome the barriers to 'getting -in'.
Longer	We have added a fourth day to the model, which included Portfolio

	Development, Workplace culture and Mock Interview
Longer	Did evaluations with participants. They would like it to be longer
Just right	Most group participants feel it is a good length. Some groups vary in opinion.

Analysis statement: Several respondents appear to have based their opinion of the suitability of workshop length on the client’s ability or willingness to attend, especially in the “just right” and “shorter” categories, while other respondents based their opinion on the length of time needed to address the curriculum.

6. Do you run Job Search Workshops targeted at specific populations (e.g., women, youth, engineers, accountants, low/high literacy level, official language capacity, skilled/unskilled workers)? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
No	22	62.86%
Yes (see table below)	12*	34.29%
Don't know	1	2.86%
Total	35	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

* This number is likely inflated, it is likely that some respondents described their typical client population - see the table which follows. Note also that some agencies deliver to more than one specific population (e.g., one for women and one for youth)

a. If yes, please describe these workshops in terms of their distinctive features (e.g., specific labour market information, speakers, topics, language complexity):

Specific Population	Distinctive Features
Skilled and highly educated individuals	Advanced resume writing and occupation specific resources. See comment on #4. Skilled workers require advanced communication strategies in all areas of job search process and contextualized labour market information.
Internationally Trained Professionals (Engineers, Accountants, IT, Healthcare, Teachers, Technicians and Technologists	Labour market information, Accreditation and Licensing, Regulatory bodies Professional Terminology, Sector specific websites, Speakers from regulatory bodies
Foreign trained engineers, accountants, medical doctors, pharmacists, medical technologists	Workshops would be held for each trade/career where a representative/professional from that field comes in to talk to the clients in regards to accreditation or certification in that field.
Youth	The Centre is holding a workshop aimed at youth late this month to assist them in getting ready to apply for summer jobs through HRSDC.
Women	There have been several workshops that have targeted only women in our community as they felt more comfortable in that setting. These workshops, though, also dealt with other

	settlement issues, especially those pertaining to domestic abuse.
All clients	Recruiting through the OPP sessions, Metro Police (where the sessions were held in Etibicoke and [sic])
Courses specifically for women	
Lower English level workshops	Create materials where the English is much easier to understand
Engineers	Guest speakers
IT	Web sites, sample resumes, guest speakers
Women	Gender specific issues that may arise e.g. women in male dominated sector
Only French speaking immigrants and convention refugees	
Engineers	Labour market, postings, employment contacts etc.
Accountants	Labour market, postings, employment contacts etc.
Healthcare/PSW	Labour market, postings, employment contacts etc.
Any newcomer but with a specific emphasis on Arabic speakers	Delivered in English, French and Arabic
General JSW	General information; however, the hand outs may be designed to address specifics of some occupations in the group
Engineering	The information is tailored to the engineering
Youth	The workshops are shorter and include information related to Summer Job program, Job connect, etc.
Women	Specific barriers for New Canadian women
Basic English level	Special sessions on application forms
Engineers	Access to Engineering in Ontario, transferring skills to other fields in the short term or for a different career.
90% of the population consist of caregivers	Labour market information, accessing hidden job market, resumes, cover letter, job interviews, assessment and accreditation, training and upgrading information, skills identifications, referrals
10% of the population consist of independent immigrants and family sponsored	Labour market information, assessment and accreditation, resumes, cover letters, job interviews, training and upgrading information, referrals, accessing hidden job market
Women	Sessions on assertiveness and confidence building, Sessions on resources available for women in the community, Provide day care and occasional transportation assistance (bus tickets) These are funded through private donations and are not sustainable

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 12

Summary of specific populations served by population

Responses	Number
Women	5
Engineers	4
Skill / education level	3

Miscellaneous Others	3
Basic English Levels	2
Specific language (French, Arabic)	2
Youth	2
Accountants	1
Caregivers	1
Healthcare/PSW	1
IT	1
Total	25

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Derived from 12 responses

Summary of specific populations served by type

Responses	Number
Profession	8
Gender	5
Language	4
Skill / education level	3
Miscellaneous Others	3
Age	2
Total	25

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Derived from 12 responses

a. Why do you offer these customized workshops? **Check all that apply.**

Responses	Number	Percentage
Students have more productive discussions	11	91.67%
Sessions can cover important topics in more depth	11	91.67%
Students can carry out a more targeted job search	10	83.33%
Students can obtain more appropriate job interviews	10	83.33%
Students can network with other students	10	83.33%
Students can gain better job search skills	8	66.67%
Other (see table below)	6	50.00%
The workshops are easier for staff to design and facilitate	4	33.33%
Total	70	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 12

Other Responses (n = 6)

Program is too new
We are meeting the specific needs of the highly skilled/educated newcomers coming to Canada who are the majority of the immigrant population.
Clients feel that they are in the same space/situation as their peers.
French speaking immigrants get service in their official language
Resume building is targeted

It helps students to understand the labour market in Canada and be able to effectively target a specific career goal

- b. Do you have data or other evidence about the effectiveness of your customized workshops?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes (see description of evidence collected below)	11	91.67%
Don't know	1	8.33%
No	0	0.00%
Total	12	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 12

Description of evidence collected (n = 11)

Feedback from clients from follow up that our service was the one that made the difference in terms of employment success. Clients regularly report that our workshop environment is welcoming, safe and inclusive, therefore, an ideal learning environment.
Post workshop evaluation forms, client e-mails, client outcomes
Client feedback from these customized workshops is that they network with each other and assist each other. The [agency name] hears about this during our feedback calls
clients express satisfaction in evaluations
Evaluation reports, success stories
All JSW participants are registered in our data base and we may be able to conduct a search that can outline if the employment status of the participant. And what the participant went on to do after the JSW
Post workshop survey
Good Feedback from evaluation forms
Informal feedback from participants.
Evaluation forms filled out by the participants and follow-ups after the workshops
Evaluation forms

Part 2: Intake and Assessment

7. Before admitting students into the Job Search Workshop, do you screen the students using any of the following: (**Choose all that apply**)

Responses	Number	Percentage
Immigration status check	32	94.12%
English/French LINC Level 4	28	82.35%
Stable child care arrangements	21	61.76%
Literacy level	19	55.88%

Access to transportation	19	55.88%
Other (11 respondents, 19 items) (see summary below)	19	55.88%
We do not screen students	1	2.94%
Total	134	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Other screening elements (summarized):

Screening element	Responses
Settlement issues, needs	4
Time allowance for workshops, willing to commit 3 days	2
Client residence location, housing	2
Client needs and strengths, skills and abilities	2
Education level, professional background	2
Health	2
Employment ready, ready to enter labour market	2
LINC level 3	1
Family issues	1
Work experience	1
Total	19

Total number of respondents that specified "other" = 11

Comments for survey question 7

We do check all of those above, but till now there is no any ways that I will be able to help my client when they do need money for transportation or child care issues.
Clients are assessed to recognize their strengths, identify if JSW is targeted to their needs and what services/programs will better fit their needs.
I also screen whether student has attended any job search training previously
The intake form asks for clients to reveal issues/barriers affecting job readiness. Non employment related issues would be referred elsewhere
Intake form asks for issues/barriers affecting job readiness. However, Non employment issues would be referred elsewhere
Daycare and transportation is an issue to some participants, we do not screen people out but recognize that some people cannot attend due to daycare or transportation issues.
Just to make the point we do have a women only JSW at one of our sites
We admit students with sufficient English to follow the facilitator.
It would be beneficial to accept LINC Level 3 students
Comprehension to ensure they understand - not necessarily LINC Level High and readiness to work

- a. If you screen students, what does your JSW program do for students who do not pass the screening? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Sometimes they are admitted and sometimes they are referred elsewhere	17	51.52%

They are usually referred elsewhere	12	36.36%
They are usually admitted to the program anyway	4	12.12%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	33	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 33 (1 null response, 1 doesn't screen)

Comments for survey question 7a

They are referred to programs/services to enhance language skills, provide them with 'hands-on' work experience and work placements.
For those clients who are not English eligible, the JSW service is delivered in both the English and Arabic and the clients are then referred to LINC/ESL classes. Usually, such clients are grouped together so as not to disrupt those who are English eligible.
Those who do not have the appropriate immigration status as referred elsewhere. We will sometimes accept individuals whose English language skills may be slightly lower than LINC Level 4
We occasionally allow ineligible clients (e.g., refugee claimants, clients with very low English, clients with work permits) to audit the workshops.
The [agency name] does not turn eligible people away, we refer to our Job Connect program for assistance with transportation costs and try to gain support for day care from community agencies if possible. If this cannot be obtained we will meet with newcomers one-on-one or refer to our Job Connect Program
Some are able to use the NSP program
Occasionally students who straddle LINC levels 3 and 4 are admitted to the program when they demonstrate the willingness to continue with language upgrading. We administer a written test to assess their reading and writing skills and the pre-workshop interview with the facilitator helps to determine the levels of listening and speaking skills.
Admission depends on the area of screening
Other than the immigration status barrier (referred elsewhere), we accept any student who can manage to overcome their barrier to attend the workshop.
Allowed person who did not make standards to sit in and she observed. She is waiting for the next session.
It would be very beneficial if refugee claimants with a valid work permit were allowable into the program.

b. If students are not accepted and are referred elsewhere after screening, what services are they referred to most often?

Library, employment resource centre, employment assistance centre, employment related website that also serve Canadian citizens
LINC classes
Settlement services, LINC programs
LINC, 1-on-1 Job Search Coaching
The Centre for skills and development, LINC assessment/classes
Language

LINC
LINC, Job Finding Centres, Career Exploration/Counseling, Assessment Centres, Rapport Youth Services, Job Connect, Coop Program, Career Edge, Career Bridge, Happen, Mentoring also, Volunteer, Internship and Bridging programs.
LINC classes, Settlement counsellors
LINC, ESL, COSTI, ERC's (for citizens, refugee claimants, etc)
English classes, Individual employment counsellor, Settlement Counsellor
ESL/LINC. As well, they are referred internally for settlement services at the [agency name].
LINC/ESL/ELT & Employment Services
London Public Library -Employment Resource Centre, Assessment Centre-LINC Classes, Professional Associations, CAP Site in CCLC Library, WIL Employment Connections
Literacy, Settlement worker, LINC/ESL ,ERC, Employment counsellor
Job Connect
Literacy, Settlement worker, LINC/ESL ,ERC, Employment counsellor
For language upgrading: LINC or ESL programs; for suitable interventions for refugee claimants, Ontario Works and [agency name] Project Job Search.
Job Connect in-house
LINC and ESL
depends on their background
Employment services and employment resources centres based on client's needs
LINC, ESL and Employment Resource Centres
ESL, LINC and other services within [agency name] programs.
Other employment services or other Immigrant Serving Agencies (ISAs)
Career Development, Computer courses, Resource centre, OW Accreditation, high school, College courses, St. Charles Adult education services, settlement services
Referred to English Class
LINC; agencies whose mandate encompasses the immigration status that we do not.
Non profit employment agencies within community where they can have job developer work with them.
An employment assistance program which does not have restrictions based on LINC Level or immigration status
a.) Students who would be coming from distant places and have problems with transportation are usually referred to agencies closer to their place. b.)Students who registered at the middle of the month and cannot wait for the start of the next batch are usually referred to other possible agencies with multiple schedules of sessions. c.)Students who have English communication issues are being referred to ESL school
We refer them to a Language Assessment or to school to continue their learning before coming back to us

Where referred (summary in two tables)*

Specific Programs /Schools / Services	Number
LINC	18
Employment Resource Centre	12
Job Connect	3

LINC Assessment	2
WIL Employment Connections	1
St. Charles Adult Education Services	1
Rapport Youth Services	1
Ontario Works Accreditation	1
Ontario Works	1
Happen	1
ELT	1
COSTI	1
Centre for Skills & Development	1
Career Edge	1
Career Bridge	1
CAP	1
Total	47

* Note: This question relates to where clients that failed screening are referred, survey question 21 relates to where clients are successfully referred in general.

Other Referrals	Number
ESL	10
Settlement services, counsellors, ISAs	10
Employment counsellor	3
Employment services	3
Internal referral	3
English class (unspecified)	3
Job developer, 1 on 1 job search coaching	2
Career exploration, counselling, development	2
Library	2
Literacy	2
High school, school (unspecified)	2
Assessment centres (unspecified)	1
College courses (unspecified)	1
Computer courses	1
Co-op program	1
Depends	1
Employment assistance centre	1
Employment related websites	1
Internships	1
Job finding centres	1
Language assessment	1
Mentoring	1
Bridging Programs (unspecified)	1
Professional associations	1
Volunteering	1
Total	56

Comments for survey question 7b

Students who are not eligible for JSW due to immigration status will not be admitted, but referred to other programs. Students with low English levels sometimes may be admitted based on their individual communication ability.
Referred to appropriate ESL/LINC/ERC/settlement agencies.
Referred to appropriate ESL/LINC/ERC/settlement agencies.
There is a need for work search programs for refugee claimants and clients with work permits.
Job Connect is a highly complimentary program to JSW it offers support to job development when required.
Students are sometimes referred to JSW providers closer to where they live.
We are making [our agency] a 'one-stop-shopping', if can't help within our existing programs we assist the individual through our partners

8. How do you find out about students' previous knowledge and needs regarding job search skills? Pick the **one method** that you use most often.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Interview or test them before they enter the workshop to find out their interests and existing knowledge	23	65.71%
Collect information from the group at the beginning of workshop to tailor it to their needs and abilities	7	20.00%
Provide a standard curriculum that meets most students' needs	3	8.57%
Be responsive to their needs as they come up during the workshop	2	5.71%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	35	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Comments for survey question 8

For the 3 rd bullet, it is usual practice for [agency name] facilitator to assess the needs of the students during the workshop period. Based on the feedback collected, the facilitator will revise the curriculum accordingly to make the workshop more valid for the students
Common assessment model for counseling
We could not limit the answer to one method, what works best is a blend of group and individual approaches. In individual follow up we are able to further contextualize service according to their specific occupation. For example, we share information about licensing bodies, professional associations, career profiles, alternative career paths, and occupation specific websites and also ensure resume and correspondence is a match for their target occupation i.e., an IT resume differs from a teacher's resume.
Interview before workshop is conducted for every students as part of the in-take process. The 3 rd choice (responsive to emerging needs), however, is proved to be more effective in adapting the curriculum, as students began to really open up about their concerns and needs when they bonded better with the facilitator and the class during the workshop. Suggestion: To reword the question to "pick the one method that you find most effective." if this is what the question is meant to ask.
Using the JSW created intake form allows us to understand the specific needs of clients and enables us to address those issues in the workshop
During the needs assessment, prospective candidates are asked questions on their education, work/volunteer experiences and what techniques they are using to search for work in Canada. As well, they are asked to discuss their strengths and accomplishments to see whether they can 'market' their accomplishments. A quick review is done of their resumes and cover letters to see if their 'targeted' expertise is highlighted.
We also give a needs assessment form on the 1st day of the workshop
Usually at intake, clients are asked of their previous knowledge and skills. They are then scheduled in a class that would most meet their needs.
Start where the group concerns are focused and tie all topics to it.
We attempt to tailor additional information in the workshops according to the needs of the group.
By finding out their needs during the pre-workshop interviews, we can tailor the workshop contents accordingly. It is also important to respond to the participants' needs as they come up during the workshop.
It makes it easier to select the most suitable delivery module for that group.

I find that if you find that if you interview during the workshop, some newcomers like to share in front of other. Find they are more open in one-on-one
It is difficult to customize the program without having large numbers of students with similar backgrounds (i.e., large number of Engineers or Teachers).
All above mentioned methods are used because they are all equally important with the effectiveness of the workshop
The intake/assessment forms currently being piloted are not the best tools to assess client's previous knowledge/needs. We have to be responsive their needs as they come up during the workshop.

9. Do you use or recommend any self-assessment or career exploration tools (e.g., online resources) that students can use either during the workshop or after classes? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes, usually	20	58.82%
Sometimes	9	26.47%
Never	3	8.82%
Don't know	2	5.88%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

- a. If yes or sometimes, which ones (please be specific)?

jobfuture.ca, interest quiz (from CIC)
Career exploration programs as well as software and on-line career profiles and we highly recommend informational meetings and mentoring programs.
http://www.cdm.uwaterloo.ca/step1.asp , and http://www.jobsetc.ca/toolbox/quizzes/quizzes_home.do?lang=e
Essential Skills; Job Futures; National Occupational Classification System; Job Banks; Resume Maker (software)
True Colors
self assessment tool
Career Exploration (http://www.jobsetc.ca/)
we do not refer to any tools, but clients assess their skills (hard skills and soft skills) based on a self assessment exercise involving action verbs in their profession
career exploration using online resources such as jobfutures.ca and labourmarketinformation.ca
Internet usage as well as individualized assistance with resume writing and internet coaching especially when it comes to posting of resumes on-line.
Career cruising & Job futures
e.g., www.jobsetc.ca
Monster.ca, workopolis.com, charityvillage.ca

Manual developed by JSW staff for clients is used during every workshop - National Occupational Classification http://www.hrdc-drhc.gc.ca/noc - www.labourmarketinformation.ca - Jobfutures - Making Sense of Labour Market Information http://makingcareersense.org - Careers http://www.canadiancareers.com/sector.html www.Codeconnector
Choices
We have an assessment or will refer clients
Career orientation tests by one of our employment counsellor
www.jobsetc.ca , www.monster.ca , www.onwin.ca
What color is my parachute? Self Assessment tools in class-how to measure your goals? Transferable Skills sheets
NOC, Career Cruising
On line & evaluation information
Career Navigator and Quizzes, Job Futures.
Tool: Choices and a couple agencies in town that use assessment tools - one in our building.- cant think of the name of program. Staff member that is in resource centre who helps with this
We have a local program "Career Planning" which several of our clients have used and have benefited from. As far as on-line tools, we find that many individuals like the one-on-one support better than on-line, or in books.
Students are given list of websites with explanation of its uses, such as Labour Market Information, 211, training and volunteering centres, assessment of credentials, settlements and web sites to look for job postings
Self Assessment - 3 Modules (paper document)
JSW program material
We help clients fill in an assessment tool developed by World Skills CAN program. We also recommend the Waterloo University careers pages self- assessment and 'What Color is your Parachute?'

Comments (Do you find these tools helpful? Should they be used more often?)

Yes, clients are more focused and have clear information to make informed decisions in their job search process
My observation is that these tools are more helpful to new graduates and students with less work experience. JSW students are mostly internationally trained professionals with extensive work experience. When considering career change due to various reasons, their cases tend to be more complicating, and require more in-depth support. Therefore individual employment counseling is more helpful in exploring their career options.
Yes, they augment the lessons and allow students to work independently when not in class
It depends on the clients
Yes, very helpful, and they should be used at least right after the workshop, especially, those you would like to change careers.
More computers for student usage would be helpful as clients need to be able to access them. As well, more staff at each agency is needed to assist the Facilitator and Intake worker to specifically assist in resume writing and internet coaching in regards to internet job search and posting of resumes.
Web sites provided on day two of our program provide links for students who are interested in self-assessment or career exploration tools

<p>Often the testing tools have a cultural jargon that has tendency to impact newcomers negatively particularly as they are struggling with language and communication skills. The Myers Briggs tests and the Personality Dimension would be the only two self assessments I would recommend.</p>
<p>Often the testing tools have a cultural jargon and can tend to impact newcomers negatively particularly as they are struggling with language and communication skills. The Myers Briggs tests and the personality dimension would be the only two self assessments I would recommend.</p>
<p>We are not sure what is meant by this question: do you mean self-assessment and career exploration tools as opposed to job search tools? We do not do extensive career exploration during the JSW and although some self assessment is done, we build on the knowledge clients already have based on their experience and chosen fields. If you are asking about the best work search tools, we find the steps in the work search process a good starting point. While there are many online resources, we feel that our clients need real life examples and success stories to help bring this information to life. They need to be able to interact with the facilitator as so many of their questions are not answered on the internet. For example "How good does my English have to be for me to get the kind of job I want?" The answer to this question must come from a person with experience working with many people. The same is true of labour market information. Although a lot of it is out there, most people have difficulty evaluating and interpreting it. Throwing a lot of web sites at people is, in our opinion, not the most helpful approach.</p>
<p>Yes, especially for those who are confused, lost, need a career change, or who want to know their strengths/choices available.</p>
<p>Yes they should be used</p>
<p>The tools are helpful and we recommend that participants use them more often.</p>
<p>Very useful if used properly</p>
<p>Only when the student has no idea of what they want to do; in those cases self assessment helps.</p>
<p>Depends on clients level of utilizing a computer and their command of English language on their own (most programs require person to do on their own</p>
<p>Yes, specially the Labour Market Information wherein the students would be able to know every essential information which will help them with their job search and career goal. 211 and settlement website are also very useful for collecting information surrounding job search.</p>
<p>Yes, very much for those who are not in a specific profession but want to know where to start</p>
<p>They are useful and should be used often</p>
<p>These tools are helpful. However, Any new, more effective tool could be used if it is made available.</p>

Part 3: Workshop Components

10. Which of the following topics does your JSW program cover? Check all the topics that you spend at least 30 minutes on during the course of the workshop. Then go back to your checked items, and find the ten topics that your workshops usually spend the most time on. Give a rank from 1 to 10 for these top ten, with 1 being the topic that usually receives the most time. Enter comments in the third column as appropriate.

Respondents to the survey sometimes incorrectly ranked the topics in the list provided to them by assigning more than one topic the same rank (e.g., 'topic x' and 'topic z' were both given a rank of 1). Therefore the data for this question was analyzed using two methods. The first method excluded all records with multiple rankings while the second method included them. As can be seen from the table below the results for both methods were highly consistent. Though the rank for each topic differed slightly depending on the method used both methods rank the identical topics in the top 12.

JSW facilitators spend the most amount of time in workshops on the following 12 topics:

	Method 1 (Clean records only)			Method 2		
	Number	Percentage	Rank	Number	Percentage	Rank
b. How to develop a resume	18	90.00%	1	27	84.38%	2
g. How to look for work (how to use various methods - e.g., cold calling, networking, newspaper advertisements, or internet listings, unadvertised jobs)	16	80.00%	2	28	87.50%	1
k. How to prepare for an interview	15	75.00%	3	24	75.00%	3
a. How to develop a cover letter	14	70.00%	4	24	75.00%	4
l. Strategies for responding to interview questions	13	65.00%	5	23	71.88%	5
n. Facilitator-led interview role playing sessions	11	55.00%	6	20	62.50%	6
j. How to research labour market trends and/or the local economy	11	55.00%	7	18	56.25%	10
d. How to customize a resume	10	50.00%	8	19	59.38%	8
q. How to market one's skills to employers and others (including introductory statements and 'elevator speeches')	9	45.00%	9	20	62.50%	7
h. How to contact employers	9	45.00%	10	17	53.13%	11
m. Facilitator-led interview coaching sessions	9	45.00%	11	17	53.13%	12
r. How to describe skills, international experience within a Canadian context	8	40.00%	12	19	59.38%	9

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: Method 1 n=20, Method 2 n= 32

The same methods were used to determine the topics that JSW facilitators spend the least amount of time on. Again the methods yielded mostly consistent results although the rankings were not identical.

JSW facilitators spend the least amount of time in workshops on the following 10 topics:

	Method 1 (Clean records only)			Method 2		
	Number	Percentage	Rank	Number	Percentage	Rank
c. How to proofread a resume	0	0.00%	1	1	3.13%	1
t. How to manage job search expectations	0	0.00%	2	5	15.63%	7
o. How to dress for an interview	1	5.00%	3	4	12.50%	3
cc. Job specific or vocational information	1	5.00%	4	4	12.50%	4
e. How to complete a job application	2	10.00%	5	4	12.50%	5
u. How to evaluate job offers (so that you don't accept jobs that will threaten your career goals)	2	10.00%	6	4	12.50%	6
s. How to follow-up after an interview	2	10.00%	7	7	21.88%	7
w. How to adjust to the Canadian workplace (i.e., understand Canadian culture)	2	10.00%	8	-	-	12
z. How to use the services of an employment agency	3	15.00%	9	5	15.63%	8
y. How to manage / maintain a job	3	15.00%	10	4	12.50%	2

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: Method 1 n=20, Method 2 n= 32

Comments for question 10 by topic (14 respondents)

Topic	Comments
a. How to develop a cover letter	Very Important
	Ranking these ten topics is not consistently accurate because the length of time spent on each topics sometimes depend on the group's dynamics.
b. How to develop a resume	Very Important
c. How to proofread a resume	Can be tied in to b
	Integrated into "b"
	They can go to H/R after they learn from us to work on examples, and learn how to tailor their resumes. Frees up more time to do self assessment and to practice goals and use internet for samples
d. How to customize a resume	Duplicating numbers mean that I spend almost the same amount of time on each of these topics
	Can be tied in to b
	May spend more time one on one
	Work with H/R

e. How to complete a job application	Students can learn how to fill out an application form by reviewing a sample form by themselves. With the limited time given in each JSW, and the volume and importance of so many other topics, I tend not to spend much time talking about application forms
	Some importance
	We do not spend more than 15 minutes on this topic
	Integrated into "b"
	Learn about, have model but do not spend much time on it
f. How to obtain / develop references	Important
	Integrated into "b"
	5 minutes explain why they need and they can use us for a reference if they meet requirements what we expect - on time, etc.
g. How to look for work (how to use various methods - e.g., cold calling, networking, newspaper advertisements, or internet listings, unadvertised jobs)	Necessary
	We find that clients are reluctant to apply what they learn unless we have practice sessions to follow up
	Spend whole day on this. Ex employer comes to talk to group to give advice, jobs available, what to do, etc. - info in morning and practice in pm
h. How to contact employers	Necessary
	All on second day
i. How to find relevant companies	May spend more time one on one
	Discussed in connection with resources for job search
	All on second day
j. How to research labour market trends and/or the local economy	This is important but need to equip 'do-it-yourself' skill so participants can do the search themselves. E.g. tools to access social services
	I put great emphasis on the importance of occupational research, by which I mean how to obtain specific, updated information about one's chosen profession, rather than researching general market trend.
	Connected to h and i
	All on second day
k. How to prepare for an interview	Very important
	Whole morning working on interview questions /. afternoon they practice - 3rd day
l. Strategies for responding to interview questions	Essential
	(for k-p): Given that many students have not had interviews before and are struggling with English as second language, preparing them for interviews is important and requires considerable time

	I think the interview process is the key source of work that the client needs help with in order to network in his field for information interviews, to have the confidence that they can do the job professionally and to articulate it in a manner that does not let the Canadian employer hesitate or doubt the clients appropriateness. As you know many of the clients have never experienced the interview process previously.
	I think the interview process is the key source of work that the client needs help with in order to network in his field for information interviews, to have the confidence that they can do the job professionally and to articulate it in a manner that does not let the Canadian employer hesitate or doubt the client's appropriateness. As you know many of the clients have never experienced the interview process previously.
	Integrated into "k"
	Done at same time as k.
m. Facilitator-led interview coaching sessions	If time permits
	Do afternoon 3rd day
n. Facilitator-led interview role playing sessions	Necessary
	If time permits
	Whole afternoon
o. How to dress for an interview	This topic used to be one of the foci. However I found recent newcomers have much better ideas about how to dress for an interview than before. Now I tend to use the time for other topics that are of more interest.
	Connected to k
	When required
	Integrated into "k"
	All together from k-p
p. How to conduct oneself during an interview	Connected to k
q. How to market one's skills to employers and others (including introductory statements and 'elevator speeches')	We find that all of these topics are critical. However, we think pen and paper application are less of a priority for the target group we serve and generally highly skilled and educated workers understand the nuances of business dress codes.
	Essential
	All the topics are very important.
	All are important. Not necessary to have all separate though. Some are covered at the same time/ i.e., prep for interview/facilitator led sessions. Legal rights is important but put in list because used up in questions that are mostly the same
	2nd day intensively = work with real employer
r. How to describe skills, international experience within a Canadian context	Necessary

	NOC Bible used and compare with their skills
s. How to follow-up after an interview	Integrated into "m"
	5 minutes - why you should
t. How to manage job search expectations	In my workshop there is no fixed time allocated especially for this topic. However, in almost each topic discussions around this issue will come up, and will be encouraged and guided.
	Somewhat
	most clients do not seem to understand much as all they want is a job
u. How to evaluate job offers (so that you don't accept jobs that will threaten your career goals)	Important
	Integrated into "t"
	Not much time spent on this - examples shown to them. Start somewhere and move from there
v. What to do if you don't have Canadian work experience	We offer multiple strategies as how to handle this complex barrier and we have evidence that the strategies we share actually work.
	Important
	Extensively, guest speakers (past students, volunteer coordinators, refer to volunteer centre, stress what they get out of it even though they do not get paid. Choose a field where they are most comfortable or in a sector that is good for them
w. How to adjust to the Canadian workplace (i.e., understand Canadian culture)	Again there may not be much time specifically allocated for this topic. Discussions of the issues are interwoven with other topics
	Necessary
	We do not spend much time as we provide this as post workshop support on a one to one basis
	Talk about with them and with ex-employer - about Canada is their country now
x. How and why to use self-assessments	Important
	Crucial - this is most important - without this they cannot go forth. They do it themselves, they have material for it and talk with themselves. Without knowing what they selling, they cannot sell. You have to believe in what you have to sell. We have speakers and video and documents
y. How to manage / maintain a job	Somewhat
	This is given when they get the job - do not put a lot of time on this - they are not ready to see how to maintain. They need to know how to get it.
z. How to use the services of an employment agency	Somewhat - depends on knowledge of participants

	There is legitimate concern by many in the field, that employment agencies adversely affect newcomers. However, [agency name] emphasizes the positive aspects of employment agencies hiring process i.e. skilled based methodology allowing for faster access to acquiring Canadian experience. It is paid employment related to their field and not unpaid volunteer work that will help them in the long run.
	Integrated into "g"
	Covered 2nd day
aa. How to locate / join professional organizations, associations, discussion groups, communities of practice or other groups/individuals in a specific area of interest	This is a critical topic and we would have ranked on the top but are constrained by a numerical ranking system
	Important
	Discuss in workshop how to develop network contacts. Organize with our other employment services staff, quarterly networking sessions.
	Through the internet and with H/R to practice. Give them web site information. Show them how to find different websites.
bb. Information regarding legal rights (e.g., Employment Standards Act, minimum wage, etc.)	Very important topic. Although it may not be regarded as the learning priority by students at the beginning of the workshop, students usually find the information very helpful afterwards.
	Important
	guest speaker session offered once a month in our ERC
	1/2 at the most. I have the ESA in room and explain what consequences and what rights they have. They know the rights but also what can happen if they are working, if they do not get overtime - they know by law they should get but they have to make a choice about the job
cc. Job specific or vocational information	Important to have. Not enough resource available now.
	Somewhat
	Offered in one on one sessions
	Integrated into "j"
	Talk about and give websites for job sites, informed on 2nd day. I do not measure time - hard to pin point how much time - some groups need more of some items to learn and others need different

11. Do the students complete a resume by the time they finish the workshop sessions (not including any follow-up period)? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
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Yes - mostly (50% to 89% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)	9	26.47%
No / Hardly Ever (less than 10%)	9	26.47%
Yes – almost always (90% to 100% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)	8	23.53%
Yes - occasionally (10% to 24% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)	6	17.65%
Yes - sometimes (25% to 49% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)	2	5.88%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 11

<p>We are not clear if the definition of 'finish the workshop' includes the individual follow up service, following the workshop. If it does, then the answer is yes. If no, then only occasionally will a client have a complete resume before the workshop ends. The issue is also quality not just the completion of the mechanics of a resume. We do a deep grammatical and spelling review and look for dangling modifiers, faulty parallelism, incorrect use of capitalization, plural and singular voice, punctuation, correct use of active voice, and overall readability. In the editing process, we also ensure the resumes and companion correspondence clearly suit the job target(s). Some participants, by virtue of their rich and diversified skill sets and interests, can target multiple employment opportunities and therefore require more than one resume.</p>
<p>Question 1: Does the question also include the case in which clients already have a useable resume when they come to the workshop? My answer doesn't include these clients. Question 2: I usually use time outside the workshop to finish this part of the job. what I focus on during the workshop is the philosophy behind a highly marketable resume</p>
<p>Most individuals' resumes are a work in progress and may require extra work beyond the JSW workshop sessions</p>
<p>They always need more time to do resume and practice according to a job position. Most of the time they do come back for more resume critics.</p>
<p>Participants want to spend a day or 2 to work on preparing the different styles of resumes and learn how to emphasize their relevant global expertise. During the workshop participants do work in-class to formulate some of the more challenging sections of their resumes, for example profile, skill sets and relevant skills.</p>
<p>Most of the time the Facilitator does not have time to individually check the resumes. Mostly, clients will make individual appointments the week after the workshop where the facilitator will check the resumes.</p>
<p>Generally students don't complete a resume prior to or during the workshop sessions. Following formal sessions and with on the proper instruction from the JSW Facilitator , client are able to produce their resume.</p>
<p>Until now, we have not had computers set-up which did not allow us to help our clients create resumes at our site.</p>
<p>Generally students don't complete a resume pre workshop. They prepare it post workshop based on the proper guidance from the JSW Facilitator during the sessions.</p>

Resumes are completed, we type them and they leave with them on the 3rd day of the workshop. They receive hard copies, disk when required and/or emailed to home computers. When required hot mail accounts are set up.

Following week follow up one to one meeting and e counseling

Some participants are unable to have an updated resume prepared in the course of a 3-day workshop. We follow up with them after the workshop for a copy to be kept on file.

It is not feasible, given the quantity of information that should be delivered at the speed which is beneficial to participants. We recommend participants complete a draft after completing the workshop, so that they can spend time researching the labour market, researching specific companies, etc. before writing their resume.

They do mini-resume, this is not the time, it is time consuming, if they need to work on other skills first. They have our H/R to help them after they finish the program. They have examples handouts. When they go to mentorship program, they are mentored with someone in their field. The resume is done with terminology of field so it happens when they are working with i.e. teacher, engineer, etc. The mentorship program happens right after the workshop. Mentorship is profession specific. This coaching is valuable and they are supported. We have meetings monthly, and I have follow-up time with them. Working with someone from their field is perfect for them.

a. If yes, are the resumes reviewed for spelling, grammatical errors and clarity as a part of the workshop? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	21	84.00%
Yes - Sometimes	2	8.00%
No - Hardly ever	2	8.00%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	25	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 25

Comments for survey question 11a

This is done individually, not during a session
The resumes are always reviewed but privately with the client
It falls between sometimes and always
This is crucial, however participants are encouraged to check address and unique spelling such as places of resident and/or education outside of Canada
A resume is a tool & participants have to develop good habits during the JSW

12. What percentage of students on average would you estimate seek one-on-one assistance with their resumes after the workshop completes (i.e., during the follow-up period)? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Most (90% to 100% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)	15	50.00%

Many (50% to 89% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)	11	36.67%
Several (25% to 49% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)	3	10.00%
Some (10% to 24% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)	1	3.33%
Few (Less than 10% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	30	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 30 (This question not in pilot, 1 null response)

Comments for survey question 12 (10 respondents)

Participants are seen 2 days after completion of JSW to ensure that their resumes are 100% error free and targeted to the positions/sectors. 99.5% of the clientele have difficulty in compressing their skills sets because of their wide experiences and training. Assistance is given to prepare at least one general resume and cover letter and clients use this to modify to meet the specifications of prospective employers.
All clients who complete the workshop are given a one on one appointment to assist with their resumes
The facilitator most often needs to schedule clients in for assistance in resume writing as it is time consuming.
Some are very self directed and needed just the reassurance that they are on the right track, that the JSW session confirmed for them.
Participants are encouraged to continue to use on on-site resources such as computers, job postings, hundreds are printed daily and placed into binders according to field of employment, e.g. office, service industry, skilled trades, etc
It depends on several factors: distance, finances, level of needs
Some students acquire enough confidence to conduct job search on their own, while others may need one-on-one support.
We have a Resource Centre to ensure that their good generic resume is put into our system to make it easier when they have to work on another resume for a position that comes up.
Mostly students do not need one-o-one assistance with their resume until they are got their Landed Immigrant Status and ready to get into the work force.
All are sent to have mentor do it or have H/R person do it.

13. Recognizing that individual needs differ, how much individual assistance **on average** would be necessary to help a student develop a resume and/or cover letter? (Please phrase answer in hours and minutes or in a range of hours and minutes e.g., "3 hours" or "1 to 2 hours")

	Range	Median	Average
Hours for resume / cover letter development necessary*	~1 to 7	2.5	2.59

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 33

* Respondents were reluctant to specify an average time stressing that individual newcomer needs and circumstances differed.

Comments for survey question 13 (12 respondents)

If resume writing was out of the workshop it would be more effective to the individual client
We refer clients to access further assistance in resume/cover letter writing, however, many clients return to our program for further support for: - Individualized support and attention to the craft of resume and cover letter development according to their level of expertise, education and occupational background. - Clients report that this kind, quality and level of customized individual support is not available in other programs in York Region. - Both Facilitators in the JSW program have taken advanced level resume writing courses to ensure that resumes and correspondence are at the appropriate level to meet the needs of usually highly educated professional and trades people newcomers. - We have received feedback that the kind of resume and correspondence support participants receive by participating in our JSW program has made a significant difference in terms of successful outcomes in meeting employment goals. It is our view that internationally trained individuals require specialized support that bridges and recognizes global experience. Through this specialized support, participants can effectively communicate through "Canadian style" resumes and job search communication - an understanding of a local labour market needs and simultaneously, also "champion" their relevant global skills and experience.
This is dependent on the nature of professions, experience and education = this differs, unable to measure as some can take 1 hour, as in the case of an Administrative Assistant, but 2 days as in the case of a Project Manager who has difficulty in measuring his accomplishments and takes time to recall same. Specific time frame is very challenging to measure as each individual has unique experiences, education and training. As well, 60% of clientele have broad international / professional experience and this can take up to 2 days to (extract appropriate information) given interruptions and other immediate tasks which have to be completed, during the time of resume and cover letter preparation.
It is a time consuming process as many students lack computer ability and therefore the facilitator most often spends the time at the computer.
In order to produce both transferable and survival resumes 4-5 hours would be ideal.
4-5 Hours would be preferred to do both transferable resumes and survival resumes for each client.
Professional clients e.g. engineers, chemical technicians can require 3 -4 hours per resume
2-3 hours as some students make return visits
It expected that the individual will have a good draft to work from
Total would be approximately 2-3 hours per resume. Some clients use more than one resume, and/or more than one style.
Most clients are career disoriented, and when they come for assistance other issues always come up before they are be able to give the information needed to create a resume.
Mentors will work on their resume as much as they need after the JSW. We spend generally an hour for a generic resume in the workshop. Professional resume with professional terminology is created with Mentor. It is not worth spending time on for us

14. Recognizing that individual needs differ, how much individual assistance **on average** does each student currently receive to develop a resume and/or cover letter? (Please phrase answer in hours and minutes or in a range of hours and minutes e.g., "3 hours" or "1 to 2 hours")

	Range	Median	Average
Hours for resume / cover letter development provided*	~.5 to 9	1.5	2.07

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 32

* Respondents were reluctant to specify an average time stressing that individual newcomer needs and circumstances differed.

Comments for survey question 14 (12 respondents)

Due to wide range of English language proficiency of the students, the individual assistance varies from 30 min to 3 hours per student
During the workshop resume and cover letter are presented in approximately 5 hours. Individual follow up usually takes more than 3 hours and is based on client needs, which vary. The initial meeting following the workshop normally lasts for 1.5 hour. After this meeting, many clients will work on their resumes and cover letters on their own and then forward it via email or return for further review and editing. This level of editing requires substantial facilitator time and sometimes we review resumes and correspondence 3 times per client to ensure it meets labour market standards.
40 minutes doesn't include the assistance the student receives from other program staff including 1-on-1 job coaching services.
When meetings are not possible or necessary, correspondence is done through email and phone. This provides flexibility to the client while allowing them to hone telephone and writing skills
Again dependent on the professions/expertise and position/sector targets, allow between 4 hours to 9 hours. see # 13 above. Sometimes clients return with additional information and then the resumes and cover letters take more time to complete.
For some clients, help is needed in targeting resumes to particular positions. We sometimes do this to provide them with an example, so they can carry on when they apply to other openings. This usually brings the time to more than 3 hours in total.
time does not include typing and proof reading
In person or online or combination. We make appointments on the last day of the workshop.
It can exceed 2 hours when French versions of their resume, cover letter have to be developed as well (e.g. application in French speaking schools, associations, ...)
Usually the student receives approximately one hour with the facilitator in a follow-up session and then electronic communication and more facilitator's time on documents continues for 1 to 2 months depending on the student.
We schedule follow-up appointments to handle such.
More or less than one hour. Refer to mentorship for additional help in professional field

15. Are students encouraged to arrive at the workshop sessions on time and dressed appropriately for work? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always*	28	84.85%
Yes - Sometimes	2	6.06%
No - Hardly ever	2	6.06%
Don't know	1	3.03%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Total	33	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 33

* Note: Many respondents clarified that students are encouraged to arrive on time but noted that appropriate dress was not necessarily encouraged. See comments below for more information.

Comments for survey question 15 (15 respondents)

Dressed for an interview situation will be discussed at the follow up session.
We do encourage to come on time and treat like a serious job search situation dress code is comfortable except for the interview session
Students are encouraged to arrive on time but they are not encouraged to always dress for an interview situation, we give them the option of dressing for an interview for the interview component
Only when mock interview / interview role play is planned, students will be required to dress up. All students are encouraged to arrive on time.
Clients are encouraged to dress professionally and to arrive on time as I've observed that formal dress tends to situate clients in a professional / business like mode, boost their self confidence and influence they way they interact and present self. I let clients know that punctuality and commitment are qualities which employers look for in prospective candidates and are questions which are presented to me (as 99% of the time I serve as a referee) about their behaviors.
Punctuality is emphasized but dress code - allowed to wear jeans and t shirts
Encouraged to arrive on time, but not asked to dress for work
Clients are always encouraged to arrive on time, but for most newcomers, [ends here in original]
We expect students to come on time but not dressed appropriately for work
Yes, they are encouraged to arrive on time. We do not specify how they should be dressed. We do discuss how to dress for a job interview.
We have answered yes to encouraged to arrive on time not dressed appropriately for work. We feel this may offer a class distinction between blue collar and professional and make some people uncomfortable who have what may be regarded as inappropriate clothing, e.g. sweat shirts and jeans.
Good habits have to be formed, this is about employment.
The students are encouraged to arrive on time. There is no demand during the workshop for business attire.
Last workshop was during March Break - it was very casual
I tell them before workshop that I am reference for them so they have a choice.

16. If students arrive at workshop sessions late, are inappropriately dressed/groomed, or if inappropriate behaviour is noted during the workshop are they given feedback to help them correct the problem? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	23	67.65%
Yes - Sometimes	10	29.41%
Don't know	1	2.94%
No - Hardly ever	0	0.00%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 16 (13 respondents)

At the workshop session, facilitator will mention about being late will lead to negative consequence to not only job interview but also to maintain the job.
Most of the students are professionals: engineers, teachers, doctors, nurses, accountants, managers, marketing and business professionals, university professors and researchers. Most of them model, by example, polished business attire. We do, however, give appropriate advice on how to dress for the Canadian seasons.
Feedback is provided individually on how to better self.
It is part of the group norms and house keeping rules
I do not ask them to come to the workshop dressed for work
Time management is stressed during the workshop. However, students may attend the workshop in casual clothing. Hygiene issues are addressed in program and of course appropriate work dress code is covered.
Time management is stressed during the workshop. However students may atten the workshop in casual clothing but a hygiene issue will be addressed and of course appropriate work dress code is covered in the workshop.
Most of our clients exhibit good behaviour without any reminding. The exception to that is they don't always remember to turn cell phones off. This can be distracting. We wish we could deal better with lateness, as participants arriving late are disruptive.
This will be done on a individual basis, in a non-judgmental and in private with a high degree of sensitivity first exploring cause.
The facilitators are sensitive to the needs of the participants, e.g. They may be late for the evening workshop because of work. If participants have had to miss some sessions due to acceptable reasons (e.g. attending job interviews), they can make up for the missed sessions in the next JSW so as to complete the course.
If they did, but have not had that happen
Inappropriately dressed/groomed never happened yet but will surely give helpful feedback if it will ever happen in the future
I tell them that I cannot be their reference, because I do not want to lie to an employer. IF they let me know ahead of time that they will be late due to circumstances. I always address this.

17. Do students have an opportunity to participate in and/or observe others perform mock interviews or role-playing exercises? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	27	79.41%
Yes - Sometimes	7	20.59%
No - Hardly ever	0	0.00%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments to survey question 17 (9 respondents)

Whether to have mock interviews depends on which phases students are at in their job search. With a group that is not ready for interviews yet, other formats of delivering the interview session will be used.
During the interviewing session of the workshop, students are filmed doing a mock interview and the video is played back in front of the class for feedback. In addition, students are given written evaluations after each interview from both interviewers.
The majority of participants enjoy this exercise and welcome critique on ways to improve their answers to possible questions.
All mock interviews are video taped and played in the class
Clients almost always comment that the opportunity to practice is the most rewarding part of the workshop for them.
When time permits.
The only time this does not happen is if we are very rushed for time. We have in this case, provided an additional session.
We also use video cam to record the mock interviews and viewed by the group or the interviewed individual, giving them a chance to have a good look of their interviews and be their own self critique.
We do mock interview. I stress the most importance of observing other people doing. They learn what not to do and what to do. We spend a lot of time on this

18. Are students encouraged to think of and rehearse interview questions during class?
Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	29	85.29%
Yes - Sometimes	5	14.71%
No - Hardly ever	0	0.00%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 18 (6 respondents)

This is done so that they will be conscious and have some experience of how to structure / present their answers during interview role play.
We always ask them to identify questions that they are concerned about. We deal with some of the most common, plus behaviour based questions and illegal questions.
There is insufficient time to devote to the rehearsal of interview questions at present.
Peer group support and encouragement
Also we encourage to look interview videos after workshops and sometimes during the workshops
To be able to see themselves in the eyes of the employer. Have them exposed to the different people with different accents to measure the comprehension.

19. Do you interact with each student to develop an after-workshop employment action plan?

Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	21	61.76%
Yes - Sometimes	9	26.47%
No - Hardly ever	2	5.88%
No - Never	2	5.88%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 19 (13 respondents)

Most of our clients have good direction and make goal plans at the beginning of the workshop. They are also offered continual support.
This is done to ensure that participants identify realistic action plans and ways to achieve same.
Students are encouraged to make an after-workshop appointment to finalize their resumes and discuss employment plans
I interact with students to develop the employment action plan as required. At times, however, the student has already developed his or her own plan.
I interact with students to develop the employment action plan as required. At times, however, the student has already developed his or her own plan.
The answer is "yes-mostly". Sometimes a client is unavailable, finds a job, goes back to their home country for awhile, has family issues...
Not everyone one can stay after a workshop due to childcare and other obligations, however it is offered to all
Due to the demand of workshop schedules, the facilitators are not always able to follow up with each student immediately after the workshop. In the 3-month follow-up, we assess the difficulties encountered in implementing the action plans and the status of their job search.
For easier follow-up
We do placements to our participants
Not as of yet, we will be.
It is important for students to have employment action plan that consist their short term, medium term, and long term goal.
Depend upon the need

a. If yes, what are the components of a typical action plan?

Resume preparation, interview improvement, volunteering (if do not have any Canadian work experience)

<p>A typical action plan will contain the clients' objective and goals. Based on an assessment of client needs, the action plan includes the following components: - Career research steps and recommendations - Job search planning and tools - Skills and language training recommendations - Referrals to: professional associations and licensing bodies, community services, settlement programs and services (HOST, ISAP, NSP, SEPYR), compatible employment programs, for example, mentoring and bridging programs. - Relevant websites, books, directories, videos and software to help clients further their goals - Up-to-date information relating to government funded initiatives designed to help our newcomer population.</p>
<p>With students with such needs I often refer them to work with our one-on-one job search coaches who will develop an action plan with them. At the same time, all students are encouraged to come back to discuss their next step plan with the JSW facilitator using email or face-to-face appointments.</p>
<p>Short term goals developing into long-term with a time-line.</p>
<p>Identification of career/job; steps to achieve same i.e. if regulated profession then assessment by regulatory body; no work experience - referring to volunteer / coop / internship placements-to break barriers; researching companies, contacting prospective employers via telephone / email / in person; network opportunities; follow-ups.</p>
<p>clear goals, time frame, steps to be taken, resources needed, cost</p>
<p>I interact with students to develop an employment action plan, as required; however some students have already done this, or will do this, through individual employment counselling as part of the Employment Assistance Program within my agency.</p>
<p>Clients will target the employment field they have identified, or go to school for more training, and will report back to the facilitator to talk of the success of obtaining employment or needing more assistance and time with the facilitator.</p>
<p>Schedule for contacting employers; referral information for other community resources and training opportunities; schedule for completion of language training, obtaining credential assessments and certifications.</p>
<p>Referral to other agencies, job search leads, recommendations for volunteering and cover letter construction</p>
<p>The main goal is to have a clear, concise target. The action plan includes the tasks to be developed and implemented to attain this goal. Aspects of the action plan include time lines for each of the following resume and cover letter development It also includes the student creating a networking circle, researching, establishing and preparing for information interviews and job interviews. Students are required to research relevant companies in order to access the hidden job market, timelines for cold calling employers and/or researching and attending programs for further training a training/skills development target.</p>
<p>Meeting to create a resume, cover letter, preparation for interview</p>
<p>The main goal is to have a clear concise target. The action plan is the tasks developed and implemented to attain this goal. Aspects of the action plan include time lines for each of the following resume & cover letter development, student creating a networking circle, research, establish and prepare for information interviews and job interviews, research relevant companies, accessing the hidden job market, timelines for cold calling employers and/or researching and attending programs for further training, a training/skills development target.</p>
<p>We identify short and long term goals and what is necessary to reach them, as well as barriers to reaching the goal. We introduce them to resources, skill development, credential evaluation, licensing, and programs/courses/services available.</p>
<p>Managing expectations, research on LMI, utilizing the resource centre, access to individual counselling and for eligible participants job development services</p>

Next steps required e.g. credential assessment, make contact with list of employers developed by student, research further employers
CFT's employment counsellors develop an action plan in individualized counselling sessions
Short term goals (such as labour market research; strengthening of job search tools (such as customizing resumes to specific jobs applied for); job search steps/routines; plan for participation in community programs to obtain Canadian experience; identify skills gaps and join courses to upgrade skills and experience
Develop short & long-term strategies
Job Search, alternative employment, training programs, additional resources
Sending resumes to the employers and give information of employers to our clients
Research, time frame, goals (short & long term), appointment for 1st appointment with us.
Assessing what was done before and modifying the long and short term goals and options for the person.
Short term and long term goal setting, credential assessment. referral to appropriate agencies to remove employment barriers, tracking and ongoing support

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 24

20. Many immigrants state that one barrier to job search is that they cannot demonstrate the Canadian equivalents of their international education and experience to employers. Do your JSW workshops help students to explain their skills and experience in terms that are relevant to the Canadian jobs they are seeking? Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes - Always	30	88.24%
Yes - Sometimes	4	11.76%
No - Hardly ever	0	0.00%
No - Never	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 20 (11 respondents)

We also help clients to create communication bridges with employers to share relevant global experience and education as well as to connect with employers in a "Canadian" communication and cultural context.
The workshop teaches participants to market and connect their relevant transferable global expertise with the requirements of sectors / positions. As well as, focus is on assisting clients to emphasize how they can help in increasing the profitability of companies.
Many students get in-depth help with this through the Employment Assistance Program, as mentioned above (especially with the issue of degree equivalency), however, I do discuss with students how to highlight their "transferable skills" for the job they are seeking in the Canadian job market.
The problem many clients are facing is that even after they have explained their skills and experiences in "Canadian terms" on their resumes, more employers see that there has been no employment within in Canada, and they will not accept them.

Due to the workshop, the students have a more tangible grasp of Canadian employer's expectations and have been given relevant information about their fields. The feedback demonstrates that they are more aware of and have more confidence to pursue their job search.
Because of the workshop, the students have learned what are the Canadian Employer's expectations and given relevant information about their fields. As such the feedback is that they are more aware and have more confidence to pursue their job search.
A big aspect of this is the self marketing, which varies from culture to culture and country to country. We show them what is normal and acceptable here from networking strategies to calling employers, to developing scripts to explain their skills.
Students are encouraged to use the NOC, useful websites and other occupational information to learn more about job descriptions, job/skill requirements and the terminology used for different professions. All these are useful references for students who wish to showcase their education and experience in a Canadian context.
It takes time and effort for a large group it is easier on individual bases
We emphasize more on the equating international experience than education as experience is more difficult to prove.
We explain to them accreditation is something they do not have control of. This may or may not give them the job. There are other options. They can sometimes work in their field without the license. Show how strong they are in their field. If there are so-so, they can expect difficulties, if at Top, they should prefer the field, some companies will not enforce the license, they may not get the title but can still work in the field.

Part 4: Information and Referral and Partnerships

21. What services do you successfully refer your JSW students to? **Check all that apply.**

Responses	Number	Percentage
Volunteer opportunities	30	88.24%
LINC English or French upgrading	30	88.24%
Computers skills upgrading	28	82.35%
Job Connect	27	79.41%
Mentorship program	23	67.65%
Academic skills upgrading	23	67.65%
Employment agency (e.g., fee based headhunter)	21	61.76%
Job Finding Club	20	58.82%
Career counselling	20	58.82%
Literacy skills upgrading	19	55.88%
Internship program	18	52.94%
Other (18 respondents, 42 items) (see below)	18	52.94%
Child care	16	47.06%
Other English or French upgrading	15	44.12%
Health care	13	38.24%
Total	321	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Summary of other referrals

	Number
Settlement services	5
Career Bridge, other bridging programs	4
Co-ops	3
Specific programs for women	3
Professional associations, communities	2
YMCA	2
Academic credentials assessment	2
Regulatory bodies, accreditation assistance	2
Library, community referrals	2
ERC's	1
Practice firms	1
Career exploration programs	1
Self employment options, programs	1
Government ministries	1
Drive test centres	1
Social Welfare	1
Food banks	1
Sector specific programs	1
Information sessions	1
Workplace cultural training	1
ELT	1
Training and education programs	1
College	1
CPR training	1
Other training (to help build self confidence/esteem)	1
New Canadian program	1
Total	42

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 21 (5 respondents)

By "Internship Program", I mean "Bridging Programs" and other paid or unpaid work placements
Employment Agencies are part of the Job Search Strategies but not fee based agencies
It should also be noted that the majority of our clients have post secondary [ends here in original]
Based on each participant individual needs
Employment agencies without fees. We give them ideas for school and available, they choose. We talk about LINC upgrading but do not send them

22. What are the **most serious gaps** in appropriate services for your JSW students?
Check all that apply.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Internship program	23	69.70%
Mentorship program	15	45.45%
Child care	15	45.45%
Volunteer opportunities	13	39.39%
Academic skills upgrading	11	33.33%
Career counselling	10	30.30%
Computers skills upgrading	10	30.30%
Other (see below)	10	30.30%
Job Finding Club	6	18.18%
LINC English or French upgrading	5	15.15%
Job Connect	4	12.12%
Employment agency (e.g., fee based headhunter)	4	12.12%
Health care	4	12.12%
Other English or French upgrading	4	12.12%
Literacy skills upgrading	2	6.06%
Total		NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 33

Description of other gaps (10 respondents)

Bridging programs
Sector specific employment services; Customized, integrated employment programs rather than over-general, stand-alone employment workshops
Transportation and a Job Developer
Employment placement programs
Transportation assistance
Job placements
Sector specific enhanced language programs. I.T. These programs must be not only available but reasonably accessible.
The gaps in service are due to the limited financial resources of our clients they cannot afford to upgrade their post secondary education to gain recognized Canadian education due to the necessity to bring money in to support their families. Family doctors are too hard to find in [name of municipality]
Communication classes that are focused, flexible and brief
Academic upgrading that is not so expensive.

Comments for survey question 22 (17 respondents)

Requirement of Internship - Level 7 in English language proficiency and need to have at least 3 years of working experience in their home country. As a result, it encounters difficulties to refer students. As for computer skills training, it usually is 1 hour workshop. If students especially male students look for more in-depth computer skill training, it is not available
Too early to evaluate
The more serious gaps the lack of bridging programs in York Region and employer education in the areas of the advantages of hiring from a global talent pool. In terms of service, other job search interventions currently available to newcomers do not always match the precise and complex needs of highly educated and skilled workers who simultaneously adapting to a new cultural environment. We believe JSW creates a welcoming, open, safe and cross-cultural environment where participants receive support in all of these areas. We would like to see more companion programs supporting JSW such as appropriate case management, co-op, bridging programs and employer education initiatives.
There is a lack of mentors in some professions
Some programs are offering free credential assessments and participants are questioning why JSW does not facilitate same.
Professional terminology language classes with focus on pronunciation and clarity , job finding clubs and job connect programs focusing on ITPs and professional jobs
Most serious gap is English language competency. LINC level-4 students (and often higher) are still struggling to speak English and this represents a huge barrier in their job search. Furthermore, even students more fluent in English are often not able to communicate using terminology relevant to their occupation. Next biggest gap is lack of volunteer or internship opportunities (relevant to students' needs and/or occupation). Also, many students feel that they are unable to take "unpaid" internship or volunteer opportunities as they are struggling financially and need to take "survival jobs" to support themselves and their families.
Clients are very disappointed in not moving into a Job Ready Program after completing JSW. Even on a voluntary basis.
We recommend computer skills upgrading when programs are available, but there is a shortage of available programs
Often the students need a level 7 English to get into the mentoring programs. This proves to be very discouraging for students seeking employment with level 5 English. There is a huge gap for volunteer opportunities for newcomers that is actually related in a meaningful manner to their professional title. Students in unpaid work placements struggle financially to support their families. They take survival jobs to pay the rent and feed the kids. Often, many relinquish their goals due to financial constraints.
Often the students need a level 7 to get into the mentoring programs. This proves to be very discouraging for students seeking employment with level 5 English. This demonstrates the language competency barrier. LINC level 4 and 4+ are struggling to speak English. One can only imagine the pressures to look and obtain a job under these circumstances. However, some do get jobs Even newcomers with much higher level English competencies struggle with the workplace terminology and communication skills. There is a huge gap for volunteer opportunities for newcomers that is actually related in a meaningful manner to their professional title. Students in unpaid work placements struggle financially to support their families. They take survival jobs to pay the rent and feed the kids. Often many relinquish their goals to earn a \$15 an hour position or less.
Public transit in the GTA needs to be improved so that clients can access companies freely. Many jobs are now in the GTA rather than in the City of Toronto and newcomers cannot access them without this importance service. Child care is a necessity especially for women, who are job ready but may need to drop out for several years. At that point, their skills are outdated and possibilities decreased due to gaps in their work history. Lack of safe, affordable and accessible child care is a serious issue that affects the long term goals and prospects of many newcomers.

It is not always easy to find volunteering opportunities that allow the students to make use of or upgrade their work skills and experience. For academic upgrading, students sometimes find the cost formidable. The need to take survival jobs also preclude some from devoting time to upgrading.
Participants sometimes get employed but if they work for more than 20 hours they cannot get into Job Connect services for example. Although this is being addressed. Also the other serious gap is FACILITATORS need facilitation assistance during the three days.
Don't have mentorship program or Internship program. Have at the YMCA but have to be a certain age. once over 29 years you cannot apply
Due to the LCP provisions on schooling and the schedules they have with the care giving jobs, clients cannot access these services because they were usually in the weekdays.
I feel that people with extensive skills must have a program/coop or placement where they can work for free to prove themselves and then given an exam. They are not all at the same level to meet Canadian standards. More and More some skills are valuable with those coming to our country. For whatever reason, this is not used. We are losing knowledge and lots of them move to US because they have a better system. A placement component, training (not to get profession) initiation, to be exposed to the Canadian workplace. They do not see the climate. It makes them shy, insecure and unable to sell what they have. A little bit of time, for free., if they had that opportunity . Internship - #1 GAP. Mentorship #2 GAP. My observation #1 and #2 is crucial for the students. Licensing process, even if licensed professional, there is a lot of work involved. Serious gaps, educators employers to know what capacity the students have.

23. How do your JSW staff find out about the needs of local employers? **Check all that apply.**

Responses	Number	Percentage
Monitor the newspaper or online job ads	32	94.12%
Visit or phone local employers	20	58.82%
Have ongoing relationships with employers (e.g., participation in industry associations)	19	55.88%
Other (see table below)	17	50.00%
Do not monitor the needs of local employers	1	2.94%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	89	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Other ways to find out about the needs of local employers (17 respondents)

As Facilitators, we do our best to keep abreast of current labour market trends.
Attend conferences, seminars involving employers, such as employer panels; Invite employers as guest speakers to the agency to talk about their hiring practice
We held a luncheon hosted by the Mayor [of town] to the Business community to discuss the benefits of hiring newcomers
Researching companies via websites, trade directories and "Who's Hiring".
Job fairs, past successful clients, invite as guest speakers, net work
Keep a list of employers that have hired my students

1. Ongoing relationships with other agencies, 2. Job fairs, information sessions and conferences put on by local employers
Attend conferences, job fairs
Attend conferences, job fairs
Our agency has job developers who refer positions to us and speak to us about their employer needs. Our agency's [numerous] locations often host information sessions with employers which staff and clients may attend and receive valuable labour market information.
Feedback from job developers in our agency
Frequent calls from employers seeking bilingual people
Labour market research, job fairs etc...
Visit job fairs; visit online job sites
Through on-going communication, case management and team work with our Job Developers
Networking
Have ongoing relationships with successful clients.

Comments for survey question 23 (11 respondents)

In addition to the above participants are encouraged to review sector reports / trends and annual reports of companies.
Given the amount of time required to do intake/assessment, counselling, workshops, outreach and administration, there is little time left for the Facilitator to develop connections with employers. A co-facilitator, or job developer, would be helpful in this regard.
Time permitting, JSW staff will network with the employers in the area or with employers in the community as well as employment agencies. [Agency name] has been able to hold a session this year, and another one just for engineers, where an employment agency specific for this field, has been able to present a workshop. Two of the clients have been able to obtain a job. The TTC is coming to recruit and present a workshop in early April 2007 for all areas of expertise from drivers to mechanics to engineers. As helpful as these sessions are, they are time consuming to prepare for and the Facilitator needs assistance.
The JSW program is a pre-employment program. There is no job development component. Perhaps a new position for job development could be added to further the students support.
The JSW program is a pre-employment program. There is no job development component. Perhaps a new position for job development could be added to further the students support.
Contact with employers is extremely valuable because it offers us up-to-date, reliable and specific labour market information. We take all opportunities we can to take advantage of employer presentations.
[Agency name] has four full time job developers with a data bank of 500+ active employers. JSW case conferences on a regular basis with Job developers as well monitoring jobs down loaded daily from popular job sites such as Service Canada,
Visiting or phoning local employers is useful but the current work demands do not allow time for doing so. Since our agency receives faxed/emailed job postings from the community, our facilitators are able to do job-matching and referrals to students via email. Occasionally we visit job fairs for an overview of hiring opportunities available out there.
We pride ourselves in the established relationships that we have formed with a number of employers in our region.
Keep flyers, etc. Because of specific fields, I train the students how to access the information on needs of employers. I cannot know what all employers need in all fields.

There is a single Employment Developer for all JSW programs

Part 5: Workshop Objectives and Outcomes

24. What objectives are students encouraged to achieve by the end of the workshop or shortly afterwards? **Check all** the objectives below that are **explicitly communicated to students** in all of your workshops.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Learning how to translate international skills into relevant Canadian descriptions	34	100.00%
Learning how to search for a job	33	97.06%
Learning how to talk to employers	33	97.06%
Completing a resume	32	94.12%
How to stay motivated during the job search process	31	91.18%
Getting job interviews	28	82.35%
Completing an employment action plan	25	73.53%
Obtaining a job	23	67.65%
Getting job offers	22	64.71%
Other (see below)	4	11.76%
We do not communicate specific objectives to students	0	0.00%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	265	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Other objectives (4 respondents)

To take ownership of their job search from research stage to job offer and beyond- to explore short and long term options in terms of career paths.
How to make well-informed decisions when choosing career directions; How to get information of their chosen profession
The need not only to rely on us but to seek out other options in the community to serve their ongoing needs that the JSW cannot supply (beyond the three month active period).
Network, hidden job market

Comments for survey question 24 (8 respondents)

We sit down individually and make an action plan
if the client's short term goal is finding a job, client is encouraged to get job offers and obtain a job. This is communicated at the 1:1 meeting with the client
Some clients do achieve their targets within the workshops or shortly thereafter. However, the average student needs the 3 month, post-program support to achieve the objectives
Clients who achieve meeting their targets within the workshops or shortly thereafter. However, the average student needs the 3 month support to achieve the objectives

The objectives belong to the client - if they are professionally trained and are able to support themselves individuals will often spend many months seeking jobs commensurate with their level of education. If the most important objective is to get a job any job to bring money in then employment will be found shortly after completing the workshop
Did not do employment action plan - not enough time
We communicate the above in a very step-based way, while demonstrating that it is possible to do several tasks concurrently.
Resume to a point - complete later in mentorship program. They know what they can and cannot do and what they need to achieve. They are brought up to their objectives. What is possible, what is reality of their existence here. They establish where they are heading, how they get there. They establish where their talents lie and then find where they want to go. They hate numbers. Talent is a solid way for success.

25. What are the top 2 or 3 things a student needs to do successfully at the end of the workshop in order for your agency to conclude that the workshop has been successful?

The responses to this question were summarized and then counted for three key outcomes - resumes (developed or know how to develop), interviews (participate in, obtain) and employment action plans.

Responses summarized

Responses	Number	Percentage
Develop a resume (targeted, proper) / and cover letter	20	57.14%
Know how to participate effectively in an interview	16	45.71%
Know how to develop a resume / cover letter	10	28.57%
Develop a plan of action, employment plan, follow up on action plan	9	25.71%
Know how to contact employers, contact employers, including cold calls	7	20.00%
Maintain contact with JSW facilitator, they can get support from agency, they are supported	7	20.00%
Know how to communicate / market skills (generally and including self-introductory statements)	6	17.14%
Know how to conduct a job search, conduct a job search	6	17.14%
Conduct research, research field, research job listings, find job listings, research LMI, understand where to find jobs	6	17.14%
Know their strengths and weaknesses / know themselves / understands transferable skills	5	14.29%
Are confident and motivated to conduct job search (as an outcome in and of itself)	4	11.43%
Be able to network, network	4	11.43%
Be job ready	2	5.71%
Other	2	5.71%
Continues to improve job search skills	2	5.71%
Get interviews	1	2.86%
Actively participate in workshop	1	2.86%
Get job offers	1	2.86%
Have realistic expectations	1	2.86%

Know their rights, legal issues	1	2.86%
Obtain dream job or using skills in related jobs	1	2.86%
Overcome different obstacles and barriers	1	2.86%
Can understand job postings	1	2.86%
Regular attendance at workshop	1	2.86%
Total	115	NA
Feel confidence / self esteem in combination with other outcomes (e.g., feel confident in job search, feel confidence in interviews, etc)	9	
Be motivated in combination with other outcomes	2	
	11	

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Responses summarized for resumes, interviews, employment action plans

Responses	Number	Percentage
Explicitly mentioned resumes	30	85.71%
Explicitly mentioned interviews	17	48.57%
Explicitly mentioned employment action plans	9	25.71%
Total	56	NA

Comments for survey question 25 (4 respondents)

As well, having the ability to remain positive and focus on their employment goals, despite the many challenges they experience during the job search process.
We hope that on completing the workshop, students will feel upbeat about their job search prospects and are equipped to do further research to help themselves in the long run.
No test
Each participant prioritizes differently, and has individual goals and needs.

26. How do you assess whether these objectives have been successfully achieved? What criteria do you use to judge whether or not training has been successful?

Response	Number	Percentage
Demonstrated appropriate behavior (completed resume, successful mock interviews, joined professional association, contacted employers, obtained interviews, action plans, etc.)	14	40.00%
Follow-up meetings, calls, emails	14	40.00%
Feedback, end of workshop feedback, evaluation	13	37.14%
Subjective evaluation during workshop, quizzes	5	14.29%
Outcomes measured against goals	3	8.57%
Got a job	2	5.71%
Total	51	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Comments for survey question 26 (1 Respondent)

We also incorporate JSW training into our ELT delivered service

27. If you had to guess, how would you compare the success of your agency's Job Search Workshops in relation to other JSW programs in Ontario? Choose only one response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Much better than average	14	43.75%
Somewhat better than average	11	34.38%
Don't know	5	15.63%
About average	2	6.25%
Lower than average	0	0.00%
Total	32	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 32

Please explain:

Interview (intensive interview will be provided as follow up session) and database on words to prepare resume will be discussed with students. In addition, there is good equipments like laptop, digital video camera and LCD projector for the program delivery
It is too early to comment
Most of our referrals come from word of mouth.
My evaluation was based on the feedback from the students. I listed reasons in a later question of this survey
We rely on internal referrals from settlement staff for our client base. This is extremely effective because [agency name] is able to provide a wide range of services in one location.
I feel that since JSW curriculum is arranged to cover set topics therefore the outcome should be somewhat similar.
We do mock interviews by videotaping clients. This helps them become aware which areas they need to improve regarding their communications skills. We are also available to meet with them individually in order to help them achieve their employment goals.
Our employment outcomes are high (around 65%), we spend extra workshop hours to cover all components, feedback from Mentoring program staff, Most of our clients are referred by word of mouth from past clients
Other resources would be helpful to complement program and improve success rate, such as enhanced language training, co-facilitator or job developer, and work placement post workshop.
1) A large number of our clients attended the JSW somewhere else before coming to [agency name]. 2) We have been getting clients who traveled to [agency name] from Vaughan, Mississauga, Richmond Hill and Brampton.
We submit monthly statistics but do not receive comparative statistics from other JSW programs
Opinion based on networking with JSW colleagues
I have no idea what other JSW programs offer because we have recently started our workshops.
Opinion based on networking with JSW colleagues, feedback from clients and other community partners

<p>Our project officer says that he has complete faith in our program. We get very positive client feedback from our clients. In some cases, they compare our services to other services (not the JSW). The JSW coordinator asked one of our facilitators to conduct a workshop for the other JSW's on needs assessment. Other staff in our agency often ask for our advice and expertise. We have developed our own manual based on client needs and we are continually updating our handouts and workshops.</p>
<p>Flexibility of our delivery gives more opportunity to newcomers to participate and learn the techniques they need. In our multi-service agency, JSW participants have access to a broad range of services and supports they require to help them be successful.</p>
<p>Most clients start their job search with a big asset: being able to speak French</p>
<p>At [agency name] we assist job seekers from a diverse backgrounds to find employment and to integrate into the Canadian job market. We achieve this by providing employment services, linking employers to skilled people and building strong networks in collaboration with community partners. [Agency name] is an employment services agency that specializes in providing assistance to newcomers who are looking for work. In addition, we benefit from having the other employment programs which have already established targets and infrastructure that support our JSW programs outcomes.</p>
<p>We provide a lot of follow-up services and in particular job referrals. As a result of the rapport developed during the workshop and the helpful attitude of our facilitators, students are keen to keep in touch with our staff. We encourage them to stay positive in the often long and stressful job search process and provide support where possible. We also try to organize one reunion gathering per year for mutual support and sharing of success stories. Over the past 3 years, we have held a job fair in the summer to engage local employers in the hiring of newcomers. We invite both current and past JSW students to participate in the event.</p>
<p>It shows when we attend JSW Conferences among others that we are doing a great job. This is not a fair question</p>
<p>Many of our clients are working now</p>
<p>Excellent Evaluations by participants, good overall outcomes</p>
<p>Somewhat better because we deal with immigrants at your agency in other capacities and therefore we are sensitive to their needs. Perfect location. 4 LINC and ESL classes and daycare and Board of Education who does upgrading and self-directed studies. Two large computer resource centres. When doing resumes, two of us where in the resource centre, computers set up in horse shoe, went through lesson, gave them a disk, and walked down the hall and gave them one on one help. Made diplomas for students as well to add to their portfolio.</p>
<p>We usually have a strong "success" rate after completion of workshop, but have lower participant numbers due to the size of our communities.</p>
<p>Considering that our organization's clients are caregivers, we fully understand their needs, barriers, and strengths and we are able to customize the workshop to meet their needs.</p>
<p>[Potentially identifying information removed.] I feel that we are much better than average. We follow up clients, establish mentorship program, actively involved in Employment Networking Group, I visit job fairs, 150 resource books, to gather material to help our students. [...] We take a particular importance of the job for the students. We are advocating and lobbying constantly. Another aspect is giving them examples, connecting them with employers, places. Show them that you are behind them in all possible way. Leave doors open. Not just giving the data. Numbers are important but we have to realize that training for employment is everywhere. Numbers should not be the important measurement.</p>

Expertise and a love for the job is the most important. People who are doing the job should be carefully screened. Our population is changing. If you are not interested in their work and just giving information, what kind of image are we giving to the student who may be more educated than we are. We are to give them enthusiasm to help them get a job and a place in Canada. A love for this work is important In some other agencies the groups sit alone and the leader is in a separate room. How can the group learn watching a TV?

Total number of survey respondents: 35
 Total number of respondents this question: 26

28. If you could teach **only two things** successfully to a student what would you teach?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Resume	17	24.29%
Interviews	15	21.43%
Be positive/stay motivated / self-confidence	9	12.86%
Job Search Broad / General	7	10.00%
Communication (resumes / interviews / verbal / written)	7	10.00%
Research	6	8.57%
Networking	2	2.86%
Goals	2	2.86%
Workers rights	1	1.43%
Transfer Background Skills	1	1.43%
Know yourself and what you can offer	1	1.43%
Job maintenance	1	1.43%
Hidden Job Market	1	1.43%
Total	70	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35
 Total number of respondents this question: 35

Responses Clustered	Number	Percentage
Cluster - Communicate skills, verbal / written (resumes / interviews)	39	55.71%
Cluster - All other topics	20	28.57%
Cluster - Job search in general / specific techniques / job search strategy	11	15.71%
Total	70	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Comments for survey question 28 (11 respondents)

Canadian culture
Teaching only 2 elements to participants would be insufficient to address their varied needs and will not prepare them well to address the many barriers and challenges they may experience during their job search in Canada. Clients do need to be empowered and have knowledge of the accreditation process (if professions are regulated), understand the work culture and ethics, labor standards and rights.
A priority with our program is to convey the message that a job seeker needs to believe in themselves and to let nothing stand in their way to success.
A priority with our program is to convey the message that a job seeker needs to believe in themselves and to let nothing stand in their way to success.
We would like the students to realize the importance of self-help and to be ready to ask for support whenever needed. A positive attitude is essential for achieving success in job interviews.
These two things cannot go alone, other areas have to be covered to come out with a total well rounded individual after the JSW.
When we have a very good knowledge of ourselves, we can go further.
I will teach them motivational tips.
Resume because they won't get the interview without the resume and interviews - need to know how to sell themselves. Teach them what not to do and how not to sit.
Although the above mention are important but are not limited to in successful job search.
Teaching networking skills are essential

Part 6: Program Delivery, Management and Administration

29. What tools, supports or equipment would make your agency more successful in delivering Job Search Workshops?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Equipment for practice, teaching (DVD player, computers, video camera, TV, projector, telephones, internet, tape recorders etc.)	14	41.18%
Job development, job developer	10	29.41%
Opportunities for employers, subject matter experts to speak at workshops, list of guest speakers should be provided, itinerate speakers	6	17.65%
Enhanced PowerPoint training for facilitators, other refresher courses, professional development, resume writing certifications, memberships in professional associations, skills transfer knowledge, more information about employment websites	5	14.71%
Child care assistance, transportation assistance, TTC tokens	5	14.71%
Tap into / connect to other programs (Job Connect, Mentoring, bridging programs, Talk English Café, NEW in Canada)	4	11.76%

Resource center for clients (computers, fax, copier, telephones, books, videos), More resources for clients - Scotts Directory, CCAI, Personality Dimensions, books	4	11.76%
More outreach materials, share outreach strategies, outreach coordinator	4	11.76%
More recent and varied samples (e.g., mock panel interviews), PowerPoints, JSW manual updates	3	8.82%
Money for food during workshops, refreshments, snacks	3	8.82%
Client database, case management database	3	8.82%
Co-facilitator	3	8.82%
Strong connection with organizations that regulate professions, connections to business community	2	5.88%
Work station for volunteers, stipend for volunteers	1	2.94%
Share best practices	1	2.94%
Organize network activities for clients (post workshop)	1	2.94%
One stop shop	1	2.94%
Mobile classroom	1	2.94%
Funding to subscribe to employment websites, software licenses, etc.	1	2.94%
Cozy well equipped room, comfortable chairs, motivating posters, quiet separate space for study, separate office for facilitators for culturally sensitive discussions with clients	1	2.94%
Career counsellor	1	2.94%
Total	74	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 29 (3 Respondents)

New program - we are in process of getting out support materials in order [sic]
Especially having a satellite office in another city, this would prove very beneficial to us.
It is important that the Facilitator be able to show the students how to post resume in the Internet in different manners.

30. Do workshop facilitators have sufficient flexibility in designing and delivering the curriculum?
Choose **only one** response.

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes	28	82.35%
No	6	17.65%
Don't know	0	0.00%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

If no, please comment (6 respondents)

We have flexibility in updating the information we provide but not in what must be presented during the workshop.

Facilitators have to abide by the guidelines and set curriculum but clients are requesting specific components of JSW (e.g. resume or cover letter writing; role playing interview questions or cold calls) and are demanding individual based counselling/dialogue. Such clients do not want to attend a complete 3 day workshop, these clients tend not to participate.

Some of us regard the freedom to design and deliver the workshop very highly. We appreciate the trust placed in us and our expertise and take it seriously.

We support our facilitators in using required flexibility to meet clients' needs, and JSW has not restricted our flexible approach to date. Flexibility in timing of workshop, location, and catering content to specific groups while still covering JSW fundamental curriculum.

We know that each workshop program must contain certain topics (which we agree are important), but leave little time to deliver individualized information.

Yes, it is mandatory to change the curriculum to help those in areas that they need.

31. If you had the resources to do things differently in relation to the Job Search Workshops program what would you do? (Describe up to three things)

Response	Number	Percentage
Expand JSW - add hands-on portions, hold support workshops to practice what is taught, more interactive program, more time for practice (have phone lines available to practice cold calling, computer terminals, mock interviews), full day on transferable skills	15	46.88%
Have a job developer, placement officer, make job/work placements, have time to network with employers, career counselling	13	40.63%
Employers, invite for Q/A, bring in as mentors, employer forums	5	15.63%
Offer specific JSW workshops for different populations (e.g., occupation, self-employed), offer workshops to organizations	5	15.63%
Having funding to, connect to mentoring, internships, job shadowing, volunteer placement, job trials, job training	5	15.63%
Invite subject matter experts, speakers	3	9.38%
Ongoing support groups for internationally trained professionals, job finding clubs, English cafes	3	9.38%
Offer child care on site, provide transportation, childcare assistance	3	9.38%
Increase communication between agencies, have someone visit agencies to compare practices, eliminate sense of competition between facilitators, provide online chat	3	9.38%
Provide central database, online chat, funded client database	3	9.38%
Have a JSW team (facilitator, admin, job developer), have an assistant facilitator	2	6.25%
Offer coffee, snacks - refreshments for networking opportunity	2	6.25%
Expand eligibility (include newcomers 5 yrs or less - even citizens), offer 1-on-1 support to those not eligible for JSW	2	6.25%
English language training, pronunciation for newcomers	2	6.25%
Focus on quality	2	6.25%
Offer several shorter workshops each month, rather than 1 - 3 day session	1	3.13%
Provide free computer training	1	3.13%
Give employers incentives to hire	1	3.13%
Assist clients with validation of their education credentials	1	3.13%
Provide an assisted job search area (allow clients to drop in)	1	3.13%
Resume certification for all JSW facilitators	1	3.13%
Increase pay for facilitators	1	3.13%
Increase JSW marketing in the community	1	3.13%
Get feedback from class, see if there is something else they want	1	3.13%
Increase resources	1	3.13%
Total	78	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 32

32. What information do you use to improve your Job Search Workshops program?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Current labour market information, current job trends, internet research, read newspaper, local labour market	25	80.65%
Look for updated, new resources for workshops (books, directories, websites, PowerPoint, trends in resumes, etc.), JSW web site	9	29.03%
Feedback from clients, employers	7	22.58%
Networking, attend events, job fairs	5	16.13%
JSW and other conferences, professional development	5	16.13%
Information on new programs (bridging, internships)	2	6.45%
Update the JSW manual, the manual	2	6.45%
Share success stories, employers hiring newcomers	1	3.23%
Regular staff meetings	1	3.23%
Offer settlement support	1	3.23%
Make the program more hands on	1	3.23%
Total	59	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 31 (This question was *not* in the pilot survey)

33. What do you think are the greatest strengths of your agency's Job Search Workshops?

Mock interview, database for words to prepare resume, off-site workshops (to make the services more accessible to immigrants), supportive and flexible.
We address the need of the client and are proactive in seeking feedback to make the workshop better
The agency fosters professionalism and cross-cultural communication and sensitivity. The facilitators bring a variety of experiences and skills in the employment field including: -Cross-cultural skills, human resources training and experience, employment counselling, writing and editing skills, resourcefulness, sensitivity and creativity. We also listen and learn from each and every client and are able to integrate the learning into practice.

<p>1. Strong team support. JSW in our agency is a part of an integrated settlement and employment service provision model. Different teams work together to support clients' job search, including settlement counselors, employment consultants, LINC and other English training programs, and job developer. Students always comment that the teamwork "atmosphere" of the agency makes them feel well supported. 2. Facilitators The facilitators' professionalism and enthusiasm in doing their job, and their deep understanding of the needs, challenges, as well as the strengths of their clients. 3. Continuous and strong support after JSW. Innovative ways to support students after the workshop are used, such as online discussion group, gathering activity, active email communication, storing sharing, etc. Students form a strong sense of belonging to the JSW community of our agency. Through JSW they have information and access to all kinds of resources available within and outside the agency.</p>
Internal referral process
Seasoned facilitation and being able to connect with the clients by putting myself in their shoes.
More personal approach, they feel like they are part of the family, and most of all the snacks that they are getting helps a lot.
Empowering clients, information targeted to clients' needs, connecting information with the reality, practice interviews and cold calls and supporting clients to vocalize their experiences / needs without them feeling pressured / different. Also, providing a friendly and supportive environment and making appropriate referrals.
Our Agency are able to provide settlement services, emotional support for certain Ethnic groups like (Mandarin, Farsi, Spanish and Portuguese) also have LINC classes and conversation club that helps them improve their communication skills
Committed hard working staff, strong follow up support, well developed workshops, focus on ITPs
The facilitator's training and experience; the location is central to the neighbourhood where majority of clients come from; agency also offers other programs to which students can be referred (i.e. LINC, Employment Assistance Program, etc.)
The [agency name] is a settlement service organization and as such, newcomer clients [ends here in original]
1, Excellent customer service 2, On-site support 3, Cultural sensitive program delivery
Facilitators' responsiveness to the needs of JSW participants as they arise during the workshops - - partnership between CCLC and WIL Employment Connections - - connection with LINC and ESL classes
The skills, experience and training of the JSW Facilitator
Positive attitude of the facilitators.
The skills, experience and training of the JSW Facilitators as well as the support and interaction with members of othe agency teams
Workshop success begins and ends with good staff! These are the people who interact with our newcomers and make them feel encouraged, welcomed, hopeful and confident through knowledge and skills. It's helpful to have stability and low turnover among staff and a large agency such as ours can offer the salaries and benefits to encourage staff to stay in their position. Experienced staff with good judgement and life experience can be very reassuring and credible with our highly sophisticated professionals.
Seamless service - great staff
As a multi-service agency, we are able to offer multiple services and supports to our clients such ERC, Job connect, LINC, settlement, women services; as well as effective information and referrals from our collaboration with other agencies and participation in a multitude of umbrella organizations e.g. OCASI, CASIP and local associations e.g. North Etobicoke Revitalization Project.

Think we reason to what our clients have to say. I think that we teach many things that are Canadian in nature. Many bad advice is given to clients on how they should do their job search.
The fact that French speaking immigrants have access to these type of workshop in French
Established employment connections, other programs, additional languages and that we focus on only employment
Our extensive follow-up services offered to JSW students - Our facilitators' helpful attitude and rapport with the participants make them feel comfortable about returning for post-workshop service - The excellent attendance records of our students are a testament to the quality of the services we render
Dedicated professional facilitators and [partnership] partnerships
Open-mindedness, comprehension, professionalism and personal behaviour with clients.
Good Curriculum, very good facilitators, complementarity of other programs; job development, ELT, resource centre.
Network
The Facilitators, power point presentations, computer lab and Facilitator client interaction
We have experienced facilitators and flexible in our time and days of our workshops. We have so many facilities within the building so we do not have to send them outside for the services.
Knowledgeable staff and other settlement services on-site.
The Job Search Workshop Facilitator who herself was an Internationally educated and trained professional, came here in Canada as Caregiver; took the same Job Search Workshop, upgraded her skills and education, and employed all the techniques and tips she learned from the workshop. These facts plus the facilitator's continuous professional development equipped the agency's workshop with more understanding of the challenges faced by clients and therefore is able to cater to their needs.
Experience (length of experience do it). Good climate to do (have what I need), I am right person to do the job. I love what I do. Support in every point. (Psychological and material support). Connecting with other agencies delivering. We help each other, connect and share information. Right resources. (mentorship program)
Serves as a platform to give newcomers a sense of belonging and worth
The unique partnership of the [partnership] agencies

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

34. What do you think are the greatest weaknesses of your agency's Job Search Workshops?

Do not have budget to set up computer laboratory for the students and do not have sufficient budget to purchase some books eg. Scott Directory is expensive, about \$300
Program too new
The number of workshops that must be delivered. We sometimes deliver 4 workshops in one month which creates a 'bottleneck' and overworks the entire team. We do not receive sufficient funds for resources for clients and professional development for the JSW team.
1. More direct advocacy / education to employers on the benefits of hiring immigrants is needed . 2. Not being able to provide child care services for students with such needs.
Not enough time for the interview skills workshop
Less resources for clients, ex computers, printers, etc.
Delivered in a group format only.

Our Agency needs an Employment Resource Center
High target numbers, Improper office space, old computers and telephones, no job developer, not enough staff
English language level tends to be lower than minimum language level for JSW; there is no workplace component and few volunteer opportunities for students post workshop
Clients usually are disappointed as they seem to think that at the end of the course it would lead them to a position. The Facilitator needs more flexibility and time to network with employers.
No other settlement programs at the same site.
- Inability to provide financial assistance for transportation, child care, or other needed services such as translation and evaluation of documents
Salaries are not commensurate to colleagues in the field - JSW program would benefit from other employment related programs within agency - Limited awareness of JSW within community
A larger space for the resource centre.
We feel that the workshop is not enough by itself to instill the skills and knowledge of effective job search. We do make referrals to other programs and services, but our newcomers often wish to continue with us once they have established a rapport. We would like to have more time individually with clients (fewer clients overall). Newcomers are at a crucial time in their lives and the decisions that they make now will greatly affect their future. They like to rely on us for information, advice and support as they go through the challenges of their work search. We would like the time to be able to contact them more frequently.
Insufficient resources
We are very hard to reach. Many client it to far to come to have a workshop.
TTC costs not covered by the program
Additional funds for marketing strategies
A job developer would be a big help in generating more resources and job leads to assist our JSW clients.
We cannot take everyone who needs the JSW because of the criteria set for eligibility to attend JSW program and not even go across into Hull. The numbers would increase even more.
We do not tolerate unnecessary discussions.
None so far for the agency As a general, issue, however, the absence of a job placement or training incentive component
We overcome our weakness
location/visibility
All the different languages and backgrounds that the participants come from sometimes can sometimes cause you to change the way you approach things with them. In some countries, they put their pictures on their resumes; you really have to know their backgrounds, which can be time consuming. You have to explain so many times, you have to repeat yourself to help them understand. We did not use as many handouts. We made them more simplistic for the group of students to understand. Some of the icebreakers we had we could not use due to them not being able to understand. We had a clerical person who could retype the document to make it simpler and clear at a grade 8 level basically. The command of English is not that good.
Unknown.
Lack of Computer Training Centre that is available to caregivers who have very limited schedules which is often in weekends only

I am having less and less clients. Affect our work. There are workshops given everywhere. In schools, supposed to teach languages, job search workshops, in health care centres, people are getting help with resumes but are missing support, and examples and training to look. Let every one do what they are best at. Having larger numbers is a better learning environment and it affects everyone in Ottawa. Worrying about the quality of work, having smaller numbers affects how the group learns and succeeds. It is harder on the trainer as well if we see people losing the quality of help that they are not getting

None

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 31

35. What professional development opportunities are needed for workshop facilitators, managers and/or administrators?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Refresher courses, professional development, conferences, professional development retreats	8	23.53%
Advanced resume writing, resume certification, latest resume trends	7	20.59%
Facilitation, public speaking skills, practical demonstrations	6	17.65%
Labour market update seminars, full time research person to research shared by all agencies, keep agencies up to date with changes to legislation (rather than training), Kept current on developments affecting newcomers	4	11.76%
Career counselling, career development, training in use of career assessment tools	3	8.82%
Effective management, supervision	3	8.82%
Interview training	3	8.82%
Outreach strategies, marketing, writing for advertising purposes	3	8.82%
Communication training, cross-cultural communication	3	8.82%
Opportunity to network	2	5.88%
Coordination meetings with JSW staff, regular JSW meetings	2	5.88%
Life skills training	2	5.88%
Counselling, how to relate to people, human relations	2	5.88%
Training on what JSW entails (for managers)	2	5.88%
Training related to employment (for administrators)	2	5.88%
More frequent updates of sector-specific information	1	2.94%
Training on how to educate employers on the benefits of hiring immigrants	1	2.94%
Ongoing training on how to best serve highly skilled/qualified immigrants	1	2.94%
Can't think of anything	1	2.94%
Leadership training	1	2.94%
Time management	1	2.94%
Conflict resolution	1	2.94%
Use of spreadsheets, diagnostic tools	1	2.94%
Neurolinguistic programming and other adult education methods	1	2.94%

How to handle stress and to handle difficult clients	1	2.94%
Human resources	1	2.94%
Employment assessment	1	2.94%
How to integrate other employment programs (access funding, development), integrate employer links	1	2.94%
Mentoring developments courses	1	2.94%
How to make resource material with appropriate levels of English	1	2.94%
Training in use of new technology and equipment	1	2.94%
Training in high-level information and referral	1	2.94%
As part of professional development recognition should be given to time spend observing other job search programs, visiting employers, and talking to other professionals such as Human Resources Specialists	1	2.94%
Total	70	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

36. What are the top three barriers that you hear from your students regarding their job search efforts?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Lack of Canadian experience	27	77.14%
Official language skills, expressing themselves clearly, confidently, poor communication skills	23	65.71%
Experience, education not recognized	13	37.14%
Transportation	6	17.14%
Lack of knowledge about Canadian culture, cultural differences, culture shock	5	14.29%
Do not know how to search for jobs, hidden job leads, lack information, don't know where to find positions, follow-ups	5	14.29%
Childcare	5	14.29%
Accreditation/licensing/regulation professions - difficult, costly, in general	4	11.43%
Survival jobs prevents attainment of career goals	3	8.57%
Shortage of networking possibilities, not knowing a lot of people	3	8.57%
Financial difficulties (general)	3	8.57%
Equating their careers to a Canadian career, trying to find companies that offer jobs similar to what they are looking for	3	8.57%
Lack of volunteering opportunities, lack of mentoring, internships, etc.	2	5.71%
Being seen as overqualified	2	5.71%
Visible minority discrimination	1	2.86%
Lack of self-esteem	1	2.86%
Lack of knowledge social system, settlement services	1	2.86%
Housing	1	2.86%
Federal government's policy of hiring only citizens	1	2.86%

Accessible computer training (for caregivers)	1	2.86%
Total	110	NA

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 35

Comments for survey question 36 (6 respondents)

As well, for many clients, not having the skills to 'market' themselves has proven to be a barrier because of the cultural expectation to be modest
These barriers tend to disempower some clients as they initially accept low-paying jobs to provide for the basics of survival. Continued frustration is developing in health and marital issues for newcomer professionals seeking work in their field of expertise.
Clients from a foreign-trained profession are stating that employers are rejecting them as being over qualified and not giving them a chance to prove themselves even though they are willing to start at the bottom.
We need much more CIC advocacy to support our clients to get the jobs they deserve and are trained and experienced to do.
We need much more CIC advocacy to support our clients get the jobs they deserve and are trained and experienced to do.
Cultural differences play a big role in how our clients look for work and how they express themselves.

37. Do you have any recommendations for how these barriers might be addressed by the JSW program or CIC?

Budget for childminding and transportation subsidy, include volunteer co-ordination of immigrants be part of the practicum of the program
Introduce wage subsidies for newcomers
Systemic issues needs to be addressed at the systemic level. CIC and other government functions need to advocate and support employers, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders to take solid actions to break down these barriers.
Provide transportation (bus tickets) to clients who do not have cars/money to travel
Partnerships with stake-holders in the three above areas which cause barriers
CIC should try to offer bus tickets, and be able to fund for job developer it will make a big different
Complementing program with a Job Developer and work placements (with recipients receiving some form of stipend) after completion of workshop. Assisting with subsidizing cost of accreditation for those who really cannot afford.
Additional programs to meet these barriers
include job development component and have job developers as part of the JSW program, funding for job finding clubs, talk English cafes to practice professional language, cultural trips events, child care support, process to access internships, etc
1. Enhanced language training programs, especially sector specific 2. JSW be lengthened to better prepare students 3. JSW to include work placement post workshop 4. It would be preferable to have immigrants aware of possible "barriers" prior to immigrating, especially in terms of English language fluency required by employers. For internationally trained professionals who are planning to work in their field, It would speed up their job search and increase chance of success in finding relevant work if they already spoke English at a fluent enough level before immigrating (including terminology relevant to their field)

<p>JSW staff need to hold regular meetings with main stream employers and to be able to refer all clients who had passed through the workshops to them. Therefore, liaison between JSW organizations and employers need to be put in place.</p>
<p>To provide "one stop" services to cater to the various needs of internationally-trained professionals</p>
<p>Barriers are already addressed during the JSW through the information provided on employment preparation but continue to be a frustration for job seekers. This is also being addressed by the London Economic Development Corporation through their new publications "global talent". One booklet is being distributed to local employers, encouraging them to recognize the skills and education of newcomers. The second booklet is provided to newcomers and includes a good summary of the process of seeking employment in London.</p>
<p>1. More Enhanced language training programs --sector specific 2. More access to bridging programs 3. More practical knowledge of what immigrants face upon entry to the workforce before they arrive for example a program similar to JSW in their country regarding Canadian job/career practices 4. Providing financial incentives (similar to wage subsidy) to offer employers to hire students</p>
<p>Immigrants who come to Canada should be able to get a job with their degree, from their home country. Employers should not make Canadian experience a priority in hiring someone who is a newcomer.</p>
<p>1. More Enhanced language training programs --sector specific 2. More access to bridging programs-- waiting for document evaluation clearance, sets clients back further, and many more bridging programs. Look at Pathways for Engineers. Only so many could get in I think it was 15 at a time. That is too little there ought to be multiple classes The Access program for Engineer again they have to have documentation. I think it should be understood that once an immigrant has begun the evaluation process then they ought to have access to the program. Often these programs are pilot programs that have limited access and disappear after a year. 3. More practical knowledge of what immigrants face upon entry to the workforce before they arrive(JSW Education in their country regarding Canadian job/career practices 4. Providing financial incentives (similar to wage subsidy) to offer employers to newcomers</p>
<p>CIC and Service Canada need to get the message to employers that their comment about lack of Canadian experience is against the Human Rights Code. Employers might phrase their comments in a way that would be more helpful to the client. For example, asking about a specific software would then allow the client to know what skills are missing. Associations and trade unions need to be more accountable for their policies and practices that discourage newcomers from being included. The Fairness Act has been a good step in the right direction. Education of employers regarding cultural awareness.</p>
<p>Money given to the agency to use at their discretion and with supporting rationale, e.g. money for translation. accreditation of documents</p>
<p>Inform newcomers better about the challenges before they arrive in Canada; more promotion of newcomers' skills to employers; job developer connected to JSW program. Overall, CIC needs to support a continuum of information and job search service delivery that newcomers can access at different stages in their integration process, and in different locations. Eliminate barriers to newcomers created by different funders, criteria for accessing different services, etc.</p>
<p>Internships or employment subsidies to hire newcomers would be excellent. The On-site program was an excellent program that I think would be excellent for the JSW program. This program was run by HRDC but could be easily adapted for Newcomers. http://epi.ca/</p>
<p>Initiative by the government to promote immigrants cultural difference to employers. Also, more accurate information given to immigrants in the embassies during the selection process.</p>
<p>Additional funding to provide tokens to and from the program, training supports for courses or items required for employment in their specific field i.e. construction worker hard hat and boots</p>

- Advanced, job-related English classes offered in flexible time schedules to meet different needs - Retaining the services of job developers for job leads and intensive labour market research - More government-funded bridging programs - Continue to educate (or provide incentives to) employers to encourage hiring of newcomers without Canadian experience.
Professional development for exchange of information with potential employers. Have a conference CIC/ employers can hear from the immigrants themselves but this has to be coordinated to create space for strategic sharing and openness perhaps organized [in name of municipality] as there are so many things happening in Toronto.
No
"Canadian Experience' is not a legal ground for accessing a job. Government should place it as such under discriminatory employment practice. For JSW and CIC: funding related to a job placement component.
Allocate some special jobs for newcomers to get Canadian experience
Employers would be more willing to recognize global experience, if they had the support of wage subsidies or something similar. Allowing professionals to work in their field with supervision while their credentials are being assessed at a reasonable cost. Internships etc.
Maybe very specific training in those areas or even an email with recommended reading, tips or a newsletter. A website with info.
If information could be prepared that identifies some advantages to hiring internationally-trained/educated individuals, specifically targeted to employers, HR Departments and Recruiters.
a. Change the LCP provisions regarding caregiver's education. b. Provide more available computer trainings on weekends
Yes, Having employers giving them opportunity to show what they can do. So they get familiar with the workplace. i.e. 3 month training at Experica. This is a great program. Those who are knowledgeable, they are able to do their job but use the time at Experica as Canadian .experience. It is not training or teaching but allowing students to use their skills in a Canadian organization. Have more of these type of organizations or volunteering work in the private sector. It shows them what is expected. It brings immigrants what they can do. Giving them chance to prove what they can do. Not free teaching, not free training. Barrier because they are immigrants is huge. (Some change their name to more English name and they get offered jobs rather than using their own name)
We need funding for on site child care and child care workers , transportation funding for participants
Funding complementary programs, i.e. Job Developers positions, to help place the large number of job ready clients on our JSW database.

Total number of survey respondents: 35
 Total number of respondents this question: 34

38. Is there anything you would change regarding the information that you report to CIC?

Responses	Number	Percentage
Yes (see below)	16	53.33%
No	14	46.67%
Total	34	100.00%

Total number of survey respondents: 35
 Total number of respondents this question: 30

Suggested changes for reporting to CIC - Summarized (16 Respondents)

Responses	Number
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Changes to narrative section	2
Add volunteering to outcomes (add to 3 month follow-up form)	2
Report quarterly	2
Have problem(s) with iCAM	1
Report time spent with clients not eligible for workshops	1
Coordinate use of agency databases (so information does not have to be entered twice)	1
Yes	1
More follow-up categories	1
The need to report client PR data is restrictive (clients feel it is an invasion of privacy)	1
Make the reporting procedure shorter and combine it with the iCAMS if possible.	1
Suggest including amount of time spent "individually" with clients, as well as workshop time.	1
Count returning clients	1
Eliminate the necessity of the Referral Form	1
The H/R coordinator sends the report. We send information through ISAP. We do intake form and send it to ISAP. The other information is coordinated through HR. Those reports are more stressing the number of participants than the quality of service delivered and number of those who have a job.	1
Not enough information with regards to what CIC wants, reporting tool should already be in place	1

Part 7: Additional comments and suggestions

39. Please indicate the roles of all of the people who participated in filling out this survey.

Check all that apply:

Responses	Number
Workshop facilitator	30
Supervisor	18
Administration	11
Executive or senior management	11
Other (JSW support staff)	1
Board or other volunteer	0
Total	71

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 34

Comments for survey question 39

The survey was completed by the JSW Facilitators. One of the Facilitators is also the Program Coordinator.

40. Other than what you have previously stated, do you have other suggestions or comments you would like to share?

Reflect the real Canadian labour market to immigrants prior to landing, specifically introduce JSW program to immigrants prior to landing (at present, most website only introduce general settlement services which JSW is part of the services)
Facilitate strong connections between JSW and other employment programs
Feedback from other facilitators
I feel that the JSW program should allow facilitators the flexibility to deliver content to address the needs of clients, in groups as well as, on a one-to-one basis. This is because some clients are well aware of labor market information, accreditation process and the barriers. These categories of clients are fully conscious of their short-term and long-term goals and had attended employment training workshops in their home countries. They are specifically asking for individual assistance to prepare resumes, cover letters or role play cold calls and interviews. As well, I have observed that some clients are desirous to attend JSW but because they are citizens and are on work permit they cannot participate. These ineligible clients have limited knowledge of the process to search for work and would benefit greatly if they are allowed into the program.
No
Yes, open the program to immigrants who became citizens (been in Canada for up to 7 years)and refugee claimants with work permits. They too have a barrier to find employment and need our assistance
There are too many "employment assistance" programs. Newcomers are often very confused as to which to participate in. These programs often are very similar in nature. JSW and these programs need to come together and combine their resources and programs in order to help clients.
The JSW program criteria need to be more flexible that is, expand the definition of newcomer to include those who may be citizens, but who have not managed to settle effectively into the job market or find a position in keeping with their qualifications.
Time to meet with clients and to do community outreach is always an issue. Our most pressing goal is to increase our workshop numbers which requires our increased presence in the community. The number of JSW meetings, conferences and retreats do not fit easily within the 2-week workshop delivery and follow up schedule. The amount (and expense) of travel time could perhaps be applied to professional development in the form of approved courses or approved client resource materials.
We feel that this program makes a difference in the lives of newcomers. We receive many comments, letters and emails to that effect. For the facilitators, this is a stimulating and challenging program where we can interact regularly with the best and the brightest of our newest immigrants. We appreciate the straightforward nature of the program and the freedom that we have to meet our clients' needs. The success of the Job Search workshop creates a win-win situation for everyone: the newcomers and their families, Canadians, our economy and our future.
Due to restrictive criteria for client eligibility, facilitators spend too much time checking and chasing PR data that could better be spent truly helping the client.
No
Program target should be indexed on unemployment rate to be more realistic and remove some pressure on facilitators
Additional funding for employment related supports and formal training for individuals involved in administering or facilitating the JSW such as: interviewing tests, employment law, leadership, recruitment best practices, recognizing and removing barriers to employment

JSW is an intensive program that provides employment information newcomers find useful. Promotion of the program among ISAP clients and LINC students is usually effective because the time commitment is manageable.
Thanks for taking the time to contact me and hope we get the results back. It would be good to have the feed-back to us via workshop.
No
If there is any chance to get a Job Developer to this program should be very successful.
Shorten the survey next time. Some of the chart choices were duplicated (meaning fall under one group rather than separate). If they had a Best Practices training/or want feedback so everyone is not all inventing the same tool and share some of learned and successful methods and lastly, provide a tracking tool for reporting. No direction, no memo and no idea of who to talk to.
It is important that the workshop is conducted by a facilitator who understands the cultural issues and systemic barriers faced by the students.
Our JSW results will be much better if all levels of govt would work jointly with employers. Less emphasis on beaucractical structure and more on direct service.
Emphasis in the success story section of JSW reporting should not be so much given to only those who obtain a job as being successful - JSW is a wonderful program that enables people to gain soft skills and other lesser tangible qualities of confidence and self worth
No

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 23

41. Are there particular areas that you would like to see addressed in this review?

Curriculum - need to be updated so as to be in line with ELT and LINC program, Canadian workplace culture should be part of the program materials so as to assist immigrants not only to build up skills to look for job but also to maintain job
The importance of continuous education for regulatory bodies, associations and employers
Transforming delivery method to include one-on-one, addition of work placements and Job Developer, access to childcare and transportation.
No
Job development as part of JSW and creating a Job developer position. An agreement between funding bodies so that programs do not have to compete with each other to meet numbers and to avoid duplication of services. An arrangement to make JSW as the preliminary process to be referred to more sector specific programs. E.g., to get into the bridging programs, clients need to complete JSW and be referred by a Counsellor - this way clients who are ready need not spend additional time to get into bridging program and this would avoid long waiting lists. WE currently experience this with the Teachers program. There are over 100 in the waiting list, whereas at least 1/3 of them do not need to take the course. They could find employment and complete the licensing process through JSW. However, as clients think a bridging program is the only way to get back into their profession, they wait for months to get into the program. If the referral process is in place, they would save tme, money and be successful in a shorter time. Funding to have a JSW team - coordinator, facilitators, job developer, and administrative assistant.
Shortening sessions and lengthening workshop; increasing resources
Employment availability to clients.
Standardized measurements for the program and well-defined outcomes
No
More resources, Extended workshop practice sessions

To eliminate barriers that newcomers experience when they arrive in Canada.
More resources, Extended workshop practice sessions
We understand that CIC is now committed to increasing salaries/supporting the true salaries paid to facilitators by our agency. This will have a stabilizing effect and allow agencies to keep this program and its excellent work.
Would like to see best practices of organizations highlighted, shared and incorporated into JSW model, while retaining a great deal of flexibility to pick from options for service delivery.
Having more clients attend the JSW program. Clients have too many programs that they can use. I think that Newcomers should only be able to attend other program after they attend the JSW program. Also I think the wage subsidies for newcomers set up like the on-site program would also be excellent.
We would like to know more about JSWs targeted at specific populations in terms of curriculum development and outcomes.
I guess it is too late now and I am late in submitting too hope someone will contact me again.
No
If you give some transportation allowance and child care help most of the newcomers attend the workshop very happily.
Individual counselling, longer workshops that include job searching, refresher courses, specialized sessions.
Developing a common evaluation form that is worded in language that our clients can comprehend. The current form is too difficult for average clients to use
Availabilities of Computer Training Centre on weekends!
Yes, job placement and job development and mentorship more widely.
Clients are present at the workshops for 7 hours a day for 3 days. Some refreshments i.e., coffee, tea, and snacks would enable clients to concentrate/participate better.

Total number of survey respondents: 35

Total number of respondents this question: 24

Appendix E - Agency Survey Protocol

The JSW Program Review Survey

Citizenship and Immigration Canada, Ontario Region is sponsoring a review of the Job Search Workshops program across Ontario. RealWorld Systems is carrying out the review under the direction of an advisory group with representation from JSW Service Providers, Human Resources and Skills Development Canada (HRSDC), Ministry of Training, Colleges and Universities (MTCU), City of Toronto, Economic Development Division Ontario Ministry of Citizenship and Immigration, OCASI and CIC.

This review will result in recommendations for changes to the program, so it is important that all service providers have input into it.

We are asking all of the agencies that deliver JSW to tell us about the way you deliver workshops, and to get your advice about how to improve JSW. We only need one survey per agency. However, please try to involve all of your JSW staff in contributing to the survey.

The survey is quite long, reflecting the importance of detailed agency input into this exercise. In fact, the survey is a key component of the study. Your responses will inform the development of recommendations for the program review. In addition, we will share the overall results with other JSW agencies so that you can take advantage of each other's experience and ideas. We greatly appreciate your help.

The survey provides space for your comments and suggestions. You can type as much as you want but you have to use the little grey boxes provided.

The individual responses to this survey will be confidential, though we may quote some of the comments without naming the agency.

INSTRUCTIONS

Please respond by Friday, March 30, 2007 by completing the attached survey (the survey is in Word format) and email it to survey@realworldsystems.net

Thank you very much for your time and thoughtful responses.

If you have any questions or need assistance completing the survey please contact Lori Criss Powers at 1-888-596-5290 ext 12 or lpowers@realworldsystems.net.

Part 1: Description of your JSW Program

42. What is your agency's name and address?

Agency Name

Agency Address:

43. How long has your agency been delivering Job Search Workshops (JSW)?
Choose **only one** response.

- Over 5 years
- Over 2 years and less than 5 years
- Under 2 years
- Don't know

44. Which Job Search Workshop Model does your agency deliver? (**Choose all that apply**)

- Model A – Daytime sessions
- Model B – Evening sessions
- Model C – Weekend sessions

45. Please describe your typical or usual workshop:

	Model A	Model B	Model C
Usual number of total hours per workshop			
Usual number of sessions (days) per workshop			
Number of days that elapse from the first session to the last session (e.g., if the workshop sessions are given on three consecutive days, response should = 3. If it is on 4 consecutive Saturdays, response should = 21).			
Usual number of students per workshop			
Usual number of workshops that your agency delivers each month			

Usual number of facilitators and assistants who attend each session			
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Comments:

46. In general, do you feel that the length of the Job Search Workshops is:

- Just right
- Should be longer
- Should be shorter
- Don't know

Comments:

47. Do you run Job Search Workshops targeted at specific populations (e.g., women, youth, engineers, accountants, low/high literacy level, official language capacity, skilled/unskilled workers)? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes
- No (Skip to Part 2 - Question 7)
- Don't know

a. If yes, please describe these workshops in terms of their distinctive features (e.g., specific labour market information, speakers, topics, language complexity):

Specific population:
Distinctive workshop features:

a. Why do you offer these customized workshops? **Check all that apply.**

- The workshops are easier for staff to design and facilitate
- Students have more productive discussions
- Sessions can cover important topics in more depth
- Students can carry out a more targeted job search
- Students can obtain more appropriate job interviews
- Students can gain better job search skills
- Students can network with other students
- Other:
- Other:
- Other:

b. Do you have data or other evidence about the effectiveness of your customized workshops?

- Yes
- No
- Don't Know

If yes, describe:

Part 2: Intake and Assessment

48. Before admitting students into the Job Search Workshop, do you screen the students using any of the following: **(Choose all that apply)**

- English/French LINC Level 4
- Immigration status check
- Literacy level
- Access to transportation
- Stable child care arrangements
- Other (specify):
- Other (specify):
- We do not screen students (Skip to Question 8)

Comments:

a. If you screen students, what does your JSW program do for students who do not pass the screening? Choose **only one** response.

- They are usually admitted to the program anyway
- Sometimes they are admitted and sometimes they are referred elsewhere
- They are usually referred elsewhere
- Don't know

Comments:

b. If students are not accepted and are referred elsewhere after screening, what services are they referred to most often?

Comment:

49. How do you find out about students' previous knowledge and needs regarding job search skills? Pick the **one method** that you use most often.

- Interview or test them before they enter the workshop to find out their interests and existing knowledge
- Collect information from the group at the beginning of workshop to tailor it to their needs and abilities
- Be responsive to their needs as they come up during the workshop
- Provide a standard curriculum that meets most students' needs
- Don't know

Comment:

50. Do you use or recommend any self-assessment or career exploration tools (e.g., online resources) that students can use either during the workshop or after classes? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes, usually
- Sometimes
- Never (Skip to Question 10)
- Don't know (Skip to Question 10)

a. If yes or sometimes, which ones (please be specific)?

Comments (Do you find these tools helpful? Should they be used more often?)

Part 3: Workshop Components

51. Which of the following topics does your JSW program cover? Check all the topics that you spend at least 30 minutes on during the course of the workshop.

Then go back to your checked items, and find the ten topics that your workshops

Workshop Component (Topics)	Check if you spend at least 30 minutes on this topic, on average, during a typical workshop	For the top ten topics, rank them from 1 to 10. 1 means that you spend the most time on this topic, on average.	Are there any that are particularly important, or any that you think should not be taught? You can put any comments here.
a. How to develop a cover letter	<input type="checkbox"/>		
b. How to develop a resume	<input type="checkbox"/>		
c. How to proofread a resume	<input type="checkbox"/>		
d. How to customize a resume	<input type="checkbox"/>		
e. How to complete a job application	<input type="checkbox"/>		
f. How to obtain / develop references	<input type="checkbox"/>		
g. How to look for work (how to use various methods - e.g., cold calling, networking, newspaper advertisements, or internet listings, unadvertised jobs)	<input type="checkbox"/>		
h. How to contact employers	<input type="checkbox"/>		
i. How to find relevant companies	<input type="checkbox"/>		
j. How to research labour market trends and/or the local economy	<input type="checkbox"/>		
k. How to prepare for an interview	<input type="checkbox"/>		
l. Strategies for responding to interview questions	<input type="checkbox"/>		
m. Facilitator-led interview coaching sessions	<input type="checkbox"/>		
n. Facilitator-led interview role playing sessions	<input type="checkbox"/>		
o. How to dress for an interview	<input type="checkbox"/>		
p. How to conduct oneself during an interview	<input type="checkbox"/>		
TABLE CONTINUES BELOW			

usually spend the most time on. Give a rank from 1 to 10 for these top ten, with 1 being the topic that usually receives the most time. Enter comments in the third column as appropriate.

Workshop Component (Topics)	Check if you spend at least 30 minutes on this topic, on average, during a typical workshop	For the top ten topics, rank them from 1 to 10. 1 means that you spend the most time on this topic, on average.	Are there any topics that are particularly important , or any that you think should not be taught ? You can put any comments here.
q. How to market one's skills to employers and others (including introductory statements and 'elevator speeches')	<input type="checkbox"/>		
r. How to describe skills, international experience within a Canadian context	<input type="checkbox"/>		
s. How to follow-up after an interview	<input type="checkbox"/>		
t. How to manage job search expectations	<input type="checkbox"/>		
u. How to evaluate job offers (so that you don't accept jobs that will threaten your career goals)	<input type="checkbox"/>		
v. What to do if you don't have Canadian work experience	<input type="checkbox"/>		
w. How to adjust to the Canadian workplace (i.e., understand Canadian culture)	<input type="checkbox"/>		
x. How and why to use self-assessments	<input type="checkbox"/>		
y. How to manage / maintain a job	<input type="checkbox"/>		
z. How to use the services of an employment agency	<input type="checkbox"/>		
aa. How to locate / join professional organizations, associations, discussion groups, communities of practice or other groups/individuals in a specific area of interest	<input type="checkbox"/>		
bb. Information regarding legal rights (e.g., Employment Standards Act, minimum wage, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>		
cc. Job specific or vocational information	<input type="checkbox"/>		
dd. Other - please describe:	<input type="checkbox"/>		
ee. Other - please describe:	<input type="checkbox"/>		
ff. Other - please describe:	<input type="checkbox"/>		

52. Do the students complete a resume by the time they finish the workshop sessions (not including any follow-up period)? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes – almost always (90% to 100% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)
- Yes - mostly (50% to 89% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)
- Yes - sometimes (25% to 49% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)
- Yes - occasionally (10% to 24% of the students have a complete resume before the workshop ends)
- No / Hardly Ever (less than 10%) (Skip to Question 12)
- Don't know (Skip to Question 12)

Comments:

a. If yes, are the resumes reviewed for spelling, grammatical errors and clarity as a part of the workshop? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never
- Don't know

Comments:

53. What percentage of students on average would you estimate seek one-on-one assistance with their resumes after the workshop completes (i.e., during the follow-up period)? Choose **only one** response.

- Most (90% to 100% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)
- Many (50% to 89% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)
- Several (25% to 49% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)
- Some (10% to 24% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)
- Few (Less than 10% of the students seek one-on-one assistance after the workshop ends)
- Don't know

Comments:

54. Recognizing that individual needs differ, how much individual assistance **on average** would be necessary to help a student develop a resume and/or cover letter? (Please phrase answer in hours and minutes or in a range of hours and minutes e.g., “3 hours” or “1 to 2 hours”)

Comments:

55. Recognizing that individual needs differ, how much individual assistance **on average** does each student currently receive to develop a resume and/or cover letter? (Please phrase answer in hours and minutes or in a range of hours and minutes e.g., “3 hours” or “1 to 2 hours”)

Comments:

56. Are students encouraged to arrive at the workshop sessions on time and dressed appropriately for work? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never
- Don't know

Comments:

57. If students arrive at workshop sessions late, are inappropriately dressed/groomed, or if inappropriate behaviour is noted during the workshop are they given feedback to help them correct the problem? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never
- Don't know

Comments:

58. Do students have an opportunity to participate in and/or observe others perform mock interviews or role-playing exercises? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always

- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never
- Don't know

Comments:

59. Are students encouraged to think of and rehearse interview questions during class?
Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never
- Don't know

Comments:

60. Do you interact with each student to develop an after-workshop employment action plan?
Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never (Skip to Question 20)
- Don't know (Skip to Question 20)

Comments:

a. If yes, what are the components of a typical action plan?

61. Many immigrants state that one barrier to job search is that they cannot demonstrate the Canadian equivalents of their international education and experience to employers. Do your JSW workshops help students to explain their skills and experience in terms that are relevant to the Canadian jobs they are seeking? Choose **only one** response.

- Yes - Always
- Yes - Sometimes
- No - Hardly ever
- No - Never

Don't know

Comments:

Part 4: Information and Referral and Partnerships

62. What services do you successfully refer your JSW students to? **Check all that apply.**

- Job Finding Club
- Job Connect
- Career counselling
- Mentorship program
- Internship program
- Volunteer opportunities
- Employment agency (e.g., fee based headhunter)
- Academic skills upgrading
- Literacy skills upgrading
- Computers skills upgrading
- Health care
- Child care
- LINC English or French upgrading
- Other English or French upgrading
- Other (describe):

Comments:

63. What are the **most serious gaps** in appropriate services for your JSW students? **Check all that apply.**

- Job Finding Club
- Job Connect
- Career counselling
- Mentorship program
- Internship program
- Volunteer opportunities
- Employment agency (e.g., fee based headhunter)
- Academic skills upgrading
- Literacy skills upgrading
- Computers skills upgrading

- Health care
- Child care
- LINC English or French upgrading
- Other English or French upgrading
- Other (describe):

Comments:

64. How do your JSW staff find out about the needs of local employers? **Check all that apply.**

- Visit or phone local employers
- Have ongoing relationships with employers (e.g., participation in industry associations)
- Monitor the newspaper or online job ads
- Do not monitor the needs of local employers
- Don't know
- Other:

Comments:

Part 5: Workshop Objectives and Outcomes

65. What objectives are students encouraged to achieve by the end of the workshop or shortly afterwards? **Check all** the objectives below that are **explicitly communicated to students** in all of your workshops.

- Getting job interviews
- Getting job offers
- Obtaining a job
- Learning how to search for a job
- Learning how to translate international skills into relevant Canadian descriptions
- Learning how to talk to employers
- Completing a resume
- How to stay motivated during the job search process
- Completing an employment action plan
- We do not communicate specific objectives to students
- Don't know
- Other:

Comments:

66. What are the top 2 or 3 things a student needs to do successfully at the end of the workshop in order for your agency to conclude that the workshop has been successful?

a.

b.

c.

Comments:

67. How do you assess whether these objectives have been successfully achieved? What criteria do you use to judge whether or not training has been successful?

Comments:

68. If you had to guess, how would you compare the success of your agency's Job Search Workshops in relation to other JSW programs in Ontario? Choose **only one** response.

- Much better than average
- Somewhat better than average
- About average
- Lower than average
- Don't know

Please explain:

69. If you could teach **only two things** successfully to a student what would you teach?

a.

b.

Comments:

Part 6: Program Delivery, Management and Administration

70. What tools, supports or equipment would make your agency more successful in delivering Job Search Workshops?

Comments:

71. Do workshop facilitators have sufficient flexibility in designing and delivering the curriculum?

Choose **only one** response.

Yes (Skip to Question 31)

No

Don't know

If no, please comment:

72. If you had the resources to do things differently in relation to the Job Search Workshops program what would you do? (Describe up to three things)

a.

b.

c.

73. What information do you use to improve your Job Search Workshops program?

74. What do you think are the greatest strengths of your agency's Job Search Workshops?

75. What do you think are the greatest weaknesses of your agency's Job Search Workshops?

76. What professional development opportunities are needed for workshop facilitators, managers and/or administrators?

77. What are the top three barriers that you hear from your students regarding their job search efforts?

a.

b.

c.

Comments:

78. Do you have any recommendations for how these barriers might be addressed by the JSW program or CIC?

79. Is there anything you would change regarding the information that you report to CIC?

Part 7: Additional comments and suggestions

80. Please indicate the roles of all of the people who participated in filling out this survey.

Check all that apply:

- Administration
- Executive or senior management
- Supervisor
- Workshop facilitator
- Board or other volunteer
- Other - please specify:

Comments:

81. Other than what you have previously stated, do you have other suggestions or comments you would like to share?

82. Are there particular areas that you would like to see addressed in this review?

Thank you very much for your time and thoughtful responses.

If you have any questions or need assistance completing the survey please contact Lori Criss Powers at 1-888-596-5290 ext 12 or lpowers@realworldsystems.net.

Appendix F - List of Agencies Responding to Survey

1. ACCES
2. Afghan Women's Organization
3. African Community Services of Peel
4. Arab Community Centre
5. AYCE
6. Brampton Multicultural Community Centre
7. Catholic Community Services of York Region
8. Catholic Cross Cultural Services
9. Centre for Information & Community Services
10. Centre Francophone de Toronto
11. Community Micro Skills Development Centre
12. Culture Link * (1 partner-agency)
13. Davenport-Perth Neighbourhood Centre
14. Dixie - Bloor Neighbourhood Centre
15. Durham Region Unemployed Help Centre
16. Folk Arts Council of St. Catharines
17. Halton Multicultural Council
18. Immigrant Women Services Ottawa
19. Intercede
20. Job Start
21. JVS of Greater Toronto
22. Kitchener- Waterloo Multicultural Centre
23. Lebanese and Arab Social Services Association
24. London Cross Cultural Learner Centre
25. Malton Neighbourhood Services
26. Ottawa Community Immigrant Services Organization
27. Settlement & Integration Services Organization
28. Skills for Change
29. Tamil Eelam Society of Canada
30. The Catholic Immigration Centre
31. Thorncliffe Neighbourhood Office
32. Woodgreen Community Services of Toronto
33. Working Women Community Centre
34. YMCA of Sarnia-Lambton
35. YMCA of Windsor-Essex County

Appendix G - Employment Service Experts Interviewed

Name - Title	Organization
Doner, Joyce - VR Consultant	Sibley and Associates
Laroche, Lionel, Ph.D., P.Eng. - Author, President	MCB Solutions
McIsaac, Elizabeth – Exec.Director	Toronto Region Immigrant Employment Council
Murray, Katrina – Project Director	Canadian Immigration Integration Project, Association of Canadian Community Colleges
Serieaux-Halls, Leonard - IT Systems Manager	CH2M Hill
Singer, Rhonda - President	Progress Career Planning Institute
Switzer, Bruce - President	Integration Resources, Ottawa
Toscani, Robert	Career Quest, Inc.